

UNIVERSITY OF SURREY

**Tracing the Structure and Evolutionary
History of the Small Magellanic Cloud with
Galactic Archaeology**

Joanna D. Sakowska

Supervisor: Dr Noelia E. D. Noël

External supervisor: Dr Tomás Ruiz-Lara

Co-supervisor: Dr Denis Erkal

Internal PhD VIVA examiner: Prof. Justin I. Read

External PhD VIVA examiner: Prof. Claudia Maraston

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Declaration of Authorship

This thesis and the work to which it refers are the results of my own efforts. Any ideas, data, images or text resulting from the work of others (whether published or unpublished) are fully identified as such within the work and attributed to their originator in the text, bibliography or in footnotes. This thesis has not been submitted in whole or in part for any other academic degree or professional qualification. I agree that the University has the right to submit my work to the plagiarism detection service Turnitin@UK for originality checks. Whether or not drafts have been so-assessed, the University reserves the right to require an electronic version of the final document (as submitted) for assessment as above.¹

Aspects of this work have appeared in, or are due to appear in the following works and publications:

- J. D. Sakowska, *Structure and Evolution of the Small Magellanic Cloud*. Report submitted to the University of Surrey, December 2021.
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Signed: JOANNA D. SAKOWSKA

Date: 22nd May 2024

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Abstract

Understanding how galaxies form and evolve remains one of the biggest open questions in modern day astrophysics. Stars play a crucial role in deciphering galaxy formation as they retain information about the conditions of their host galaxies at the time of their birth. By resolving individual stars and studying their properties, we can uncover direct links to their host's past history, performing what is known as "galactic archaeology". The Magellanic Clouds (MCs), visible from Earth as "milky patches" in the sky, provide a unique window into how galaxies interact and evolve, offering valuable insights into the Lambda Cold Dark Matter (Λ CDM) model that governs the behaviour of our Universe. The Small Magellanic Cloud (SMC), in particular, exhibits a highly disrupted morphology, encoding clues on its past interactions with the neighbouring Large Magellanic Cloud (LMC). The goal of the present thesis is to probe galaxy evolution by producing a state-of-the-art picture of the complex evolutionary history of the SMC. First, I present a detailed star formation history (SFH) of a shell-like structure in the SMC's northeastern outskirts. I provide direct evidence that this structure formed due to the complex interplay between the SMC, the LMC, and the Milky Way (MW) over the last ~ 2 Gyrs. To derive the SFH, I develop a new method that uses Red Clump (RC) stars to quantify the line-of-sight depth of the region, incorporating this depth into the SFH derivation. Theoretical tests with mock stellar populations confirm the method's robustness, showing that accounting for the SMC's line-of-sight depth results in more accurate age and metallicity determinations. Following this, I derive the SFH for the entire SMC and its peripheral region. The SMC has experienced star formation enhancements ~ 2 Gyr, ~ 1.3 Gyr, ~ 0.9 Gyr, ~ 0.5 Gyr, and ~ 0.2 Gyr ago, as well as one ongoing episode, all linked to the interactions with the LMC. The radially integrated SFH reveals a positive age gradient across the SMC, and several plausible causes for it are evaluated. I derive a mean metallicity, $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -0.94 \pm_{0.07}^{0.06}$ for the entire SMC from photometric metallicity maps, which show subtle gradients towards the LMC. Finally, I present technical work towards a comprehensive exploration of the Magellanic periphery for ancient ultra-faint dwarf galaxies/clusters associated with the MCs. The results presented in this thesis demonstrate the influence of the LMC (and the MW) on the structure and evolution of the SMC, shedding new light on how the SMC arrived at its current, complex state.

Dedicated to my loving grandad.

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Although this PhD reflects the research done over the last ~4 years at the University of Surrey, the scientific thinking began ~8 years ago when I joined as an undergraduate student. At first I didn't do well enough in my A-Level exams for a Physics degree but, by some strange luck, I got accepted onto a Physics bachelor thanks to someone's admin mistake (don't tell anyone). Now I'm leaving with a PhD and too many incredible things to say. I wish I could thank everybody individually that contributed to my education and development as an Astronomer over all these years.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 The cosmological context

The widely accepted standard model of cosmology, the Lambda Cold Dark Matter (Λ CDM, or LCDM; e.g., [Einstein 1919](#); [White & Rees 1978](#); [Blumenthal et al. 1984](#); [Moore et al. 1999](#)), describes the evolution of the Universe and the large scale structures within. The name combines three core ingredients that are thought to govern the expansion and fate of the Universe and its large-scale structures: dark energy (Λ , the cosmological constant), dark matter (DM), and visible matter itself. Modern studies of the Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB), the signature radiation produced by the Big Bang approximately 13.8 billion years ago, parametrise the current Universe as $\sim 70\%$ dark energy, $\sim 25\%$ dark matter, and only $\sim 5\%$ visible, baryonic matter (galaxies, stars, gas, and us, [Planck Collaboration et al. 2020](#)).

Historically, observational evidence for the “dark” ingredients - dark energy and dark matter - emerged from the study of galactic light. In the 1920s Georges Lemâitre and Edwin Hubble independently found a link between a galaxy’s distance from Earth and its redshift, arriving at the same conclusion: galaxies are receding from us with a velocity proportional to distance ([Lemaître 1927](#); [Hubble 1929](#); [Nussbaumer & Bieri 2011](#)). Given the Universe is isotropic and homogeneous on large enough scales we can infer that, at every point in the Universe, galaxies are moving away from us. We now know that this is due to a Universal expansion fuelled by dark energy. This important discovery confirmed the result derived earlier by the cosmologist Alexander Friedmann, who adapted Einstein’s field equations for the geometry and behaviour of our Universe to show a Universal expansion is mathematically possible ([Friedmann 1922](#)):

$$\dot{R}^2 - \frac{8\pi G}{3}\rho R^2 = -kc^2 \quad (1.1)$$

where R is a scaling parameter, G is the gravitational constant, ρ is the density of the Universe, c is the speed of light in a vacuum and k is the curvature parameter that describes the geometry of the Universe. The Friedmann equation therefore describes the relationship between the density of the Universe and its geometry. If $k = +1$ then the Universe is dense enough to collapse under its own gravity, deeming it ‘closed’. However, if $k = -1$, then the Universe is not dense enough for a collapse and expands indefinitely (an ‘open’ Universe). Studies of the CMB favour something in between, i.e. $k = 0$, with implications of a ‘critical’ density ρ_c at which, once

reached, Universal expansion would stop. This is considered to be a ‘flat’ Universe (Bennett et al. 2003; Planck Collaboration et al. 2016). It is useful to define the density of the Universe as relative to the critical density, i.e. the density parameter $\Omega = \rho/\rho_c$. Using the field equations we can show that the density parameter relies on the delicate balance between matter, radiation and vacuum over time:

$$\Omega(t) = \Omega_\Lambda(t) + \Omega_m(t) + \Omega_r(t) \quad (1.2)$$

and, further, that this vacuum possesses a *negative* energy density. This term is believed to represent the outward expansion of the Universe in the form of dark energy. Observations of type IA supernovae throughout the Universe agree that not only is the Universe expanding, but it is doing so at an *accelerating* rate. Type IA supernovae act as ‘standard candles’ given that they shine with the same intrinsic luminosity everywhere in the Universe. By comparing their apparent brightness at high redshift to a well-calibrated measurement we can infer their distances from us. Riess et al. (1998); Perlmutter et al. (1999) presented convincing results for dark energy by demonstrating that the distances to well-observed Type IA SNe are further than expected and are therefore moving away from us at an accelerating rate. A review on dark energy can be found in Mortonson et al. (2013).

One of the most striking pieces of evidence for dark matter was presented by the Swiss-American astronomer Fritz Zwicky in the 1930s. Zwicky applied the virial theorem (Clausius 1870) to calculate the mass and velocity dispersion of the Coma cluster and found a significant discrepancy between the calculated velocity dispersion against the measured velocity dispersion along the line-of-sight (Zwicky 1933, 1937). Zwicky thus concluded that “*dark matter is present in much greater amount than luminous matter*”, a conclusion also supported by Sinclair Smith’s mass estimate of the Virgo Cluster around the same time (Smith 1936). In the decades that followed these results on the mass discrepancy in galactic clusters were met with much scepticism and a review of these discussions can be found in Bertone & Hooper (2018). In the meantime, traces of evidence for anomalous mass in galaxies came in from studies of galactic rotation curves (e.g. Babcock 1939; Volders 1959) although no consensus was yet reached partly due to instrumental capabilities limiting the quality and amount of data available at the time. As technology advanced, evidence for DM became irrefutable with the increasing amount of data across the electromagnetic spectrum on galactic rotation curves consistently showing flat profiles (e.g. Freeman 1970; Rubin & Ford 1970; Bosma & van der Kruit 1979; Rubin et al. 1980; van Albada et al. 1985). Famous examples of additional evidence for DM include observations of gravitational lensing, i.e. the bending of light from a background source as it encounters a mass concentration on its path, (Einstein 1917); the Lyman-alpha (Lyman- α) forest, i.e. a series of absorption lines of neutral hydrogen (HI) in the spectra of distant galaxies and quasars which is sensitive to the density of matter it encounters (e.g. Weinberg et al. 2003); or the temperature distribution of hot gas in galaxies and galaxy clusters (e.g. Hansen et al. 2011), to name a few.

1.1.1 Galaxy formation under Λ CDM

According to the Λ CDM cosmological model, the Universe was isotropic and highly homogeneous following the Big Bang. Nevertheless, tiny fluctuations at the quantum level during the inflation period (see Liddle & Lyth 2000 for a detailed description of inflation) grew into density

perturbations which pulled DM to clump together as the Universe cooled down. This cosmic DM web attracted baryonic gas and, as the density perturbations gravitationally collapsed into DM ‘halos’, shocked the gas to its virial temperature causing it to settle into hydrostatic equilibrium in the potential well of the DM halo. Over time the gas cooled, flowed inwards, collapsed under its own gravity and eventually formed the very first stars (Mo et al. 2010). A key prediction of Λ CDM is that DM halos grow in size via the accretion of smaller ones (e.g., White & Rees 1978). DM halos therefore provide the scaffolding on which visible galactic structures form in and allow them to interact, merge, and grow visibly. This is called the ‘hierarchical mass assembly’ process, and it has been widely observed throughout the Universe via interactions and mergers of galaxies into larger galaxies, such as our own Milky Way (MW, $M_{total} \sim 10^{12}M_{\odot}$) and clusters of galaxies (e.g., $M_{total} \sim 10^{15}M_{\odot}$). As galaxies interact and merge they experience tidal forces namely due to the gravitational forces at play between the galaxies and their respective DM halos. Indeed, tidal interactions ‘strip’ material off galaxies, affecting their stellar, gaseous and dark matter content, and perturbing their morphology by producing so called tidal features. Tidal features are diffuse, non-uniform stellar structures which extend out from galaxies and visually trace incoming and completed merger events. The nature of the tidal feature depends on the accretion event, and some visual classifications include ‘tails’, ‘streams’, ‘shells’ and ‘fans’ (e.g. Morales et al. 2018; Martínez-Delgado et al. 2019; Miro-Carretero et al. 2024). Through comparisons of observations with cosmological simulations of tidally interacting galaxies, we can uncover the evolutionary history of the galaxy at hand and probe the robustness of Λ CDM itself (e.g. Khalid et al. 2024; Walder et al. 2024).

While the Λ CDM model has been extremely successful at reproducing observations across scales larger than ~ 1 Mpc, Λ CDM has faced several challenges for distribution scales $\lesssim 1$ Mpc and for masses $M_* \leq 10^9 M_{\odot}$, corresponding to the ‘dwarf’ galaxy mass regime (Bullock & Boylan-Kolchin, 2017). Some of such issues include the ‘missing satellites problem’ (Moore et al. 1999; Klypin et al. 1999), related to the fact that cosmological simulations predict thousands of DM sub-halos around a MW size galaxy but only dozens of dwarf galaxies have been discovered around the MW; the ‘cusp-core’ problem, where friction arises between the inferred DM content from the kinematics of stars inhabiting the inner parts of gas-rich dwarf galaxies and the prediction from numerical models (Read & Gilmore, 2005); and the ‘too big to fail problem’, related to the difficulty in explaining both the measured kinematics and the observed number density of dwarf galaxies within the Λ CDM (Read et al. 2006, Boylan-Kolchin et al. 2011). For a complete review of all the small-scale problems see Bullock & Boylan-Kolchin (2017) and references therein.

Although the above can seem detrimental for Λ CDM, these issues do not necessarily indicate fundamental drawbacks for the underlying cosmological model. The ‘missing satellites’ issue can be explained if an appropriate mapping between the sub-halos and observed satellites is performed (e.g., Kim et al. 2018). The new groundbreaking method presented by Read & Erkal (2019) and based on abundance matching shows that there is no basis for such a “missing satellites” issue in the MW above a typical dwarf galaxy pre-infall mass of $\sim 10^9 M_{\odot}$. In the case of the ‘cusp-core’ problem, Read et al. (2019) presented a solution showing that the discrepancy comes from the fact that the initial numerical models assumed a DM only Universe; when extra ingredients such as gas cooling, star formation, and gas blow-out due to exploding stars are added, the inner DM content of the gas-rich dwarf galaxy at hand is lowered. Finally, with regards to the ‘too big to fail’ issue, several solutions have been studied, from changes to our ideas of DM (e.g., Spergel & Steinhardt 2000), to DM “heating” due to bursty star formation

causing the “cuspy” DM density profile to flatten and resemble more that of a “core” (e.g., [Read & Gilmore 2005](#)).

1.1.2 The importance of dwarf galaxies

FIGURE 1.1: Cut out images of nine Local Group dwarf galaxies, selected to illustrate a range of stellar masses (six orders of magnitude) and different morphologies. Image credit: [Bullock & Boylan-Kolchin \(2017\)](#)

As mentioned in Section 1.1, detailed observational inferences on the properties, behaviour, and number of galaxies of stellar mass $M_* \leq 10^9 M_\odot$ have been pivotal in calibrating our ideas on Λ CDM. In fact, galaxy mass distribution models and observations suggest that dwarf galaxies are the most abundant in the Universe (e.g., [Baldry et al. 2008, 2012](#)). One technique by which we can study the ages, metallicities, and properties of dwarf (and more massive) galaxies in a largely statistical manner is by observing galaxies at increasing redshift in the distant Universe. This involves fitting the integrated light we receive from their unresolved stars (e.g., from surveys like CANDELS, the Cosmic Assembly Near-infrared Deep Extragalactic Survey; [Grogin et al. 2011](#)) to models. By fitting multiple Simple Stellar Population models (SSPs, see [Maraston](#)

1998 for a definition) to their Spectral Energy Distribution (SED) we can probe distant galaxies of different masses, morphologies, and diverse environments. Examples of SSP libraries include Starburst99 (Leitherer et al., 1999), BC03 (Bruzual & Charlot, 2003), GALEV (Kotulla et al., 2009), MILES (Sánchez-Blázquez et al., 2006; Vazdekis, 1999; Vazdekis et al., 2010), and *MaStar* (Maraston et al., 2020). This exciting approach means we can look back in cosmic time and probe galaxies across the galaxy evolution spectrum, shedding light on the youngest galaxies in the Universe. Unfortunately, a prevailing disadvantage of this method is that it relies on our ability to correctly identify progenitor galaxies, with potential biases at play. Moreover, we are limited on the level of detail we can obtain about the system's properties and morphology given the insufficient resolution to dissect the galaxy at hand and examine individual stars.

Another approach is to study the formation and history of resolved systems, the so-called 'Galactic archaeology'. Although nearby objects are scarce and do not provide the statistical significance that the early Universe does (in terms of the number of systems), the study of close galaxies, where we can resolve their individual stars, provides a detailed fossil record of the history of a system. Hence, the Local Group (LG) of galaxies - the collection of dwarf galaxies around the two large spiral galaxies MW and Andromeda - offers an outstanding laboratory to carry out Galactic archaeology, providing a treasure trove of information on their ages, metallicities, kinematics and spatial distributions. Within the LG there are many 'flavours' of dwarf galaxies, each possessing their unique mass-to-light ratios, morphologies, star formation histories (SFHs, to be discussed in Section 1.3), etc. In Figure 1.1 I depict a selection of LG dwarf galaxies- the top row contains some of the largest (by stellar mass) and therefore most luminous dwarfs, corresponding to the 'bright dwarf' classification ($M_* \leq 10^{7-9} M_\odot$, classifications adopted from [Boylan-Kolchin et al. 2011](#)), the middle row corresponds to the 'classical dwarfs' ($M_* \leq 10^{5-7} M_\odot$) and the bottom row shows the 'ultra-faint' dwarfs (UFDs, $M_* \leq 10^{2-5} M_\odot$). The Large Magellanic Cloud (LMC, to be introduced later), WLM, and Pegasus are dwarf irregular (dIrr) galaxies, which typically have ongoing star formation due to their gas reservoirs. The remaining six are dwarf Spheroidal (dSph) and dwarf Elliptical (dE) galaxies, which are not currently forming stars as their gas supply has almost run out. Some bright dwarfs such as the LMC have been known since the beginnings of humankind as they can be seen with the naked eye from Earth. The classical dwarfs were the faintest galaxies known until two decades ago when the arrival of digital surveys such as the Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS, [York et al. 2000](#)), the Dark Energy Survey, (DES, [The Dark Energy Survey Collaboration 2005](#)), and the Panoramic Survey Telescope and Rapid Response System (Pan-STARRS, [Chambers et al. 2016](#)), uncovered a wealth of ultra-faint dwarf galaxies (UFDs) around the MW and Andromeda.

FIGURE 1.2: Absolute magnitude versus azimuthally averaged half-light radius plot taken from Cerny et al. (2023c, including Sakowska). The newly-discovered ultra-faint stellar system DELVE-6 is depicted with a yellow star. Its nature as a UFD or UFC is ambiguous. See Appendix B of Cerny et al. 2023c for further info on classifications.

Since the first UFD was observed, almost two decades ago (Willman et al., 2005a,b), the discoveries of these small systems have dramatically increased. UFDs represent the smallest, faintest ($L \leq 10^5 L_\odot$), least chemically evolved ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -2$ to -3.5), most ancient ($\tau \geq 12$ Gyr), and most dark matter dominated galaxies known (see Simon 2019 and references therein for an in-depth review of the properties of UFDs). The proximity of the systems within our Local Group deems it the best hunting ground for UFDs and ultra-faint clusters (UFCs). As of writing, only ~ 60 UFDs/UFCs around the MW are known¹. Several key properties of UFDs deem them important contributors to our understanding of cosmology. Observations and models agree that UFDs likely formed before the epoch of reionisation in the early Universe (see, e.g., Zaroubi 2013) approximately 1 Gyr after the Big Bang. UFDs represent both the earliest stages of galaxy formation and the conditions prevalent in the early Universe, as they likely underwent negligible to no further evolution (e.g., Bovill & Ricotti 2009, 2011; Wheeler et al. 2015). Although the DM halos of UFDs are some of the smallest in the Universe, the comparison between their DM halo mass (simulations suggest as large as $\sim 10^8 M_\odot$ for a star-forming UFD, e.g., Bovill & Ricotti 2009; Safarzadeh et al. 2018) against a significantly less massive baryonic component is significant. Essentially “dark-matter capsules”, observations of UFDs’ stellar motions, internal dynamics, and spatial distributions help test predictions of different dark matter models at the

¹https://github.com/apace7/local_volume_database

smallest scales (see, e.g., the EDGE simulations: [Rey et al. 2019](#)). Indeed, increasing discoveries of UFDs within the LG ease the ‘Missing satellite’ problem.

The increasing number of detections of ultra-faint stellar systems in the Local Group poses a new challenge in galaxy evolution: discriminating between a UFD or a UFC is tricky. Globular clusters are thought to be more spatially concentrated than dwarf galaxies and, most importantly, no DM has been found in them (see, e.g., [Moore et al. 2006](#)). Globular clusters could traditionally be distinguished from dwarf galaxies using the size-luminosity relation. In [Figure 1.2](#), taken from [Cerny et al. \(2023c\)](#), including [Sakowska](#), we show the location of the DELVE-6 stellar system in the size-luminosity space. DELVE-6 was recently discovered (as of writing) in the DECam DELVE survey (to be introduced in [Chapter 5](#)). It is not immediately clear if DELVE-6 is a cluster or a galaxy - its half-light radius falls in between the expectation for a cluster or a galaxy. So far, an effective classification method consists of measuring the velocity dispersion - dwarf galaxies should exhibit a higher rotation velocity thanks to their DM content contributing to a higher total mass. Unfortunately, this means obtaining spectroscopic data for the object at hand, which is not always readily available.

1.2 The Magellanic Clouds

The largest satellite dwarf galaxies of the MW, the Small and Large Magellanic Cloud (SMC/LMC), are excellent workplaces to investigate the processes involved in galaxy evolution and formation. Thanks to their visibility from Earth, the Magellanic Clouds (MCs) have captivated civilisations in the southern hemisphere for thousands of years. Visually, the LMC can be described as an irregular galaxy with a very prominent off-centre bar and a disc seen face-on from Earth. The SMC is a dwarf irregular galaxy with a very intricate geometry, heavily affected by tidal interactions, likely with the LMC ([Noël et al. 2013, 2015](#); [Carrera et al. 2017](#); [De Leo et al. 2020](#)). At ~ 50 kpc and ~ 62 kpc ([Pietrzyński et al. 2013](#) / [Scowcroft et al. 2016](#)) from us, the MCs are the closest pair of interacting galaxies, offering an outstanding opportunity to study galaxy mergers in exquisite detail. The interactive past of the MCs produced several features of interest such as the Magellanic Bridge (MB, [Hindman et al. 1963](#); [Nidever et al. 2013](#)), composed of tidally stripped neutral hydrogen gas and stars of all ages, including young stars likely formed in-situ during a recent interaction $\sim 150 - 250$ Myr ago (e.g., [Oliveira et al. 2023](#)) and intermediate age stars likely tidally stripped by the LMC ([Noël et al. 2013, 2015](#); [Carrera et al. 2017](#); [Grady et al. 2021](#)). Another structure is the Magellanic Stream (discovered by [Mathewson et al. 1974](#), see [D’Onghia & Fox 2016](#) for a review), a tail of HI gas spanning *at least* $\sim 140^\circ$ in the night sky ([Nidever et al. 2010](#)) tracing the past orbit of the MCs. There is also the Leading Arm, *leading* the MCs ([Putman et al. 1998](#)), a $60^\circ \times 80^\circ$ HI gas patch ahead of the MCs. The reproducibility of these features is an important checkpoint in modelling the interactive history of the MCs. Assessing how the MCs arrived to their current state has implications on our understanding of the evolutionary path of a dwarf galaxy that is undergoing accretion by a larger one.

Indeed, prevailing dynamical models of the MCs suggest that they are, most likely, in-falling into the MW. As to whether or not the MCs are completing their first or second passage around the MW is an interesting question. For a long time, the MCs were believed to have completed several passages around the MW (e.g., [Tremaine 1976](#); [Gardiner & Noguchi 1996](#); [Diaz & Bekki 2012](#)). With the arrival of very high precision, multi-epoch proper motion (PM) data of the MCs from the Hubble Space Telescope (HST), it became clear the MCs exhibit a tangential velocity much

higher than expected for two stable satellites of the MW (Kallivayalil et al. 2006a,b). Dynamical models of the MCs using PM data suggested the MCs are on their first passage around the MW, and thus the first passage scenario became dominant (e.g., Besla et al. 2007; Costa et al. 2011; Besla et al. 2012; Kallivayalil et al. 2013). Prevalent models suggest that the MCs collided ~ 1.5 -2 Gyr ago (Diaz & Bekki 2012; Lucchini et al. 2021) in agreement with the derived ages of the Leading Arm and Stream (Nidever et al. 2008; Fox et al. 2018) and the age of the LMC's spiral arm (Ruiz-Lara et al. 2020). Model realisations in which the SMC had three pericentric passages around the LMC ~ 2 , ~ 1 , ~ 0.4 Gyrs ago match kinematic studies of the LMC's periphery Navarrete et al. 2023; Cullinane et al. 2022. The next close encounter occurred approximately ~ 250 -150 Myr ago, forming the Magellanic Bridge (e.g., Besla et al. 2007, 2012; Choi et al. 2022) and widely evidenced by observational studies (see previous examples). Nevertheless, the current level of uncertainty in both the MW's potential and LMC's parameters means alternatives to the first passage scenario are still being explored (e.g., Vasiliev 2024).

FIGURE 1.3: Map of star clusters and dwarf galaxies in the Magellanic system, plotted in Magellanic Stream coordinates from Nidever et al. (2008). Black points are star clusters from Bica et al. (2020). Red dots are recently discovered UFCs. Blue triangles are candidates and confirmed UFDs potentially associated with the MCs. The SMCNOD overdensity, which has an ambiguous nature, is shown in orange (Pieres et al. 2017). The yellow star represents DELVE-6. See (Cerny et al., 2023c) for further information.

The LMC/SMC are near enough such that their stellar populations (SPs) can also be resolved

from ground-based telescopes (such as VMC, [Cioni et al. 2011](#); SMASH, [Nidever et al. 2017](#); and DELVE, [Drlica-Wagner et al., 2021](#), including [Sakowska](#)). The arrival of large field-of-view, multi-CCD cameras such as the Dark Energy Camera (DECam, [Flaugher et al. 2015](#)) produced outstanding, deep data on the intricate peripheries of the MC, shedding new light on the complexity of the Magellanic system. As previously discussed, DECam has contributed to many discoveries around the MW, and the MCs are no exception. In [Figure 1.3](#) I show the concentration of UFCs (red) and UFDs (blue) uncovered in the Magellanic periphery ([Cerny et al. 2023c](#)), contextualises the location of DELVE-6 (introduced in [Section 1.1.2](#)). The MCs and the Magellanic Bridge are traced with star clusters taken from [Bica et al. 2020](#) (depicted with black circles). The concentration of UFDs and UFCs in the Magellanic periphery is notable—*could the Magellanic Clouds possess their own population of satellites?* Indeed, simulations suggest that many of these newly-discovered systems have a Magellanic origin and are currently undergoing accretion by the MW (e.g., [Deason et al. 2015](#); [Drlica-Wagner et al. 2015](#); [Wetzel et al. 2015](#); [Jethwa et al. 2016](#); [Sales et al. 2017](#); [Jahn et al. 2019](#); [Nadler et al. 2020](#)) supporting theoretical predictions of a satellite population around the MCs ([Lynden-Bell 1976](#); [D’Onghia & Lake 2008](#)). Membership of satellites is mostly assessed using space telescope PM data, and given the uncertainties of these measurements it is challenging associating UFDs with the MCs (e.g., [Kallivayalil et al. 2018](#); [Simon 2018](#); [Patel et al. 2020](#); [Pardy et al. 2020](#)). Nevertheless, the very presence of UFDs around the MCs forms another important consideration in modelling their past orbital history. [Vasiliev \(2024\)](#) demonstrate that a second passage scenario could explain the observed ‘planar’ distribution of these galaxies around the MCs if the satellites underwent tidal stripping during a first pericentre passage ~ 5 to 10 Gyr ago.

A contiguous census of stellar systems in the Magellanic periphery with deep data from ground-based telescopes holds vast potential in uncovering many more faint stellar systems. This forms part of the work I present in [Chapter 5](#) with the DECam DELVE survey. The discovery of more satellites has the potential to shed new light on the Magellanic system and how it arrived at its current state. The MCs are, indeed, a fascinating workplace for galactic archaeology.

1.3 Star Formation Histories

Star formation is one of the fundamental processes driving galaxy evolution. It has been shown that a galaxy’s star formation rate (SFR), gas content, and morphology are influenced by the environment in which it resides (see e.g., [Gallart et al. 2015](#)). This is because external factors such as tidal stripping (see [Section 1.1.1](#)) or ram pressure stripping enable gas compression, enrichment or removal which, in turn, enhances or decreases the SFR accordingly. As galaxies move through a dense medium, such as a cluster of galaxies or another galaxy’s gaseous halo, they can experience ram pressure due to the drag forces present. If the ram pressure is sufficiently strong it can lead to gas stripping and, in some cases, stop star formation all together “quenching” the galaxy (e.g. [Gunn & Gott 1972](#); [Mo et al. 2010](#)). On the other hand, in some cases star formation is enhanced if the remaining non-stripped gas is compressed by ram pressure ([Dressler & Gunn 1983](#); [Gavazzi et al. 1995](#)). Star Formation Histories (SFHs), i.e. the star formation rate and chemical enrichment rate as a function of cosmic time (SFR(t) and Z(t)), help pinpoint what physical processes aid the formation of a galaxy’s stellar content. SFH determinations from deep photometric data present the past history of a galaxy in such detail that we can identify potential epochs of synchronised star formation or quiescence periods between systems ([Massana et al. 2022](#), including [Sakowska](#)). Hence, the SFH of a galaxy can be used to search for past

interactions with nearby galaxies, permitting us to unpick the fossil record of a galaxy's past in exquisite detail.

As alluded to in 1.2, the proximity of the MCs allows us to obtain the most detailed SFH of two interacting galaxies possible. The SMC/LMC interactions not only influence their kinematics but also create local bursts of star formation. As an example of this, [Massana et al. \(2020\)](#) found that the young population in the SMC shows a 'jump' in the density profile at ~ 4.5 kpc from the SMC centre indicating a heavily disturbed younger component, as opposed to the smoother profile shown by the surrounding older population that suggests a very quiet early SFH, as expected in isolated dwarfs (i.e. [Cole et al. 2014](#); [Rey et al. 2020](#)). Indeed, the highly disrupted nature of the SMC (e.g., [De Leo et al. 2020](#)) makes it an interesting galaxy to dissect with SFH studies. Moreover, the stellar masses, SFHs, and interaction histories of the MCs are also expected to influence the properties of their satellite populations (e.g., [Jethwa et al. 2016](#); [Jahn et al. 2019](#); [Dooley et al. 2017](#)).

In summary, we can use the spatially resolved SFHs of the MCs to search for observational hints of their shared interactive history. These can be used to constrain dynamical modelling of the MCs around the MW and shed light on their evolutionary path. This forms part of the work presented in Chapters 2 and 4.

1.3.1 The colour-magnitude diagram

FIGURE 1.4: An example model colour-magnitude diagram (CMD) showing the locations of stars across different age intervals (13 Gyr ago - present). To compute this I assumed a constant SFR with $Z = 0.002$ and a Kroupa initial mass fraction (IMF, [Kroupa 2001](#)). The effect of binary stars has been removed. Throughout this thesis, I used the solar-scaled BASTI-IAC library ([Pietrinferni et al. 2004](#)). The key phases of interest are marked: MS (main sequence), TO (turn-off, commonly referred to as main sequence turn-off or MSTO), HB (horizontal branch), RC (red clump), RGB (red giant branch), AGB (asymptotic giant branch). See text for details.

Studies of resolved stellar populations began in the 1940s with W. Baade who first resolved Andromeda’s dwarf satellites into individual stars. W. Baade concluded that the SPs observed contrasted to those commonly observed in our Galaxy (Baade 1944a,b). Since then, the field has seen a massive transformation with the influx of advanced, high-resolution space (such as the HST) and ground-based telescopes with wide-field camera detectors that could obtain detailed photometry. This enabled the production of comprehensive colour-magnitude diagrams (CMDs) containing individual stars. CMDs act as blueprints of galaxies as they hold key evolutionary parameters (i.e. age, metallicity, Initial Mass Function) that guide us to understanding how the galaxy arrived at its current state.

The proximity of the Magellanic Clouds allows us to obtain detailed CMDs, down to the oldest main-sequence turnoff (oMSTO). In Figure 1.4 I provide an example theoretical CMD with the main stellar evolution phases annotated. To compute this CMD, I set a constant SFR with fixed metallicity $Z = 0.002$ (consistent with the SMC’s metallicity) and a Kroupa initial mass fraction (IMF, Kroupa 2001). Throughout this thesis, I used the solar-scaled BASTI-IAC library (Pietrinferni et al. 2004). For illustration purposes, the effect of binary stars has been removed². The key phases of interest are marked: The main sequence (MS), where stars spend 90% of their life burning hydrogen (H) at their cores (e.g., chapter 22 of Kippenhahn et al. 2013); the turn-off (TO), commonly referred to as MS turn-off (oMSTO), the point where stars leave the MS after exhausting the H in their core; the red giant branch (RGB, e.g., chapter 2 of Karakas & Lattanzio 2014), where stars have an inert He core and a H-burning envelope; the horizontal branch (HB) and Red Clump (RC), where stars are fusing He in their cores (e.g., Girardi & Salaris 2001; Cassisi & Salaris 2013; Girardi 2016); and the asymptotic giant branch (AGB) where stars exhausted the He in their cores (e.g., chapter 3 and 4 of Karakas & Lattanzio 2014). A thorough review of the utility of each stellar evolution phase in SFH determinations, and a comparison of the libraries available, is provided by Gallart et al. (2005).

We can use state-of-the-art algorithms to quantitatively compare observed CMDs to model CMDs in which observational uncertainties are modelled. This, in turn, reconstructs the observed CMD (‘solution’ CMD) from which we can read the SFH. This is considered the most reliable procedure to obtain detailed SFHs of nearby systems (Gallart et al. 2005) and has been extensively used (e.g., Gallart et al. 1999; Tolstoy et al. 2009; Cignoni et al. 2012; Bernard et al. 2018; Ruiz-Lara et al. 2018, 2021; Rusakov et al. 2021). The Magellanic Clouds are no exception to this well-known technique (e.g., Harris & Zaritsky 2004; Noël et al. 2007, 2009; Weisz et al. 2013; Rubele et al. 2015, 2018; Ruiz-Lara et al. 2020; Massana et al. 2022).

1.3.2 Structure of the Small Magellanic Cloud

The need to investigate the effect of the SMC’s structure on its spatial SFH determinations is fuelled by the fact that SMC has an elongated, irregular morphology with a considerable extension along its line-of-sight (see, e.g., Hatzidimitriou & Hawkins 1989, Hatzidimitriou et al. 1989, Gardiner & Hawkins 1991, Gardiner & Hatzidimitriou 1992, Crowl et al. 2001). These line-of-sight depth effects can be seen in the observed CMDs: the sharp RC region, shown in Figure 1.4, appears vertically ‘smudged’ in observed magnitude, suggestive of a strong dispersion of stellar positions away from the distance modulus used to the region at hand. The line-of-sight

²For the results presented in this thesis, I set the binary fraction as $\beta = 50\%$ with a minimum mass ratio of 0.1. This is consistent with Massana et al. (2022) who also computes SFHs from the SMASH survey data.

depths create an extra layer of observational effects on the observed CMDs that must be taken into account in quantitative SFH determinations. As such, obtaining accurate SFHs of the SMC from CMD reconstruction is challenging.

Tracing stellar populations of all ages, variable stars constitute outstanding objects to obtain accurate line-of-sight depths for the SMC that can be used to find and assess SFHs. The young Classic Cepheids (CCs; typically $\lesssim 1$ Gyr old) are likely to have formed in-situ, making them excellent imprints of the structures formed during recent LMC/SMC interactions. Historically, one of the first scientific articles on the SMC was Henrietta S. Leavitt's work on the SMC variables (Leavitt, 1905). The SMC's proximity enabled Henrietta Leavitt to study 16 variable stars, finding that "the brighter variables have the longer periods" (Leavitt 1908), and derive the famous period-luminosity (PL) relation in Leavitt & Pickering (1912). Scowcroft et al. (2016) used the PL relation on infra-red Spitzer telescope on 92 SMC CCs to visualise just how the line-of-sight depths are caused by the elongated morphology of the SMC, confirming that the SMC is tilted and elongated such that its eastern side is up to 20 kpc closer to us than its western side, with the south-west (SW) edging away from us and the north-east (NE) "Wing" orientated towards the Magellanic Bridge, the LMC, and us. Using a larger sample of 4663 SMC CCs from the OGLE-IV survey, Jacyszyn-Dobrzniecka et al. (2016) confirmed that the SMC is ellipsoidal with two prominent off-axis structures: a significantly younger one in the NE (closer to its main body) and older one in the SW. In fact, not only is the closer NE component younger than the SW but the NE CCs have two age maximums at 110 Myr (closest to us) and 220 Myr (further), suggestive of this component to have formed in-situ during a recent LMC/SMC interaction. The young (< 300 Myr) CCs in the Magellanic Bridge support this. The older (> 10 Gyr) RR Lyrae, statistically considerably more numerous than CCs ($\sim 22,859$ in OGLE-IV RR-Lyrae catalogue, Jacyszyn-Dobrzniecka et al. 2017) have also been used to quantify the SMC's line-of-sight depth. The SMC RR-Lyrae are ellipsoidally distributed along the line-of-sight (Haschke et al. 2012; Subramanian & Subramaniam 2012; Deb et al. 2015), but more centrally concentrated than CCs (Deb et al. 2015; Jacyszyn-Dobrzniecka et al. 2017) resulting in line-of-sight depth measurements ranging from ~ 1 kpc to ~ 10 kpc (Muraveva et al. 2018). Another superb distance indicators are the Eclipsing binaries (EBs), known to carry the least systematic errors (de Grijs & Bono 2015). EBs suggest SMC depths of up to ~ 7 kpc (33 EBs, North et al. 2010; 10 EBs from OGLE-IV, Graczyk et al. 2020). Unfortunately, the scarcity of EBs in the SMC compared to CCs or RR Lyrae, hampers a proper determination of its geometry when using them as indicators.

Although variable stars have been pivotal in mapping the complex structure of the SMC, the stellar populations of the SMC contain a broad range of ages and metallicities forcing us to find alternative indicators to estimate the line-of-sight depth. Instead, we can use the magnitude spread of the RC stars among the SMC. Given that the RC has a very narrow magnitude range its shape is the part most conspicuously affected by line-of-sight depths on CMDs, causing it to appear vertically 'smudged' in magnitude. The RC technique in observed CMDs has been previously used to obtain SMC's line-of-sight depths (e.g., Hatzidimitriou & Hawkins 1989; Gardiner & Hawkins 1991); however, up until recently, it was not a reliable technique given that the magnitudes of the RC stars are affected by distance, photometric errors, and population effects (e.g., Sarajedini 1999). With the advent of more precise photometric surveys, the RC became a prime alternative to assert line-of-sight variations in the SMC (e.g., Subramanian & Subramaniam 2012; Nidever et al. 2013; Tatton et al. 2021; El Youssoufi et al. 2021).

All of the arguments presented here strengthen the argument that RC stars constitute optimum distance indicators for estimating the line-of-sight depth effects. In Chapters 2 and 4 I present

FIGURE 1.5: SMASH data release 1 and 2 (DR1/2) survey fields covering the Magellanic System. The hexagons depict one DECam field. The LMC is covered with shallow and deep fields and the SMC is fully covered with deep fields. In grey is the H I column density map from [Nidever et al. 2010](#). The blue contours are RGB star counts from 2MASS ([Skrutskie et al. 2006](#)). The DES footprint is marked in pink. See text for more details. Credit: SMASH DR2, [Nidever et al. \(2021, including Sakowska\)](#).

an updated SFH method to obtain the SFH with the line-of-sight depth effects, and in Chapter 3 I critically evaluate the results of my investigation into the effect of the line-of-sight depth on spatial SFHs.

1.4 SMASH: Survey of the Magellanic Stellar History

The data used throughout this thesis is from Survey of the MAgellanic Stellar History (SMASH, [Nidever et al. 2017](#); [Nidever et al. 2021](#), including Sakowska). SMASH is a Magellanic System survey conducted with the Dark Energy Camera (DECam; [Flaugher et al. 2015](#)) installed on the Blanco 4-m telescope at the CTIO (Cerro Tololo Inter-American Observatory) in Chile. DECam’s large ($\sim 3 \text{ deg}^2$) field of view enabled SMASH to survey across $\sim 2400 \text{ deg}^2$ of the Magellanic System and produced $\sim 480 \text{ deg}^2$ of high-quality photometric data. The achieved coverage is illustrated in Figure 1.5 where the hexagons, contiguously covering the LMC/SMC main bodies, represent one DECam image. The MCs’ bodies and peripheries are studied with contiguous, deep ($ugriz \sim 24.5 \text{ mag}$) optical coverage. In Figure 1.6 we can appreciate the large on-sky coverage of one SMASH DECam image. Figures 1.7 and 1.8 show the deep SMC and LMC images, respectively, obtained with SMASH. SMASH also covered features such as the Magellanic Bridge, Magellanic Stream and Leading Arm using ‘island’ fields. In Figure 1.5 the dark grey areas represent HI density columns belonging to the Magellanic Stream. For reference, the shaded purple area is the Dark Energy Survey (DES) footprint. An ongoing DECam survey

FIGURE 1.6: A SMASH DECam view of the Small Magellanic Cloud. One DECam image covers 3 deg^2 of the sky- comparable to 15 moons! Credit: D. Nidever

DELVE (DECam Local Volume Exploration Survey, [Drlica-Wagner et al. \(2021; 2022\)](#), all including [Sakowska](#)) is currently filling in these coverage gaps to comparable depth as part of its DELVE-MC program.

The main science goals of SMASH consist of (i) to derive SFHs across the Magellanic Clouds, (ii) to study the faint, low surface brightness stellar structures associated with the MCs and, (iii) to search for stellar counterparts of the leading and trailing part of the Magellanic Stream. To achieve the first goal (i) the oMSTO must be reached at $g \sim 22$ mag. DECam’s photometric capabilities have led to unprecedented, deep images of the MCs, all reaching $ugriz \sim 24$ mag and some as faint as $g \sim 26$ mag, making them suitable for aims (i) and (ii). For a thorough description of the SMASH data reduction methodology and its data release contents see [Nidever et al. \(2011, 2017\)](#). Some of the exciting MC studies done using SMASH include the identification of a new MW satellite, Hydra II ([Martin et al., 2015](#)) and a new faint globular cluster, SMASH-1 ([Martin et al., 2016](#)); probing the outskirts of both the LMC (down to surface brightness $\mu \sim 34$ mag /arcsec²; [Nidever et al. 2019](#)) and the SMC (down to $\mu \sim 32$ mag /arcsec²; [Massana et al. 2020](#)); producing a rigorous, extensive reddening map for the entire LMC ([Choi et al. 2018a](#)); detecting a “ring-like” stellar overdensity in the LMC ([Choi et al. 2018b](#)); among others.

1.5 Aims of this work

The overarching aim of this thesis is to shed light on the evolutionary history of the SMC, going back as far as ~ 13.7 Gyr. In Chapter 2, I compute the SFH of a shell-like structure in the northeastern outskirts of the SMC finding a conspicuous link between its formation and a very recent interaction with the LMC. In Chapter 3, I assess the robustness of my SFH methodology, in the context of the SMC’s line-of-sight depths. In Chapter 4, I present the spatially resolved global SFH of the SMC. In Chapter 5 I present work towards detecting ancient, metal-poor stellar

overdensities in the Magellanic periphery shedding light on the complexity of the Magellanic system. Finally, in Chapter 6 I present the conclusions of this thesis.

FIGURE 1.7: One of the deepest optical images of the Small Magellanic Cloud, created with SMASH data. Credit: D. Nidever

FIGURE 1.8: One of the deepest optical images of the Large Magellanic Cloud, created with SMASH data. Credit: D. Nidever

Chapter 2

Star Formation History in the Small Magellanic Cloud's Outskirts: characterisation of the 'shell' structure

I declare that the research presented in this chapter represents original work that I conducted during my PhD, and corresponds to the following submission to the peer-reviewed Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society:

Sakowska, Joanna D., Noël, Noelia E. D., Ruiz-Lara, Tomás et al. 2024, MNRAS, "Star formation history of the Small Magellanic Cloud's northeastern shell: quantifying the line-of-sight depth effects".

This submission has had its initial round of reviewer comments addressed and has been resubmitted. The anonymous peer reviewer from MNRAS made significant and helpful suggestions that improved the quality of this paper.

Statement of Contribution: I have made all of the contributions to the analysis and writing of this paper, with extremely valuable guidance and feedback from Dr. N. E. D. Noël and Dr. T. Ruiz-Lara. My analysis includes visual inspection of SMASH data, region selection, colour-magnitude diagram (CMD) production, star formation history (SFH) derivation, development of a statistical method to measure the line-of-sight depth in the CMD, extension of the star formation history pipeline to include the method, discussion and analysis of the results.

2.1 Abstract

I derive quantitative star formation histories (SFH) of a shell-like structure ('shell') and surrounding regions located in the northeastern part of the Small Magellanic Cloud (SMC). I use colour-magnitude diagrams (CMD) which reach down to the oldest main-sequence turn-off ($g \sim 24$ mag) from the SMASH survey. I also compute the SFHs of the shell's arm-like structure and two nearby control regions. For the first time, I present a novel technique that uses RC stars from the CMDs to assess and account for the SMC's line-of-sight depth effects present during the SFH derivation. I quantify a depth of ~ 7 kpc for the shell and depths as large as ~ 22 kpc for the control regions, which are all in good agreement with depth estimates from RC stars in the

northeastern SMC. I find extensive, young star formation in the shell with enhancements at ~ 250 Myr, ~ 450 Myr, ~ 650 Myr, ~ 1 Gyr ago, and one intermediate-age peak at ~ 2 Gyr. I analyse the shell's SFH against that of the LMC's northern arm SFH, also obtained using SMASH data, finding distinctive synchronicity between the SFHs of the two components. I argue that a combination of ram pressure stripping, tidal stripping, and circumgalactic gas interplay may have played an important role in the formation and build-up of the SMC's shell. Higher resolution hydrodynamical models of the SMC's last pericentric passage with the Milky Way are needed to unambiguously ascertain the origin of the structure.

2.2 Introduction

The faint peripheries of galaxies contain stellar fossil records of their mass assembly history (e.g., through galactic mergers, accretions and/or dynamical interactions with other galaxies) and, hence, harbour important clues to understanding the galaxy's formation and evolution (e.g., [Elmegreen & Hunter 2017](#)). As such, star formation history studies of galactic peripheries can provide important information on the processes that govern galactic growth. The outskirts of the Small and Large Magellanic Clouds, located at ~ 60 kpc and ~ 50 kpc away from us ([Pietrzyński et al. 2019](#); [Graczyk et al. 2020](#)), offer an outstanding opportunity to study SFHs of galactic outskirts in exquisite detail as we can resolve the individual stars of these tidally disrupting galaxies, down to the oldest oMSTO using ground-based telescopes (e.g., STEP: [Ripepi et al. 2014](#); SMASH: [Nidever et al. 2017](#); VISCACHA: [Maia et al. 2019](#); YMCA: [Gatto et al. 2020](#); DELVE: [Drlica-Wagner et al. 2021](#)).

Given the SMC's smaller total mass ([De Leo et al. 2023](#)) it is plausible that the LMC's gravitational influence played a key role in tidally shaping the SMC (e.g., [De Leo et al. 2020](#)). Indeed, the SMC's outskirts are home to a deluge of stellar structures such as the young (~ 150 Myr) shell-like overdensity ('shell', [Martínez-Delgado et al. 2019](#), hereafter MD19), the SMCNOD overdensity $\sim 8^\circ$ northwest of the SMC ([Pieres et al. 2017](#)), the various potential stellar streams in the northwest outskirts of the MCs ([Belokurov & Koposov 2016](#); [Navarrete et al. 2019](#)), the RR Lyrae stars overdensity connecting both MCs ([Belokurov et al. 2017](#); [Jacyszyn-Dobrzniecka et al. 2020](#)), and an elongated distribution of intermediate-age stars and Mira variables in the eastern outskirts of the SMC pointing in the same direction as the RR Lyrae overdensity ([El Yousoufi et al. 2019](#); [Deason et al. 2017](#)). Hence, the complex peripheries of the SMC merit a thorough study of their SFHs to help us elucidate key elements of its formation and evolution.

In particular, the coherent shell-like overdensity, already noted in photographic plates from the 1950s in the northeastern SMC (see [de Vaucouleurs & Freeman, 1972](#)), and subsequently confirmed by others ([Brueck & Marsoglu 1978](#); [Albers et al. 1987](#)) has been the subject of studies since its detection. Analysing shallow colour-magnitude diagrams (CMDs), [Brueck & Marsoglu \(1978\)](#) hinted at the presence of a young population in this region (called "outer-arm" in their work). Using deep CMDs from the SMASH survey, MD19 showed that the shell stands out when the spatial distribution density map of younger populations (upper main-sequence stars) is depicted rather than when the intermediate-age and old populations are presented (see Fig. 2.1 below). Indeed, [Piatti 2022](#) identified some of the shell's star clusters to be as young as ~ 44 Myr, evidencing very recent star formation. To disentangle the nature of the shell, MD19 applied the colour function method, first introduced by [Noël et al. \(2007\)](#), and found hints of not only young but also intermediate (~ 1.5 Gyr - 6 Gyr) and old (~ 8 Gyr - 13.5 Gyr) stellar populations.

Analysis of control regions near the shell highlighted the shell’s young stellar populations to be in stark contrast to the control regions. Guided by the ages of the Classical Cepheids (CCs) and young star clusters within the shell, MD19 suggested that the structure formed in a recent SF episode was likely triggered by an interaction between the MCs around ~ 150 Myr ago (Choi et al., 2022). MD19 were not able to date the intermediate and old-age populations further and suggested that these populations could be part of the background. Additionally, the authors did not find any evidence favouring that the shell might be a part of a larger spiral arm-like structure, or that it is a remnant of an accretion event. Instead, they suggested it could have formed via hydrodynamic interaction with a gas-rich object (e.g., MW halo, or LMC’s gaseous envelope; see, e.g., Tumlinson et al. 2017; Gatto et al. 2013; Fraternali et al. 2013). To comprehensively examine the shell’s stellar content, accurately date the young, intermediate, and old-age populations, and shed further light on the origin of the shell structure, a quantitative SFH determination is required.

As alluded to in the introduction (Chapter 1), the line-of-sight depths create an extra layer of observational effects on the observed CMDs of the SMC and should ideally be taken into account when obtaining quantitative SFHs¹. Although variable stars have been pivotal in mapping the complex structure of the SMC, the stellar populations of the shell contain a broad range of ages and metallicities forcing us to find alternative indicators to estimate the line-of-sight depth.

I present here a painstaking SFH determination of the SMC’s shell-like structure and surroundings including, for the first time, the line-of-sight depths. I use data from the second and final release of the SMASH (SMASH DR2; Nidever et al. 2021) and introduce, for the first time, the line-of-sight depth effect on our CMD-fitting techniques. Chapter 2 is organised as follows. In Section 2.3.1 I present the SMASH data and the selection of the different spatial regions. The SFH determination methods, including the consideration of the line-of-sight depth effects, are described in Section 2.4. In Section 2.5 I show the results from the SFH. In Section 2.6 I discuss the implications of the findings. Finally, in Section 2.7 I draw the main conclusions.

2.3 Data

2.3.1 The SMC’s shell in SMASH

I use the second and final SMASH data release (SMASH DR2; Nidever et al. 2021) to study the shell, located across the SMASH Field 9 (central coordinates (J2000): $\alpha = 01:01:27.40$, $\delta = -70:43:05.51$), SMASH Field 14 ($\alpha = 01:20:26.78$, $\delta = -71:15:32.76$) and SMASH Field 15 ($\alpha = 01:24:33.52$, $\delta = -72:49:30.00$). In Section 2.3.3 I describe in detail how I spatially select the shell, its arm-like structure and the two control regions in the periphery and on the main body. To study the control region on the main body I add SMASH Field 10 ($\alpha = 01:03:36.32$, $\delta = -72:18:54.4$). I refer the reader to Figure 2.1 that presents a stellar density map highlighting the studied regions and Figure 1 of Nidever et al. 2021 as a reference for SMASH fields.

The SMASH DR2 catalogue has several columns generated by PHOTRED (see Nidever et al. 2017 for details on SMASH image reduction) which are used to constrain the photometric selection in the g and i bands. I set a $-2.5 < \text{SHARP} < 2.5$ constraint to reduce the contamination by

¹The SFH is understood as the star formation rate (SFR) and chemical enrichment (average metallicity Z) as a function of time.

galaxies and spurious objects (as tested and proven effective in Ruiz-Lara et al. 2020; Massana et al. 2022). Following the previous works, the photometric uncertainties in the g and i bands were limited to 0.3 mag. Dust correction was applied using a reddening map constructed with RC stars following the techniques described in Choi et al. (2018a), assuming an intrinsic $g - i$ colour of 0.72². I adopted a distance modulus to the SMC of $(m - M_o) = 18.96$ (de Grijs & Bono, 2015).

2.3.2 Artificial star tests

In order to evaluate the photometric errors and completeness of the data, caused by stellar crowding, blending, and other measurement errors, the SMASH collaboration performed artificial star tests (ASTs)³. We adopted a standard AST method as extensively discussed in the literature (see, e.g., Stetson & Harris 1988). The ASTs consist of adding a certain number of artificial stars of known (injected) magnitude to the observed frames. After obtaining the photometry of the resulting synthetic frames using PHOTRED as done for the observed data, the comparison between the injected and recovered magnitudes of the artificial stars provides information about the crowding effects on the photometry. The resulting magnitudes are then compared with their initial values, quantifying the observed photometric errors and, in case those injected stars are not recovered, completeness of our observations (see Sect. 2.4.1). The procedure applied in the SMASH data for computing ASTs is discussed in more detail in Monelli et al. (2010) and Rusakov et al. (2021). The SMASH collaboration performed ASTs in SMASH Fields 9, 10, 14, and 15 (Nidever et al., 2021) each containing $\sim 2.1 \times 10^6$ injected stars covering the full regions in the CMD where we find stars. From these fields, I selected the regions studied (see Sect. 2.3.3) and calculated the completeness in each region based on the results of the ASTs. For the shell region, the completeness was 90% at magnitudes of ~ 3.6 for the g band and ~ 3.1 for the i band, and 50% at magnitudes of ~ 5.65 for the g band and of ~ 4.9 for the i band. The oMSTO, crucial in obtaining accurate ages and metallicities during SFH derivations (see e.g., Gallart et al. 2005), is located at i band ~ 3.6 , reaching 85% completeness, putting us in prime position to derive SFHs.

2.3.3 Region selection

To visualise the shell-like structure I followed the procedure presented in MD19. I isolated SMC stars located in different regions of the combined i and $g - i$ CMDs of SMASH Fields 9, 10, 14, and 15 to see how they are spatially distributed. In the top panel of Fig. 2.1, I present the red giant branch (RGB) and RC stars (indicators of intermediate-age and old populations) of the northeastern SMC. In the bottom panel of Fig. 2.1 I show stars occupying the upper young main-sequence (MS) region of the same fields, noting that the shell-like structure is only

²The SMASH DR2 reddening values are derived from the Schlegel et al. 1998 dust map, which is known to decrease in accuracy towards the main bodies of the MCs (see Section 5 and Figures 10-11 in Choi et al. 2018a). To provide the most accurate de-reddening possible, tailored to the SMC, I have used the reddening map purely based on the SMASH SMC RC data. The Choi et al. 2018a dust map is more accurate than the Schlegel et al. 1998 map in the SMC's optically thick regions, yet also consistent with the Schlegel et al. 1998 map in the optically thin regions (see discussion of Choi et al. 2018a). The two available SMASH SFH works (Ruiz-Lara et al. 2020; Massana et al. 2022) also use the Choi et al. (2018a) reddening map. By using the same SMASH dust map, we can make a self-consistent comparison between the SMASH SFHs.

³While the ASTs used in this work were mostly completed before I began my PhD, at the start of my PhD I ran ASTs for remaining SMASH fields.

FIGURE 2.1: Top: Spatial distribution of selected intermediate and older populations (RGB and RC stars) across the SMC with $\sim 655,558$ stars. Bottom: density map of the younger populations (upper main-sequence stars) with $\sim 324,535$ stars. The regions belonging to the shell are outlined: the shell (pink), and the arm (blue, dashed). For comparison, I added control regions in the SMC's main body (body control, green) and in the periphery (periphery control, orange dashed).

FIGURE 2.2: CMDs for the four regions studied selected in Figure 2.1. I have overlaid isochrones from the BaSTI-IAC library with three different ages and metallicities: a young isochrone shown in cyan ($Z = 0.002$, age = 150 Myr), an intermediate-age isochrone presented in green ($Z = 0.002$, age = 2 Gyr), and an old isochrone depicted in magenta ($Z = 0.001$, age = 10 Gyr). A young population is clearly present in all three regions with the exception of the control periphery region (left bottom CMD) where a double RC feature is also observed.

discernible when isolating these young MS stars. For a proper analysis of its stellar content, and to put it in the context of its surroundings, I divided this area into several regions as seen at the bottom panel of Fig. 2.1 (see figure caption for more details). The region marked with the solid pink polygon corresponds to the SMC's shell, while the blue dashed polygon represents the shell's arm-like region (following MD19's naming convention). The peripheral control region is represented by a dashed orange polygon in Fig. 2.1 and was selected in order to probe for young star formation in the area that could be also linked to the shell structure. Finally, I selected a second control region shown as a solid green polygon in Fig. 2.1, which would represent the typical stellar population of the SMC's main body in the northeast, carefully avoiding the central fields where crowding effects are dominant.

In Fig. 2.2 I present the observed SMASH CMDs corresponding to the four regions shown in Fig. 2.1; from top left, clockwise, we see the CMDs of the shell-like structure, the shell's arm, the control body, and the periphery. All CMDs are very well populated and are great examples of the photometric accuracy of the SMASH data set. To visually illustrate the stellar populations present, I overlay young ($Z = 0.002$, age = 150 Myr), intermediate-age ($Z = 0.002$, age = 2 Gyr), and old ($Z = 0.001$, age = 10 Gyr) isochrones from the BaSTI-IAC library⁴ (Pietrinferni et al. 2024). While the overlaid isochrones are for a fixed SMC distance, the isochrones unequivocally highlight the young nature of the shell and the presence of intermediate-age and old populations within the region. The adopted metallicities follow MD19 in consistency with spectroscopic determinations using young stars, Cepheids, and HII regions in the SMC (Russell & Dopita 1992; Romaniello et al. 2009; Lemasle et al. 2017). The selected stellar model predictions correspond to the model set accounting for the solar-scaled heavy element mixture, convective core overshooting, efficient atomic diffusion, and mass loss efficiency fixed at $\eta = 0.3$ (see Hidalgo et al. 2018 for more details).

From Fig. 2.2 we see that the CMDs of the shell, the shell's arm, and the control body show stars of all ages including young stars and intermediate-age and old populations. The CMD corresponding to the SMC periphery is predominantly comprised of intermediate-age and old stars as indicated by the lack of upper main-sequence stars which are prominent in other fields. There is a 'double' RC in the periphery CMD, which could be the result of tidal stripping during the formation of the Magellanic Bridge (e.g., Nidever et al. 2013), showing the presence of two different stellar populations separated by ~ 12 kpc (Subramanian et al. 2017; Tatton et al. 2021; El Youssoufi et al. 2021; James et al. 2021) with distinct radial velocities and proper motion distributions (Omikumar et al., 2021). I note that this simple inspection of the observed CMDs already shows that the bright MS part of the shell is more densely populated than that of the periphery control or the shell arm.

2.4 Star Formation History determination procedure

In this Section, I describe in detail a novel approach to compute SFHs taking into account line-of-sight depth effects using existing codes. This approach consists of a two-step SFH recovery. In the first step, I solve for a representative SFH of the region under study without simulating line-of-sight depth effects. The second step then uses this solution CMD to assess the line-of-sight depth by comparing its RC with the observed RC. The final SFH is then computed taking into account the line-of-sight depth.

⁴<http://basti-iac.iaa-brno.cz>

2.4.1 Step 1: Standard SFH determination

I created individual synthetic CMDs for a robust comparison between the observed CMDs and theoretical models. To construct the synthetic CMDs I used the solar-scaled BaSTI-IAC stellar evolution models and generated a global synthetic population containing 5×10^7 stars⁵ with a flat distribution in age and metallicity ranging from 0.03 to 13.9 Gyr in age and from 0.00001 to 0.025 in metallicity (Z). Following Ruiz-Lara et al. (2020) and Massana et al. (2022), I assumed a Kroupa initial mass function (IMF; Kroupa 2001) and a binary fraction of 50% with a mass ratio ranging from 0.1 to 1. I simulated observational effects on these synthetic CMDs. These effects were modelled using DisPar that utilises the ASTs results relevant to the region at hand to ‘disperse’ the stars from their actual positions on the synthetic CMDs, according to the measured observational errors and completeness (see Appendix B of Ruiz-Lara et al. 2021 for a description of DisPar). To obtain the best solution of the SFH per region studied I used THESTORM (Bernard et al. 2015, 2018). THESTORM uses a Poisson adapted χ^2 (Cash, 1979) to find the best combination of simple stellar populations (SSP; e.g., Maraston 1998) from the dispersed synthetic CMD that fits the distribution of stars in the observed CMD. The set of SSPs that I have used reflects the following age-metallicity grid:

- Age: [0.03 - 0.1; 0.1 - 1.0 in steps of 0.1; 1.0 - 2.0 in steps of 0.2; 2.0 - 3.0 in steps of 0.3; 3.0 - 10.0 in steps of 0.5; 10.0 - 13.9 in steps of 1] Gyr
- Z: [0.1, 1, 6, 16, 30, 45, 65, 90, 120, 160, 200, 249] $\times 10^{-4}$

Which equates to using 396 SSPs from the BaSTI-IAC stellar evolution library. The best-fitting combination is to be adopted as the SFH of the population. From it, we can derive a ‘solution CMD’, with similar characteristics as the observed CMD. For the comparison of the distribution of stars in the observed CMD and each combination of SSPs, I followed an *a la carte* approach and parametrised the observed CMD into six different sections that I call ‘bundles’ according to the nomenclature used in previous works (e.g., Monelli et al. 2010, Ruiz-Lara et al. 2018, Ruiz-Lara et al. 2020, Rusakov et al. 2021, Massana et al. 2022). The bundles’ locations have been carefully chosen in order to properly account for the evolutionary sequences in the CMD that can provide stronger constraints on the age and/or metallicity of the stars. Only the stars within the bundles’ limits are considered for the SFH calculation. The bundles are further divided into smaller boxes (containing around 0-100 stars/box). The comparison itself is done by counting the number of stars in small boxes within each bundle. The sizes of the boxes in each bundle vary according to their usefulness in the age-metallicity determination: regions populated by stars that are modelled with smaller theoretical uncertainties, or that are more sensitive to changes in age/metallicity are divided into small boxes (e.g., the MS region) than those affected by more uncertainty (e.g., RGB). I show this approach in the top left panel of Figure 2.3 that displays the observed CMD of the shell (see Figure 2.3 caption for more details) and the solution CMD with

⁵The size of the synthetic population chosen follows previous SMASH SFH works (Ruiz-Lara et al. 2020; Massana et al. 2022) albeit these works state a global synthetic population of 1.5×10^8 stars. The reason for this discrepancy is that these works state the total number of stars computed despite not all stars being written to the final file (as they are too faint/bright, for example). As such, the true number of stars used by these works is around 5×10^7 . In this work, I state the total number of stars used *after* any cuts are made (totalling 5×10^7 stars). Additionally, tests with mock stellar populations not shown in this work have demonstrated that SFH results using a synthetic population three times as large (1.5×10^8 stars written to file) are within the error bars of the SFH results generated with a global population containing 5×10^7 stars. Given this result, and the extensive computation time associated with using a larger population, I use a global population containing 5×10^7 stars.

the bundles overlapped (top middle). The sizes of the boxes in which each bundle is divided are shown as an inset table in the top middle panel. These different boxes used for different bundles determine the weight of each bundle in the final fit. Additionally, the bundles only include stars which are brighter than the magnitude threshold corresponding to a 50% completeness level ($i_0 \sim 4.9$ mag). To account for the Milky Way (MW) foreground contamination, an extra bundle (bundle 7) populated exclusively by MW halo stars is added. Bundle 7 was modelled by THESTORM using a field located far from the SMC's main body and thus, dominated by MW stars (SMASH Field 139 from [Nidever et al. 2021](#)). Further tests done to validate our bundle strategy can be found in appendix A of [Ruiz-Lara et al. \(2021\)](#).

Intrinsic sources of uncertainty in the SFH determination include (i) the effect of binning in colour-magnitude and age-metallicity planes and (ii) the statistical sampling of the observed CMD. To deal with (i), I fractionally shifted the colour-magnitude and the age-metallicity grids around one position (set using the average colour and magnitude shifts of the star formation history of the entire SMASH SMC catalogue (See Chapter 4) and the final SFH is an average of all solutions. I shifted five times in colour and age, and four times in magnitude and metallicity, producing 20 χ^2 fits in total. For the case of (ii), THESTORM re-sampled the observed CMD following a Poissonian distribution four times, and the SFH was recalculated. Following [Hidalgo et al. \(2011\)](#); [Rusakov et al. \(2021\)](#), I calculated the errors in the SFHs as a combination in quadrature of the standard deviation of the colour-magnitude shifted solutions, and the standard deviation of the Poisson-resampled solutions. For a more detailed description of the fitting procedure, I refer the reader to [Rusakov et al. \(2021\)](#).

In the top middle and top right panels of Figure 2.3 I present the resulting solution CMD and the residual CMD, respectively, for the first SFH derivation. While residuals are seen across the entire CMD, the most conspicuous residuals are across the MS and the RC. These residuals arise from the use of data that is less than 90% complete (below $i_0 \sim 3.1$ mag) and due to the line-of-sight depth effects. The line-of-sight depth effects are most conspicuously seen in the RC region of the CMD given the RC feature occupies a narrow magnitude range. In Section 2.4.2 I will discuss this feature further and how I account for this effect in the SFH determination.

2.4.2 Step 2: Incorporation of line-of-sight depth effects in the SFH determination

The standard procedure to derive the SFH described in Section 2.4.1 assumes that all of the stars in the observed sample are at the same distance. This assumption works well for galaxies where their stellar populations are more tightly distributed, which is not the case of the SMC. This galaxy has line-of-sight depths of up to approximately $\sim 1/3$ (~ 23 kpc in the northeast) of its distance to us (~ 61 kpc). Therefore, the spread in distance among the SMC's stars is visible in the form of magnitude variations on its observed CMDs. The magnitude variations are particularly conspicuous for the RC structure that is expected to be a narrowly concentrated (in magnitude) feature on the CMD⁶. In order to account for the line-of-sight depth effect in the CMD fitting, I follow an approach in which I simulate a magnitude dispersion across the synthetic CMD. In this section, I will describe how I quantify the line-of-sight depth by comparing the luminosity function of the observed RC with that of the best fitting model (see Sect. 2.4.1) of the first run of

⁶The RC can also show some intrinsic spread in magnitude. This intrinsic spread depends on population effects- i.e., on the characteristic age and metallicity spread of the underlying stellar population- as well as on the adopted photometric passbands (the spread significantly decreases when moving from the optical to the near-infrared bands. See [Cassisi et al. 2007](#), and references therein, for a detailed discussion on this topic).

FIGURE 2.3: Top left: The observed CMD parametrised using the bundle strategy; these bundles were further binned into boxes of varying dimensions which add different weights in the final fit (see text for details). Top middle: The parametrised solution CMD from the *first* SFH derivation with a table showing the binning in colour (ΔC) and magnitude (ΔM) applied during the fitting process for all of our results. Top right: Same as top middle, but for the *final* SFH derivation *after* the line-of-sight depth is accounted for. Bottom left: Residual CMD (observed - SFH solution) in units of Poisson sigmas for the *first* SFH solution. Bottom right: Same as the bottom left, but for the *final* SFH derivation *after* the line-of-sight depth has been accounted for in the SFH derivation. The residuals across the entire CMD have significantly improved after I have accounted for the line-of-sight depth.

FIGURE 2.4: First column: zoom in on the red clump region of the observed CMDs. Top to bottom by row: the shell, shell's arm, periphery control, and body control regions. Second column: luminosity function (represented as a normalised density distribution) of the region's solution CMD RC (cyan) versus observed RC luminosity (black, dashed). In purple is the luminosity function of the corresponding solution CMD RC (cyan), with a *line-of-sight depth injected into the CMD* during the line-of-sight depth estimation process. Here, I show the RC luminosity function with the best-fitting line-of-sight depth found for the region. Last column: RC luminosity function of the *final SFH solution* CMD RC after the line-of-sight depth is accounted for *during the SFH derivation process* (blue) versus observed RC luminosity (black, dashed). See text for details.

THESTORM to the observed CMDs not considering any line-of-sight depth (standard procedure). Then, I simulate such line-of-sight depth in the synthetic CMDs used for a second and final SFH derivation.

2.4.2.1 Estimating the line-of-sight depth from the RC luminosity function

The first column in Figure 2.4 shows a zoom-in of the RCs from the CMDs depicted in Figure 2.2. From each CMD, I calculate the observed RC luminosity functions (black, dashed histograms in the second column of Figure 2.4) and compare them with the ‘solution’ RC luminosity functions (cyan histograms in the second column of Figure 2.4). These solution RC luminosity functions were derived from running the first SFH solution, which in return gives us the first estimate of the age and metallicity distribution of the stars in the observed RC. The mismatch between the observed and the solution RC luminosity functions is mostly due to the line-of-sight depth affecting the observed data and not the model (as THESTORM was run without simulating any line-of-sight depth to the synthetic CMD). This way, by simulating several degrees of distance spread to the solution CMDs, and comparing the resulting RC luminosity function to the observed one, allows us to quantify the distance spread of the stars observed in each of the four areas (shell, shell’s arm, periphery control, and body control). First, I assume that the stars in the SMC are located along the line-of-sight following a Gaussian distribution. Assuming a distance modulus of 61.5 kpc as the mean, I construct the Gaussian distribution of stellar distances with its full width at half maximum (FWHM) representing the total extent of the line-of-sight depth (Nidever et al., 2013). After this, I randomly sample the fractional distance modulus shifts from the distribution (ranging in FWHMs from 0 to 23.5 kpc, in steps of 0.2 kpc, 250 times) and inject such shifts, in the form of magnitude shifts, into the absolute magnitudes of solution CMD stars. At each step, I re-measure the solution RC luminosity functions. In order to identify the RC luminosity function with a distance spread that best replicates the observed RC luminosity function, I use a two-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov (KS) test (Chakravarti et al. 1967) and select the depth which returns the highest probability statistic (p-value). This selection is done by plotting the p-value (averaged over 250 iterations) as a function of increasing line-of-sight depth and, given the curve approximates a Gaussian distribution, identifying the highest average p-value and its corresponding line-of-sight depth. The error σ on the line-of-sight depth can be approximated by smoothing the distribution with a gaussian kernel and measuring the corresponding FWHM, where $\sigma \approx FWHM/2$. For the shell region, the best fitting line-of-sight depth was 7.06 ± 4.00 kpc. For the shell’s arm, body control and periphery control regions, the best fitting line-of-sight depths equalled 18.37 ± 5.53 kpc, 5.18 ± 0.94 kpc and 21.67 ± 2.12 kpc, respectively.

In the second column of Figure 2.4 I show the above mentioned best-fitting RC luminosity functions measured during the line-of-sight depth estimation procedure (purple histograms). These luminosity functions are measured from the solution CMDs (from the first SFH run, cyan histograms) after simulating a line-of-sight depth corresponding to the best-fitting estimation. There is now a better agreement between the observed and RC luminosity functions (purple) in all cases with the exception of the periphery control sample. This is expected given that THESTORM has not been designed to reproduce double RCs in its solutions.

2.4.2.2 Line-of-sight depth as given by variable stars in the shell

As a sanity check, I cross-matched the SMASH data for the shell region with 76 CCs and RR-Lyrae stars from the OGLE-IV survey (Jacyszyn-Dobrzyniecka et al. 2016, Jacyszyn-Dobrzyniecka et al. 2017). I found that, for the shell region, the distribution of CCs and RR Lyrae stars can indeed be represented by respective Gaussian distributions, measuring the line-of-sight depth between ~ 4.7 kpc (CCs) and ~ 7.6 kpc (RR Lyrae). Combining the two distance indicators the resulting line-of-sight depth is ~ 5.7 kpc. This value is compatible with my estimate for the line-of-sight depth from the RC luminosity function (~ 7 kpc). Given that the shell occupies a relatively small area of the SMC there is a limitation in the amount of variable stars. Besides, the advantage of using the RCs luminosity functions to estimate distances is that the stellar populations of the shell are better represented and that the RCs are very well populated (Nidever et al. 2013; El Youssofi et al. 2021).

In any case, it is important to highlight that the scope of this work is not a geometrical characterisation of the SMC, but rather to improve the determination of SFHs of the SMC by taking into account the possible effects of the spread in stellar magnitudes in the SFH solutions.

2.4.2.3 Simulating the line-of-sight depth in synthetic CMDs

We are now armed with the tools to compute the SFH considering the line-of-sight depth. To achieve this, I construct a Gaussian distribution in which its FWHM represents the best-fitting line-of-sight depth. From the Gaussian distribution, I sample distance modulus shifts, converting them to fractional g, i magnitude shifts. I then inject the magnitude shifts into the stars in the synthetic CMDs and proceed to obtain the SFH as described in Section 2.4.1, with the difference that the synthetic CMD has now the line-of-sight depth incorporated. After the respective line-of-sight depth has been considered in the second and final SFH determination, I now have a final SFH in which line-of-sight effects have been taken into account. In Figure 2.3, top right, I show the solution CMD of the final SFH after the line-of-sight depth has been considered and, in the bottom right panel, I show the residual CMD. Here we see that, in comparison to the first SFH solution's residuals (bottom left panel), accounting for the line-of-sight depth of the shell has greatly improved the residuals observed across the CMD. Indeed, we can also inspect the final SFH solution by measuring the RC luminosity function. In the last column of Figure 2.4 I show the RC luminosity functions for the shell and the remaining regions (blue histograms, see caption for further details) and depict the observed RC luminosity functions for comparison (black, dashed lines).

While the robustness of THESTORM in deriving SFHs has been tested multiple times (e.g., Ruiz-Lara et al. 2020; Rusakov et al. 2021; Massana et al. 2022) the effects of line-of-sight depths on SFH recovery using THESTORM have not been previously studied. I assess the SFH recovery with the inclusion of the line-of-sight depths in Chapter 3, where I overview previous line-of-sight depth tests on SFH recovery from the literature, show the full (two-step) SFH procedure on mock data, assess the effects of the line-of-sight depths on mock data recovery in single bursts and complete SFHs, and show the age-metallicity relations (AMR) for the various scenarios. From all those tests I can conclude that the SFH recovery improves if we consider the line-of-sight depth effects while solving for the SFH. In what follows, and unless otherwise stated, the shown SFHs have been computed using this two-step SFH recovery, i.e. taking into account the line-of-sight depth effects.

2.5 Star formation history results

The SFHs recovered for all four studied regions are presented in Figure 2.5 and Figure 2.6. The SFRs before and after the simulation of the line-of-sight depths are shown and, for the metallicities, I show them after the simulation.

In the top panel of Figure 2.5, I present the SFHs of the shell region when accounting for a ~ 7 kpc line-of-sight depth (according to our calculations following Section 2.4.2.1) and when no line-of-sight depth is simulated (standard procedure). Both SFHs are in good agreement within the errors showing recent bursts of young ($\leq \sim 1$ Gyr) star formation with enhancements at ~ 1 Gyr, ~ 0.65 Gyr, ~ 0.45 Gyr, and a recent, conspicuous peak at ~ 0.25 Gyr (which is twice as intense as the young enhancements) but no hints of star formation episodes in the last ~ 0.25 Gyr are observed. Indeed, the agreement between the SFH results before and after the line-of-sight depth has been considered and re-iterates the robustness of our method in deriving the SFHs of the SMC. At intermediate ages, there is a peak in the SF at ~ 2 ago in agreement with the findings from Massana et al. (2022) and after that, there are no clear SF peaks. One explanation for this could be the decreased sensitivity for resolving short bursts at older ages as presented in Chapter 3, where I show that, beyond ~ 3.5 Gyr, our ability to resolve short (~ 0.1 Gyr), not prominent bursts of star formation decreases due to the photometric limitations of our dataset.

In the rest of the panels of Figure 2.5 I compare the SFHs of the shell to the SFHs of the control regions. The SFH of the shell's arm (bottom left panel) shows that this part of the SMC experienced an SFH similar to that of the shell between 3 and 0.75 Gyr ago, with young star formation bursts at times similar to those of the shell. However, the SFHs depart from one another in the last Gyr when the SFH of the shell's arm indicates a more quiescent period as compared to the SFH of the shell.

In the case of the body control region (second panel), which is selected to represent the SFH across the northeastern SMC's body, we observe an SFH that is in synchronisation with the shell's SFH from, at least, ~ 2 Gyr ago but still shows similar trends throughout all ages, with the difference that, at intermediate ages, the star formation rate is stronger in the main body. In particular, contrary to the shell, the star formation events that we infer between 3 and 6 Gyr ago would be more intense and or extended than the young ones in this part of the galaxy. Also, the episode at 2 Gyr ago is comparatively more intense in this field than in the shell. Another important difference is that star formation continues here to the present time, with the last peak occurring at a younger age than in the shell.

The last panel in Figure 2.5 shows the SFHs of the periphery control region that, unlike the other parts, does not show any SF younger than ~ 1 Gyr old (even less than for the shell's arm) with a rather flat SFH throughout the first ~ 12 Gyr.

The average metallicity results for all four regions analysed are shown in Figure 2.6. Given that the metallicity is calculated as the average Z of the stars present within the respective age bin, I expect the metallicity to fluctuate. In the case of a lack of a population of a given age, the metallicity will strongly fluctuate showing large uncertainties so I mask those areas (regions where the SFR is less than 5% of the maximum SFR); at younger ages, I use narrower metallicity bins (see Section 2.4.1) and therefore we are more likely to see fluctuations at these ages. In the top panel of Figure 2.6, I present metallicity distribution of the shell where we observe a mostly linear increase in metallicity, with a sharp increase at ~ 0.25 Gyr. In the other three

FIGURE 2.5: SFR(t) results for all four regions analysed in this work before and after the simulation of the line-of-sight depth during the SFH derivation process. Shaded areas represent uncertainties as explained in the text.

FIGURE 2.6: Age-metallicity relations displaying the average metallicity Z over lookback time for all four regions analysed in this work after the simulation of the line-of-sight depth during the SFH derivation process. Shaded areas also represent uncertainties. Here I mask the age bins in which SFR is less than 5% of the maximum SFR for the region to avoid uncertain average metallicity determinations driven by the lack of stars of such ages.

regions (top: arm, bottom: control regions) the metallicity from ~ 0.5 Gyr ago to 1.5 Gyr ago is higher than that of the shell but given that all of the metallicities are still within the error bars, we cannot draw major conclusions from this. Therefore, I suggest that all four regions follow similar chemical enrichment histories.

Next, I constructed cumulative mass fractions (CMF) as a function of lookback time. CMFs (also known as cumulative SFHs) indicate which fraction of the present-day stellar mass has formed before a specific lookback time. CMFs are useful as they help circumvent uncertainties in the measured SFHs since we look at total stellar mass assembled up to a given time rather than an instantaneous SFR. In the left panel of Figure 2.7 I present the full CMF result up to 13.7 Gyr, and in the right panel I explore the CMF in the shell and control regions over the last 3.5 Gyr. In both cases I show the CMF of the SFHs after including the line-of-sight depths. The right panel of Figure 2.7 also includes the shell's star formation bursts (see Figure 2.5) depicted as grey dashed vertical lines with the ages annotated. The CMFs of the shell indicate that at least $\sim 10\%$ of the total stars formed within the last 0.5 Gyr, $\sim 16\%$ within the last 1 Gyr, and $\sim 23\%$ of in the past 2 Gyr, more than in any other of the control regions under analysis (up to 10% of the stellar mass in the last 2 Gyrs at most). The CMFs also show that $\sim 50\%$ of the stars formed in the shell and the body control sample in the last ~ 6 Gyr whereas 50% of the mass was built at

FIGURE 2.7: Cumulative mass formation (CMF) for all four regions. Solid colour lines show the results after the respective line-of-sight depths are simulated. In the left panel, I show the CMFs throughout the whole history of the galaxy; I mark the 50% CMF. In the right panel, the CMFs from 3.5 Gyr ago up until now are shown; the vertical dashed lines mark the shell's SF peaks.

FIGURE 2.8: Comparison between the SMC shell's SFH (pink line) and the SFH of the LMC's northern spiral arm (blue line) (see Ruiz-Lara et al. 2020). The grey vertical dashed lines highlight the shared SFR enhancements in the SMC shell and the LMC's northern arm at ~ 0.25 Gyr, ~ 0.45 Myr, ~ 1 Gyr, and ~ 2 Gyr ago.

least a couple of Gyrs earlier for the shell's arm and periphery. It is in the last 4 Gyr of evolution that the SFHs of the shell and the body control sample depart.

My findings from quantitative SFH determinations are in good agreement with the qualitative age determination by MD19, who combined information overlapping isochrones on CMDs and used the age distributions of CCs and clusters within the shell. To conclude, I can claim that, despite the similarities shown between the analysed regions, the shell region is the one that formed the most stellar mass in the last ~ 2 Gyr.

2.6 Discussion

2.6.1 The dance of the SMC around the LMC

While the SFRs, average metallicities, and CMFs for the shell, the shell's arm, the periphery and body control regions presented in Section 2.5 show many similarities across all four regions (see Figure 2.5 and Figure 2.7), there are some features of interest I highlight in this discussion.

Beginning at ~ 2 Gyr ago, the shell and the body control regions share a similar SFR pattern which, eventually, matches in intensity at ~ 1 Gyr. From ~ 1 Gyr to ~ 250 Myr, the SFRs synchronise, with the enhancement at ~ 250 Myr proving the most significant for the shell. After the ~ 250 Myr enhancement, SF ceases in the shell yet continues across the control region on the body. One possible interpretation of this pattern is that the shell could have experienced extended SF, with recent enhancements during the last ~ 2 Gyrs (in synchronicity with the rest of the SMC), and the strongest peak ~ 250 Myr ago. Alternatively, the shell could have formed from the ~ 250 Myr enhancement alone. Given that we are viewing the SMC face-on, it is not possible to tell whether we are contaminating the shell's CMD with stars older than ~ 250 Myr in the form of background or foreground stars. As such, from this data alone it is very difficult to distinguish between the two formation scenarios proposed.

In either case, the overall coherence between all four regions makes it unlikely for the shell structure to be a separate entity and decoupled from the SMC such as a tidal dwarf galaxy (Bournaud & Duc, 2006). I do not see indications of a merging event with a more metal-rich secondary system as we do not find significant metallicity enrichment episodes for lookback times greater than 2 Gyr nor do we identify any counterpart structures or metal-poor overdensities either. What we can unequivocally say, however, is that the shell belongs to the SMC, with the enhancement at ~ 0.25 Gyr ago proving the most significant for it.

To contextualise the SFHs derived here within the pericentre passages between the MCs including MW effects, Figure 2.8 shows a comparison between the SFHs of the SMC shell and the SFH of the LMC's northern spiral arm (Ruiz-Lara et al., 2020), also obtained using SMASH photometry. I find that the SFHs follow a similar trend for the past ~ 3.5 Gyr, with more notable synchronicity at ~ 0.25 Gyr ago, ~ 0.45 Gyr ago, ~ 1 Gyr ago, and ~ 2 Gyr ago (similar to the findings from Massana et al. 2022 for the full SMC). I note that the enhancement in the shell's SFH at ~ 0.25 Gyr ago coincides with a trough in the SFH of the LMC's northern arm (see Figure 2.8). The peak in the SFH of the SMC is immediately followed by opposite trends in LMC's SFH, showing a very steep rise in LMC's SFH and a sharp decline in the shell's SFH. The synchronised enhancements found here have been linked to key events in the orbit of the SMC around the LMC, either predicting that the MCs had their first close encounter 2 Gyr ago (Diaz & Bekki, 2012), subsequent pericentre passages ~ 1 Gyr ago and ~ 0.4 Gyr ago (Navarrete et al., 2023), and a pericentre passage $\sim 0.25 - 0.15$ Gyr ago likely linked to the formation of the Magellanic Bridge (Besla et al. 2012; Noël et al. 2013; Noël et al. 2015; Carrera et al. 2017; Zivick et al. 2018; Cullinane et al. 2022; Choi et al. 2022). Additionally, over the past ~ 0.5 Gyr, the gravitational influence of the MW on the internal structure of the MCs is thought to have increased owing to their first close approach to the MW (see Besla et al. 2007; Patel et al. 2020).

2.6.2 Potential scenarios for the formation of the shell

In recent years, there has been growing evidence that the halo regions of nearby galaxies (up to their virial radii) contain multiphase gas, known as ‘circumgalactic medium’ (CGM; e.g., [Tumlinson et al. 2017](#); [Armillotta et al. 2017](#)). Given that it traces the inward flows from the intergalactic medium as well as the outward flows of enriched material from galaxies, the CGM has become an important player in our understanding of how galaxies evolve in their environments. As such, the CGM is a key fuel for setting star formation in a galaxy (e.g., [Binney 1977](#); [Gatto et al. 2013](#)), a venue for galactic feedback and recycling (e.g., [Hobbs et al. 2013](#); [Agertz et al. 2020](#)), and a main regulator of the supply of gas within the galaxy (e.g., [Davé et al. 2012](#); [Fraternali et al. 2013](#)). The proximity to the MW is believed to be the reason for the removal of material from nearby galaxies (e.g., [Grcevich & Putman 2009](#); [Gatto et al. 2013](#)), so the interactions between the MC system and the MW’s CGM likely alter the appearance and dynamics of their gaseous components; as the MCs fall through our Galaxy’s CGM, their tidal forces strip loosely bound gas from their discs, forming part of the massive Magellanic Stream ([D’Onghia & Fox, 2016](#)). Indeed, simulations that include CGM surrounding the LMC and SMC can explain the ionised gas component of the Magellanic Stream ([Lucchini et al., 2020](#)).

Tidal interactions unquestionably play a dominant role in shaping the gas in the MC system such as in the case of the Magellanic Bridge region where observations ([Noël et al. 2013](#); [Noël et al. 2015](#); [Carrera et al. 2017](#)) attribute the significant amount of gas and stars found there to tidal forces from encounters between the MCs, a fact also confirmed by current models (e.g., [Besla et al. 2010](#); [Besla et al. 2012](#)). On the other hand, ram pressure stripping has in all likelihood contributed to the structure of the MCs gaseous discs (e.g., [Mastropietro et al. 2005](#); [Salem et al. 2015](#); [Lucchini et al. 2021](#)). This is mainly supported by the fact that, while the bulk of the Magellanic Stream has a very low metallicity, the parts closer to the MCs are more metal-rich ([Richter et al., 2013](#)) suggesting that it has possibly been enriched from gas that has been stripped from the MCs ([Lucchini et al., 2020](#)) via ram pressure. Moreover, the LMC possesses a northeastern edge, also called the ‘leading-edge’ ([Salem et al., 2015](#)), that shows an abrupt truncation in the HI gas at ~ 6.2 kpc from the LMC’s centre but with a stellar profile that continues uninterrupted well beyond this radius ([van der Marel & Cioni, 2001](#)).

Following the above discussion, the MCs have conceivably experienced an increase in gas removal due to the introduction of ram pressure from the MW’s CGM. In addition, there is a gas wake behind the LMC and a large bowshock surrounding the LMC-SMC system caused by the passage of the LMC through the MW CGM, where the SMC is predicted to have spent the last ~ 0.25 Gyr in or near the bowshock ([Salem et al. 2015](#); [Setton et al. 2023](#)). As a result of these factors, the SMC is expected to have recently travelled through a higher-density gas environment than it has in the past. Given that ram pressure is known to increase SF on the leading edges of infalling galaxies ([Verdugo et al. 2015](#)), this may explain the increased intensity of the SF burst in the SMC shell ~ 0.25 Gyr ago. Ram pressure has been suggested to both trigger and quench star formation in dwarf-dwarf galaxy interactions ([Kado-Fong et al. 2023](#))-this could have contributed to the simultaneous trough in the LMC’s SFR ~ 0.25 Gyr ago and SF enhancement in the SMC shell. After ~ 0.25 Gyr, as the SMC continued to approach the LMC’s disc, the SMC’s gas may have been stripped and the LMC’s gas compressed and SF reignited.

I suggest that one possibility for the formation of the shell is that, as the SMC was moving near the LMC’s disc and near the bowshock over the past $\sim 1-2$ Gyr, its gas was shocked into a shell of star-forming gas. Then, the gas shell experienced SF enhancements in line with the SMC’s

orbit around the LMC over the past 1 Gyr, and the intensity of the last SF burst ~ 250 Myr could be explained by the SMC passing through an increasingly dense environment/approaching the bowshock. In fact, these bowshocks have been linked to the LMC's large "shell" of dense star-forming gas (de Boer et al., 1998).

Although it is puzzling that, at look back times greater than 0.25 Gyr, the SFH results for the shell show a strong coherence with the rest of the SMC's SFHs, I echo that it is extremely difficult to establish whether the shell contains stars that are only 250 Myr old, or if there truly are intermediate and old populations within the shell already. In the case of the latter, it is possible that the tidal stripping of gas and stars from the inner SMC during the formation of the Magellanic Bridge ~ 250 Myr ago could have formed the shell-like structure (e.g., Piatti 2022), and contributed to the young, intermediate-age, and old stellar populations detected.

We have to be cautious in arriving at conclusions because, although we know that the SMC is crossing over the CGM at high speeds (e.g., Costa et al. 2011), its position, orientation, and motion are considerably less well-constrained than for the LMC. For instance, the past pericentric approach of the SMC to the MW is highly uncertain due to its orbit being strongly perturbed by the LMC. Despite this, a purely tidal origin is unfeasible given that, in a tidal interaction scenario, intermediate-age and old populations are also triggered (Noël et al., 2013), and these are not visible in the shell-like structure from Figure 2.1. Given that current hydrodynamic simulations do not have sufficient resolution to predict stellar structures such as the shell, we cannot unequivocally confirm or rule out the frameworks discussed here.

2.7 Conclusions

I presented here the quantitative SFH analysis of a shell-like structure and three further regions in the northeastern SMC. I incorporated, for the first time, the SMC's line-of-sight depths in the SFHs calculation by comparing the observed RC luminosity function against the theoretical RC luminosity function (from the first SFH obtained) and quantifying the line-of-sight depth present in the observed CMD. I then injected the line-of-sight depth into our model and re-calculated the final SFH. I obtained the SFHs, that we decompose on the SFR(t), Z(t), and the CMFs, for the four regions analysed. Finally, to discuss potential frameworks for the shell's origin, I compared its SFH with the SFH of the LMC's northern arm (obtained using SMASH). I summarise my overall findings below:

- The best fitting line-of-sight depth for the shell region was quantified at 7.06 ± 4.00 kpc. For the control regions studied, the largest depth was found to be 21.67 ± 2.12 kpc, in line with depth estimates in the northeastern SMC from RC stars (e.g., Nidever et al. 2013).
- Although there is conceptual improvement in the results from the mock tests (particularly in the metallicity recovery, see Chapter 3) and decreased residuals during the CMD fitting, the SFHs recovered before and after simulating the line-of-sight depths maintain agreement with each other and do not show significant changes.
- For the shell region I find conspicuous, young SF with enhancements at ~ 250 Myr, ~ 450 Myr, ~ 650 Myr, and ~ 1 Gyr ago. The strongest enhancement occurred ~ 250 Myr and I do not detect star formation younger than this. I find an intermediate-age peak at around ~ 2 Gyr ago and no significant peaks in the SFH for older ages.

- All of the shell's enhancements are also found in the control region on the SMC's body, and the young ($\leq \sim 1$ Gyr) bursts match in scale. However, it is true that the burst ~ 250 Myr ago is more significant in the shell than in the other regions, suggesting a possible link with the formation of the shell. In any case, contamination from the overall SMC population is expected and thus hampers a cleaner conclusion on the origin of the shell.
- Regardless, the comparison between the shell's SFH and the LMC's northern arm SFH shows unequivocal synchronicity in the SFHs, with mutual enhancements at ~ 450 Myr, ~ 1 Gyr and ~ 2 Gyr ago and, at ~ 250 Myr, the shell's enhancement coincides with a trough in the northern arm's SFH. I therefore link the formation of the shell to the interaction history of the SMC with the LMC/MW during the past ~ 2 Gyr
- Finally, I argue that the complex processes of ram pressure stripping, tidal stripping, and CGM interplay involved in the SMC/LMC/MW system over the past ~ 2 Gyr have played an important role in the formation of the shell-like structure. To help discriminate between whether the shell has formed thanks to SF enhancements over the past ~ 2 Gyr, or solely from the shell's most intense SF burst ~ 250 Myr ago, a higher resolution hydrodynamical model of the SMC/LMC/MW system over the last ~ 250 Myr would be highly beneficial in assessing if the physical conditions ~ 250 Myr ago could lead to the formation of a shell-like structure similar to the one studied.

I have demonstrated here my ability to obtain the SFH of the SMC shell-like structure in unprecedented detail using a novel technique incorporating line-of-sight depth effects during the SFH computation. Regarding the formation of the shell, my conclusions remain largely speculative given that better constraints on the SMC's position, orientation, and motion are needed. Finally, in order to draw further conclusions, improved models of the past pericentric approach of the SMC to the MW are required; such models should, ideally, address the high uncertainties due to the SMC orbit being strongly perturbed by the LMC.

Chapter 3

Assessing the Star Formation History recovery and quantifying the line-of-sight depth effect uncertainties

I declare that the research presented in this Chapter represents the Appendix of the original work that I conducted during my PhD, and corresponds to part of the following submission to the peer-reviewed Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society:

Sakowska, Joanna D., Noël, Noelia E. D., Ruiz-Lara, Tomás et al. 2024, MNRAS, "Star formation history of the Small Magellanic Cloud's northeastern shell: quantifying the line-of-sight depth effects".

This submission has had its initial round of reviewer comments addressed and has been resubmitted. The anonymous peer reviewer from MNRAS made significant and helpful suggestions that improved the quality of this paper. In this chapter, I showcase extra analysis that was not included in the paper.

Statement of Contribution: I have made all of the contributions to the analysis and writing of these results, with extremely valuable guidance and feedback from Dr. N. E. D. Noël and Dr. T. Ruiz-Lara. I have extensively improved and further developed the pipeline used to derive star formation histories with mock data, a pipeline originally written by Dr. T. Ruiz-Lara and Dr. P. Massana. My contributions include simulating the line-of-sight depth effect into the mock data, writing new, extensive pipelines which recover the SFH with or without the line-of-sight depth effect considered, and fine-tuning the fitting parameters I have designed the test objectives, and extensively analysed and described all of the results provided.

3.1 Abstract

I explore here the efficacy of recovering star formation histories (SFHs) using THESTORM, a suite tested against various scenarios. I examine novel approaches to recovering SFHs, including considering various line-of-sight depths. I perform comprehensive tests on mock populations with a range of star formation bursts. I show that accounting for line-of-sight depth in the SFH derivations gives promising conceptual improvements for large (~ 22 kpc) depths. In the case

of the northeastern shell region of the Small Magellanic Cloud (SMC), which has a smaller ~ 7 kpc line-of-sight depth, accounting for these effects recovers an SFH within the error bars of the results obtained for the SFH when line-of-sight depths are not accounted for. These findings underscore the importance of addressing observational effects for accurate SFH recovery.

3.2 Introduction

As shown in Chapter 2, understanding the star formation history (SFH) of the Magellanic Clouds (MCs) is pivotal for unravelling their evolutionary trajectory and deciphering the underlying processes shaping their morphology and composition. Here, I test the ability of THESTORM to recover SFHs including line-of-sight depth effect uncertainties. Although THESTORM has been robustly tested in the literature (e.g, Ruiz-Lara et al. 2020; Rusakov et al. 2021; Massana et al. 2022), this is the first time the line-of-sight depths are considered.

The work presented here builds upon established methodologies, refining our understanding of SFH reconstruction by scrutinising the impact of line-of-sight depth effects. I delineate the methodological framework underpinning the analyses and subsequently present the results, beginning with an exploration of age and metallicity resolution tests for mock CMDs featuring singular bursts of star formation (Sections 3.3 and 3.3.1). Next, I examine the recovery for mock CMDs with a more complex, bursty SFH, using both the shell’s and the periphery control region’s SFH result as input (Section 3.4). Through meticulous analysis and interpretation, I elucidate the nuances of SFH recovery in the presence of line-of-sight depth effects. With these tests, I quantify our ability to resolve star formation bursts, and the effects of the line-of-sight depth on SFH recovery, without the uncertainties caused by foreground stars, distance, reddening guesses, and stellar evolution libraries.

3.3 Recovering single bursts of star formation affected by a line-of-sight depth

I present here the first set of tests examining a mock population with star formation bursts at ~ 0.2 Gyr ago, ~ 0.6 Gyr ago, ~ 1 Gyr ago, ~ 2 Gyr ago, ~ 3.5 Gyr ago, ~ 5 Gyr ago, ~ 7 Gyr ago, and ~ 10 Gyr ago, each set to be 0.1 Gyr wide. For each burst, the metallicity of the stars was set to resemble the range shown in the average metallicity of the SMC’s northeastern shell: $Z = 0.003 - 0.008$ for the young populations (≤ 1 Gyr), and $Z = 0.00001 - 0.005$ for the intermediate and old populations (> 1 Gyr). The mock populations are drawn from the same global synthetic population (also known as the ‘mother’ CMD) which I use to create the synthetic CMDs for the SFH calculations presented in Chapters 2 and 4.

I examine CMDs with simulated line-of-sight depths of 0 kpc, 7 kpc, 14 kpc, and 21 kpc. I exclude larger line-of-sight depths because my results on the line-of-sight depths across the global SMC data do not suggest depths above 23 kpc (see Section 4.5). This test is designed to examine if accounting for the line-of-sight depth effect improves SFH recovery, as well as to assess the age-metallicity resolution when computing SFHs in general. The line-of-sight simulation follows the procedure described in Section 2.4.2. I simulated observational effects applying DiSPar on these mock CMDs (using the AST results for the SMC’s northeastern shell

region), as described in Section 2.4.1. Following this step, I cut the mock CMD in size to match the number of stars in the CMD of the northeastern shell as well (214,527 stars).

For this set of tests, I fit the mock CMD against a synthetic CMD that either contains (case 1) or does not contain (case 2) the same line-of-sight depth as in the input mock CMD. For case 1, both the mock and synthetic CMDs have the same line-of-sight effect simulated, using the method presented in Section 2.4.2. This case would mimic the updated method in which line-of-sight is taken into account. For case 2, only the mock CMD has the line-of-sight effect simulated. This case would mimic the original approach, in which the observed data is affected by a distance spread that is not considered in the fitting process. The fitting procedure closely followed that presented in Section 2.4. The same bundle strategy was used (with no bundle 7, given a lack of MW foreground).

In Figure 3.1 I show the age-resolution tests for a mock CMD with a SFH consisting of single, 100 Myr wide bursts. The top left panel in Figure 3.1 shows the recovery of singular bursts (yellow) against the input stellar ages (grey, dashed) with no line-of-sight depth present in the mock nor the synthetic CMD. If no depth effects are considered, the recovery of young ages ($\lesssim 1$ Gyr) is excellent. The 100 Myr wide peaks are discernible and do not blend. After ~ 1 Gyr we note that the ability to resolve star formation bursts degrades for intermediate ages, with bursts difficult to discern beyond 5 Gyr ago. The reasons for this degradation include photometric errors, a comparatively smaller number of old and intermediate-age populations in the synthetic CMD, and intrinsic uncertainties with our method (Section 2.4.1). Hence, the capacity to resolve short (~ 100 Myr) bursts, of the intensity we have simulated in these tests, is limited at intermediate ages. In Section 3.3.1 I present results that investigate this matter further.

In the top right panel and bottom panels in Figure 3.1 I show the case in which the mock CMD was constructed with an added line-of-sight depth, and the synthetic CMD has or has not the line-of-sight depth included (teal if added, purple if not added). At 7 kpc, our ability to recover and individually resolve bursts is slightly better when the line-of-sight depth is considered, but nothing substantial. As the line-of-sight depth increases and becomes more impactful, the improvement when the effect is considered is visible at 14 and 21 kpc with the young peaks blending less. However, given the decreasing resolution, it is not clear how the line-of-sight depth affects the recovery of intermediate-age and old populations.

In Figure 3.2 I show the recovery in the age-metallicity plane (AMR in 2D). In the top left panel I show the input AMR for all of the mock CMDs, and, in the top right panel, I show the AMR recovery when no line-of-sight depth is present in the mock nor the synthetic CMDs. It can be observed that stars up to 2 Gyr old are recovered very well, and signatures at 3.5 Gyr, 5 Gyr, 7 Gyr, and 10 Gyr old are there.

The next middle and bottom rows in Figure 3.2 examine the effects of the line-of-sight depth (7 kpc, 14 kpc, and 21 kpc) on the AMR recovery. On the two middle and bottom left panels, we see the recovered AMR when the input mock CMDs have a line-of-sight depth and no line-of-sight depth is accounted for in the synthetic CMD. On the two middle and bottom right panels, the line-of-sight depth is accounted for in the synthetic CMD. It is clear that the inclusion of the line-of-sight depth considerably improves the AMR recovery in all three cases. Accounting for the depth effect is especially significant at large line-of-sight depths: the metallicity estimate of young stars is significantly less spread out, resembling the input AMR.

FIGURE 3.1: Age-resolution tests for a mock CMD with a SFH consisting of singular bursts. I consider line-of-sight depths of 0 kpc, 7 kpc, 14 kpc, and 21 kpc. The ages of the stars inputted into THESTORM are shown in grey. The results with no line-of-sight depth in the mock nor the synthetic CMD are presented in yellow. The results when there is a line-of-sight depth in the mock CMD and not in the synthetic CMD are shown in purple. In teal the line-of-sight is present in both, the mock and synthetic CMDs.

FIGURE 3.2: Age-metallicity recovery plots for a mock CMD with a SFH consisting of singular bursts, corresponding to Fig. 3.1. To ease interpretation, I have masked AMR that is less than 3% of the maximum AMR. The first row left shows the AMR of input stars mock CMDs for all tests. The first row right shows the AMR recovery when no line-of-sight depth is present in mock CMD and is not simulated in synthetic CMD, corresponding to the top left panel in Figure 3.1. In grey, I included the input AMR as a reference. The second, third, and last rows on the left show the recovered AMR when line-of-sight depths (of 7 kpc, 14 kpc, and 21 kpc) are present in the mock and the same line-of-sight depth is **not** accounted for in the SFH derivation. The second, third, and last rows on the right show the recovered AMR when an increasing line-of-sight depth is present in the mock CMD and the same line-of-sight depth is **is** accounted for in the SFH derivation. To ease interpretation, I have masked AMR that is less than 3% of the maximum AMR.

3.3.1 Recovering single bursts of star formation at intermediate and old ages

Assessing the effect of line-of-sight depth at intermediate and old ages is not trivial given the uncertainties inherent to both THESTORM and the stellar evolution models used at those ages. In addition, given the mother CMD accounts for stellar death, the number of intermediate to old stars available (and their signal in comparison to that of the young populations) is highly minimised. With all this in mind in Figure 3.3 I investigate further the age resolution at intermediate and old ages without any line-of-sight depth considerations. For this test, I created an input mock CMD with the same bursts I described in Section 3.3. This time, I derived the input mock CMD from a larger mother CMD. The new mother CMD contained an extra 3×10^6 stars at 5 Gyr, 7 Gyr, and 10 Gyr, such that the signal at these ages is amplified and should be easily detected. It is also three times larger than the standard mother CMD we use to derive the SFH from observed SMASH data (and to perform the rest of the mock tests within this chapter). This way we can gain insight as to whether our resolution is limited by (i) the efficiency of THESTORM in recovering intermediate and old age enhancements, (ii) the crowding and photometry of the SMASH dataset, or (iii), the number of SSPs available in the intermediate and old age ranges.

In the top panel of Figure 3.3, I show the solution for the SFH using the same mother CMD as I used to obtain the SFH from the observed SMASH dataset (i.e., a smaller mother CMD with no extra stars in the intermediate-age and old populations). THESTORM has detected a large number of intermediate-age and old stars albeit with an age dispersion. In the bottom panel, I solve for the SFH using a synthetic CMD constructed from the same mother CMD as the input mother CMD. THESTORM clearly recovers the sharp bursts of 5, 7, and 10 Gyr stars.

It is unlikely THESTORM does not recover intermediate and old age stellar populations with good accuracy, given it has previously done so in literature. For example, Rusakov et al. (2021) use mock tests (very similar to those shown here) to recover an 11 Gyr enhancement with less age dispersion than that presented here. Rusakov et al. (2021) use data from the Hubble Space Telescope, which is less affected by observational errors than the SMASH dataset given that space-based telescopes produce more accurate photometry than ground-based ones. The observational errors simulated in their mock tests (also with DiSPar) are likely smaller, leading to improved accuracy in intermediate and old ages. Observational errors likely play a role in the decreased age resolution. In addition, the size of the age bins used by thestorm to solve with also matters. At 5 Gyr, 7 Gyr, and 10 Gyr the age bins used were 0.5 Gyr wide (see Section 2.4.1 for the age-metallicity grid configuration). While we will not recover 0.1 Gyr bursts with this configuration, this is unlikely the cause for the decreased resolution given that the recovered 7 Gyr old and 10 Gyr old bursts are not centred on the input age peaks.

It is clear that solving with a mother CMD with extra intermediate and old age SSPs led to sharp enhancements being detected (option iii). However, both of the tests recovered the peaks with very similar age dispersion making it unlikely that using larger (in this case, three times larger) mother CMDs leads to better SFH recovery. Indeed, I have derived SFHs using three times larger mother CMDs and the results were within error. Going ahead, all of the results presented in this thesis were computed with the smaller mother CMD due to issues with memory crashes when the large mother CMD was used.

In conclusion, the coarser age resolution at the intermediate and old ages is likely due to the photometric errors and completeness of the SMASH dataset. Motivated by the results presented

FIGURE 3.3: Age-resolution tests for a mock CMD with a SFH consisting of singular bursts. In grey are the ages of the stars inputted into THESTORM. The input mock CMD contains 3 million extra stars at 5 Gyr, 7 Gyr, and 10 Gyr. The recovered SFH is shown in yellow. Top: the SFH solved with a model CMD constructed from the same global population as the input mock CMD. Bottom: the SFH solved with a model CMD which is three times smaller and does not contain extra stars at 5 Gyr, 7 Gyr, and 10 Gyr. This is the global population with which we solve for the SFH from observed data.

in Section 3.3 and here, in the next Section I used both the northeastern shell's and the periphery region's final SFH solution CMD as the input mock CMD and examined the recovery.

3.4 Recovering the star formation histories of regions affected by their respective line-of-sight depth

In Figure 3.4 I show the results of the recovery of the northeastern shell's final SFH, which I use as the input mock CMD (i.e., the line-of-sight depth has been accounted for in the fitting procedure in Section 2.4.2). The solution CMD already had observational effects simulated with DisPar and the northeastern shell's line-of-sight depth (7 kpc). The SFH was solved with the same mother CMD as for observed data. The top left panel in Figure 3.4 shows the age distribution (lookback time as a function of normalised amount of stars formed), the upper right panel shows the input AMR, the bottom left panel shows the AMR after not considering the line-of-sight depth (7 kpc). The bottom right panel shows the AMR after considering the 7 kpc line-of-sight depth in the SFH derivation. I recover the input ages up to ~ 3 Gyr (see top panel). Regarding the AMR recovery, both sets of results are also very similar. On the one hand, we could draw a parallel between this result and the single burst case in Figure 3.2 for 7 kpc, and

say that both of the results appear within their error because a 7 kpc depth is relatively small. To check this conclusion, in the next section, I use the periphery control's solution CMD (with its 22 kpc line-of-sight depth simulated) as the input mock CMD and repeat this test.

In Figure 3.5 I show the results of the recovery of the periphery control region's final SFH, which is affected by a 22 kpc line-of-sight depth. Just like for the shell region, I solved for the SFH firstly without considering its 22 kpc line-of-sight depth, and then repeated the derivation considering it. The top left panel suggests that accounting for the large line-of-sight depth present has improved our SFH recovery. From now until ~ 3 Gyr ago, the result that accounts for the effect (teal) reproduces the width of the input stellar ages (grey) very well. After ~ 3 Gyr ago, the teal result appears to follow the input stars better than the yellow result (when the effect is not accounted for), although it is difficult to say with certainty as both results appear within error. In terms of the AMR recovery, accounting for the ~ 22 kpc line-of-sight recovers the input AMR significantly better. At ~ 1 Gyr ago, the AMR is recovered with less metallicity dispersion and there is no AMR gap seen at ~ 3 Gyr ago. I also note that the AMR intensity is recovered better at ~ 8 Gyr - 10 Gyr.

From the tests presented here, I conclude that it is better to account for the line-of-sight depth when obtaining the SFH, as per the significant improvements in the mock tests presented here. Thanks to these findings I have decided to account for the line-of-sight depth in my SFH derivations.

FIGURE 3.4: Age-resolution tests for a mock CMD with a ‘realistic’ star formation history. The mock CMD used is the shell’s solution SFH. The solution is after the line-of-sight depth was simulated, hence the CMD contains a line-of-sight depth of 7 kpc. To ease interpretation, I have masked AMR that is less than 3% of the maximum AMR. Top, left panel: in grey are the ages of the stars inputted into THESTORM. In yellow is the result when the 7 kpc line-of-sight depth is not accounted for in the fitting process. In teal is the result when the line-of-sight depth is accounted for. Top, right: Input AMR of mock CMD. Bottom, left: recovered AMR of mock CMD when a line-of-sight depth of 7 kpc **is not** accounted for. In the background we show the input AMR of the mock CMD (from the top right panel), however, I show it in a red/yellow colour scheme to help the reader distinguish between the input and output stars. Bottom, right: recovered AMR when line-of-sight depth of 7 kpc **is** accounted for.

FIGURE 3.5: Age-resolution tests for a mock CMD with a ‘realistic’ star formation history. The mock CMD used is the periphery control’s solution SFH. The solution is after the line-of-sight depth was simulated, hence the CMD contains a line-of-sight depth of 22 kpc. To ease interpretation, I have masked AMR that is less than 3% of the maximum AMR. Top, left panel: in grey are the ages of the stars inputted into THESTORM. In yellow is the result when the 22 kpc line-of-sight depth is not accounted for in the fitting process. In teal is the result when the line-of-sight depth is accounted for. Top, right: Input AMR of mock CMD. Bottom, left: recovered AMR of mock CMD when a line-of-sight depth of 22 kpc **is not** accounted for. In the background we show the input AMR of the mock CMD (from the top right panel), however, I show it in a red/yellow colour scheme to help the reader distinguish between the input and output stars. Bottom, right: recovered AMR when line-of-sight depth of 22 kpc **is** accounted for.

3.5 Discussion

3.5.1 Comparison with SMC line-of-sight depth tests in literature

Harris & Zaritsky (2004) calculated the SFH on a central $4 \times 4.5^\circ$ area on the SMC's main body using the Magellanic Clouds Photometric Survey (MCPS). To test for line-of-sight depth effects, they fitted a mock CMD with a 12 kpc line-of-sight depth against a synthetic CMD without a line-of-sight depth using χ^2 minimisation, concluding that the recovered SFHs were comparable within the errors. Rubele et al. (2018) performed a spatially-resolved, SFH determination of a contiguous area of 23.57 deg^2 of the SMC's main body using near-IR VMC data. They tested for line-of-sight depth effects by fitting the observed CMD against a synthetic CMD with no line-of-sight depth; a synthetic CMD with a line-of-sight depth estimated from Muraveva et al. (2018); and a synthetic CMD with a best-fitting line-of-sight depth (found by searching a grid of different depth values, which used different reddening and distance values). They presented the results for an example region in the northeast (which also contains the SMC's northeastern shell). The RR Lyrae distribution in the area equalled $4.3 \pm 1 \text{ kpc}$ (closely in agreement with my estimate by cross-matching OGLE and SMASH data); the line-of-sight depth in the synthetic CMD was simulated using a Cauchy distribution which considered depths up to 25 kpc. Rubele et al. (2018) found little to no improvement, with all three solutions within their error bars, noting that estimating the line-of-sight depth using RR Lyrae distribution is limited due to the presence of many different stellar populations within the SMC.

To my knowledge, the work I present here forms the most extensive investigation performed into whether the SMC's line-of-sight depth affects its SFH recovery.

3.6 Conclusions

The tests presented here assessed the robustness of our method in recovering the ages and metallicities of star formation enhancements at different epochs. The tests also probed the age/metallicity recovery from CMDs affected by a line-of-sight depth. For the most realistic comparison possible, I simulated observational uncertainties into the mock observed CMDs. The SFH derivation followed closely the updated methodology presented in Section 2.4.1. The observational uncertainties used were derived from the AST results of the northeastern shell region.

- I find that the age/metallicity recovery of singular, young ($\leq 1 \text{ Gyr}$) 100 Myr enhancements from CMDs unaffected by line-of-sight depths is excellent, with little age dispersion.
- Once a line-of-sight depth is present in those CMDs, accounting for the effect in the SFH derivation improves the age recovery. The improvement is most noticeable in the metallicity recovery- the metallicity dispersion is significantly decreased.
- Due to the coarser age resolution seen in the single burst case of intermediate/old ages, I did not test their line-of-sight depth effects. Such coarser age resolution is likely due to the photometric uncertainties and completeness associated with the SMASH dataset.

- The final set of tests used the SFH result of the northeastern shell region and the periphery control region from Chapter 2. These SFH results already accounted for the line-of-sight depth during the derivation- as such, the shell's and the periphery control's respective solution CMDs already have a ~ 7 and ~ 22 kpc line-of-sight depths simulated. For the northeastern shell region, both approaches produced results that appear to be within the errors. For the periphery region, simulating its line-of-sight depth significantly improved the results. From these mock tests, I conclude that accounting for a line-of-sight depth makes a positive difference if the depth is large (e.g., ~ 22 kpc) rather than relatively small (e.g., ~ 7 kpc). This result is consistent with the singular burst case- the ~ 7 kpc result shows little improvement in contrast to the improvement seen in the ~ 22 kpc case. Motivated by the improvement seen in the tests, I decided to consistently account for the line-of-sight depth effects going forward.

The tests presented here lend credibility to the SFH results from Chapters 2 and 4. The inclusion of line-of-sight depths contributes to robust and informed conclusions as to the SFH of the system at hand.

Chapter 4

Star Formation and Chemical Enrichment Histories of the Small Magellanic Cloud

I declare that the research presented in this chapter represents the content of the original work that I am currently conducting and planning to submit to the peer-reviewed Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society:

Sakowska, Joanna D., Noël, Noelia E. D., Ruiz-Lara, Tomás, et al. 2024, MNRAS, "Star formation history of the Small Magellanic Cloud with SMASH".

Statement of Contribution: I have made all of the contributions to the analysis and writing of these results, with extremely valuable guidance and feedback from Dr. N. E. D. Noël, Dr. T. Ruiz-Lara, and Dr P. Massana. I binned the data into smaller regions, ran the individual star formation histories, estimated the line-of-sight depths for every region, and re-calculated the final SFH. I have extensively analysed and described all of the results.

4.1 Abstract

I present the spatially-resolved star formation history (SFH) of the Small Magellanic Cloud's (SMC) body and periphery, covering at least 31 deg^2 of the galaxy and reaching as far as 5.47° (5.86 kpc). The SFHs have been corrected for the line-of-sight depth effects, measured to reach up to ~ 23 kpc in the northeastern and southeastern SMC. Overall, I find star formation enhancements at ~ 2 Gyr ago, ~ 1.3 Gyr ago, ~ 0.9 Gyr ago, ~ 0.5 Gyr ago, ~ 0.2 Gyr ago, and a young burst occurring presently. I display a spatial map of stellar mass formation across the SMC's epochs, showing unequivocal evidence of star formation towards the LMC during these enhancements. Before this, the inner SMC was star forming at an increasing pace until a significant drop ~ 4 Gyr ago. Soon after, star formation was significantly reignited in the outskirts following a possible SMC/LMC close encounter ~ 1.5 -2 Gyr ago. The radial SFH results I present here suggest a positive age gradient across the SMC- the exact onset and cause of the age gradient is difficult to constrain. Possible scenarios include 'outside-in' quenching, radial migration of stars, or an accreted stellar halo. Finally, I present photometric metallicity

maps that show hints of a metallicity gradient towards the LMC, finding a mean metallicity $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -0.94 \pm_{0.07}^{0.06}$. These results are highly important towards constraining the chemical evolution of a highly tidally disrupted galaxy, and the orbital history of the Magellanic Clouds.

4.2 Introduction

The Magellanic Clouds (MCs) have significantly progressed our understanding of galaxy evolution. Not only does their proximity enable a holistic picture of a galactic ecosystem in exquisite detail, but the interconnected nature of the MCs and the Milky Way (MW) provides important information on how galactic mergers proceed, a phenomenon frequently observed throughout the Universe (e.g., [Whitmore et al. 2010](#); [Wild et al. 2014](#); [Weaver et al. 2018](#); [Paudel et al. 2018](#)). Studying the MC's interactive history through star formation history (SFH) determinations allows us to explore the role of the environment on galactic quenching, chemical enrichment and mixing, and on the sizes and morphologies of tidally disrupted galaxies, among others.

SFH studies of the SMC have historically either prioritised wide field coverage of the SMC with ground-based telescopes at the expense of deep photometry ([Harris & Zaritsky 2004](#); [Rubele et al. 2015, 2018](#)) or used photometry reaching below the oldest Main Sequence (MS) turnoffs (oMSTO), covering small fields (e.g., [Noël et al. 2009](#); [Cignoni et al. 2012](#); [Cignoni et al. 2013](#); [Weisz et al. 2013](#)). [Harris & Zaritsky \(2004\)](#) performed the first spatially large ($4 \times 4.5^\circ$), global SFH of the SMC. Albeit the coverage, the photometry was relatively shallow, not reaching the oMSTO. They found enhancements at ~ 0.06 Gyr ago, ~ 0.4 Gyr ago, and ~ 2.5 Gyr ago, which were preceded by a quiescent star formation period from $3 \text{ Gyr} < t < 8.4 \text{ Gyr}$. As the oldest MS stars accessed were $\sim 2 - 3$ Gyr old, age/metallicity determinations of the intermediate and older populations hold large uncertainties. Instead, [Noël et al. \(2007, 2009\)](#) used 12 relatively small ($8'.85 \times 8'.85$) fields which resolved stars below the oMSTO. In contrast to [Harris & Zaritsky \(2004\)](#), the work by [Noël et al. \(2007, 2009\)](#) found a significant intermediate-age population across all fields, thanks to the information provided by stars below the oMSTO. [Noël et al. \(2007, 2009\)](#) also showed, for the first time, that interactions with the LMC could have been the main trigger of the conspicuous difference between the recent SFH in the eastern parts and the lack of stars younger than ~ 2 Gyr in the western areas of the SMC. The most recent wide-field SMC SFH work was done by [Rubele et al. \(2018\)](#), who surveyed 23.57 deg^2 of the SMC with the near-infrared VMC survey data finding a recent burst at $\sim 0 - 0.2$ Gyr ago, and extended star formation from $\sim 2 - 8$ Gyr ago, with a peak at $\sim 4 - 6.5$ Gyr ago. Unfortunately, their data only reaches the oMSTO (and does not go below it) limiting their findings.

In this context, SMASH photometry offers the best compromise of the two aspects to date, providing a contiguous coverage of the SMC hand-in-hand with stars resolved well below the oMSTO. [Massana et al. \(2022\)](#) utilised SMASH photometry to obtain SFH results of the SMC's main body and periphery. Early results show current star formation, in addition to four distinct global star formation peaks ~ 1.1 Gyr ago, ~ 2 Gyr ago, and ~ 3 Gyr ago which coincide with the peaks presented in [Ruiz-Lara et al. \(2020\)](#) (who also computed an SFH of the LMC using SMASH data). In addition, comparisons of the spatially resolved SFHs suggest that mutual interactions between the SMC/LMC could have affected the evolution of the Northern arm of the LMC. Despite these exciting initial results, the depth and coverage of SMASH data hold vast potential for more intricate MCs' SFH investigations- such as obtaining SFHs across the SMC considering the morphology of the region at hand.

FIGURE 4.1: A 2D projected map of the SMASH DR2 dataset studied divided into Voronoi bins. The corresponding Voronoi bin numbers are annotated. I marked the main SMC body with a 1° and 2° radii annulus.

In this Chapter, I build upon the pioneering work by [Massana et al. \(2022\)](#). In Section 4.4 I apply the updated SFH derivation methodology (first presented in Chapter 2) to derive 76 spatially resolved SFHs across the SMC which account for the SMC’s line-of-sight depth effects. In Section 4.5 I present a 2D map of the line-of-sight depths derived across the SMC. In Section 4.6 I present the SFHs- I analyse the global SFH (Section 4.6.1), the radially integrated SFH (Section 4.6.2), and the 2D maps of average age and fraction of stars formed as a function of time (Section 4.6.3). In Section 4.7 I present, for the first time, the SMC chemical enrichment histories as derived from SMASH data. I provide the global chemical enrichment history (Section 4.7.1), the radially integrated chemical enrichment history (Section 4.7.2), and the 2D maps of average metallicity and metallicity a function of time (Section 4.7.3). I discuss my findings and outline future work in Section 4.8, concluding in Section 4.9. With these results, I build a state-of-the-art picture of the SMC, depicting its chemical and morphological evolution since its beginnings.

4.3 Data

I obtain the spatially resolved SFH and chemical enrichment history of the SMC using SMASH DR2. Specifically, I studied Fields 4, 5, 6, 7, 9, 10, 11, 12, 14, 15, 16, 178 (see Figure 1 of [Nidever et al. 2021](#) for reference)¹, covering at least 31 deg^2 of the SMC. The star/galaxy separation, dust correction applied, and distance modulus assumed are consistent with the work presented in Chapter 2. That is, I selected stars using the $-2.5 < \text{SHARP} < 2.5$ photometric

¹Field 3 (a field in the south-west, adjacent to bins 19, 24, 25, 36, 71) has been excluded from this work due to earlier problems with the artificial star tests (ASTs). These errors have been partially resolved in May 2023. It is recommended that a thorough SFH of Field 3 is left as future work

constraint and with uncertainties less than 0.3 mag, corrected for interstellar dust and reddening using Choi et al. (2018a), and adopted a distance modulus to the SMC of $(m - M_o) = 18.96$ (de Grijs & Bono, 2015). This produced a catalogue with at least 20 billion stars. All of the fields included have had their corresponding ASTs completed. The AST procedure is described in Section 2.3.2. I divided the data into 76 spatial bins (each containing on average $\sim 274,000$ stars) following the Voronoi tessellation scheme (Cappellari & Copin 2003). In Figure 4.1 I show a map of the SMC with the Voronoi bins annotated by number. To ensure I include the highest quality of data, I excluded bins where the photometry was measured to be at least 50% complete from our analysis. These bins corresponded to the central, most crowded regions of the SMC (bins 9, 11, 12, 20, 21, 22, 23). This benchmark is also compatible with the cut applied in Massana et al. (2022).

4.4 Star Formation History derivation

To compute the global SFH for all 76 observed CMDs, I followed the procedure outlined in Section 2.4 for the northeastern shell structure. Here, I summarise the procedure and highlight any differences.

I created 76 individual synthetic CMDs corresponding to the 76 observed regions studied using the global synthetic population described in Section 2.4.1. Next, I used the spatial boundaries of the region to tailor the results of the ASTs to each Voronoi bin. This information was used by DiSPaR to simulate a degree of observational effects into the synthetic CMD (corresponding to the bin) by ‘dispersing’ the synthetic stars from their original positions in accordance with the level of crowding measured. Finally, I used THESTORM and employed the bundle strategy demonstrated in Section 2.4.1 to obtain the SFH of the region at hand. For consistency, THESTORM parameters set follow exactly those applied to derive the SFH of the shell in Section 2.4.1. I solved for the first SFH (with no line-of-sight depth considered) twice. The first time I used the program’s ‘Grid search’ setting. Here, the code sampled positions in a colour-magnitude grid around the entire CMD searching for the position where the χ^2 is at its minimum. The shifts are performed to minimise the effects of possible mismatches between the observed photometric system and the bolometric corrections when creating the synthetic CMDs. To robustly compare the different regions of the galaxy it is important to use an average colour and magnitude shift for all 76 regions. For example, at a given age, a higher stellar metallicity translates into redder colours. Hence, if we do not use the same colour and magnitude shift, we lose the ability to compare the stellar populations in different parts of the galaxy. From this step, I obtained the required colour and magnitude shifts. Finally, I re-solved the entire SMC data for the SFH following the methodology described in Section 2.4.1 (fractionally shifting the colour-magnitude and the age metallicity grids around the average colour and magnitude shift, i.e. [+0.1, +0.04]).

Once I obtained the first SFH result for all 76 regions, I proceeded to measure the line-of-sight depth from all 76 RC luminosity functions following the methodology alluded to in Section 2.4.2. As a reminder, I define the line-of-sight depth as the full width at half maximum (FWHM) of the best-fitting distance distribution used. In most cases, the RC luminosity function was Gaussian-like with a clear luminosity peak. This allowed me to fit the solution RC luminosity function’s peak to the brightest, observed RC luminosity function peak. However, a few regions in the northeastern and southeastern SMC showed hints of ‘double’ RCs, i.e. two (or more) peaks in the red clump luminosity function. The double RC was first presented in Figure 2.2

FIGURE 4.2: A 2D projected map of the best fitting line-of-sight depths across the entire SMASH dataset studied. I added circular rings to mark areas with 1, 2, 3, and 4° radius from the SMC centre. In the East ($\xi \geq -2$), line-of-sight depths up to ~ 23 kpc are best-fitting. Masked out are the very central bins not included in the global SFH. See the text for details.

of Section 2.3.3 since it is also observed in the periphery region studied in Chapter 2. In these cases, I fit the solution RC luminosity function to both the centre of the peaks and the most prominent RC peak, adopting the line-of-sight depth which gave the best Kolmogorov–Smirnov (KS) test result. In all cases, both fitting approaches gave similar line-of-sight depth distances.

4.5 Line-of-sight depths across the SMC

In Figure 4.2 I present the results on the best-fitting line-of-sight depths across the SMC. I added circular rings to mark areas within 1°, 2°, 3°, and 4° radii of the SMC centre. Note that the SMC has not been projected with a position angle and inclination (I will do this for radially integrated SFHs in Section 4.6.2). Here, I re-iterate that the main aim of the work is to measure the appropriate line-of-sight depth which, once incorporated, improves our SFH recovery rather than a full characterisation of the geometry of the SMC.

I find that the line-of-sight depth effect in the CMDs does not measure more than ~ 6 kpc within a 0 - 1° radius centred on the main body. Between 1 - 2°, the northeast displays larger line-of-sight depths than the rest of the bins within this area, reaching up to ~ 9.5 kpc (bin 48), suggestive of a line-of-sight depth gradient from the centre of the SMC towards its northeast. In fact, between 2 - 2.5° (not drawn) in the east, the line-of-sight depths consistently reach up to ~ 10 kpc. In the Western SMC, bin 57 has a significantly larger line-of-sight depth in comparison to the neighbouring regions. On closer inspection of the observed CMD, there is contamination from the MW globular cluster Tuc 47 along the RGB (and potentially RC). This is also the case for bin 58 (due to the presence of NGC 362). While I do remove most of the MW contamination with

our bundle strategy, the approach is insufficient to remove Tuc 47 and NGC 362 stars given the contamination is not constrained to the redder part of the CMD. In the immediate future I plan on cleaning these regions using the method presented in [Massana et al. \(2020\)](#) and re-computing the SFHs in these bins. Between $2.5\text{-}4^\circ$ in the eastern SMC we consistently reach significantly larger line-of-sight depths, ranging from ~ 13 to ~ 23 kpc. The CMDs belonging to these bins show the presence of double red clumps. For some regions (e.g. bin 61) there appear to be four peaks. While in [2.4.2.1](#) I have shown hints of a double RC feature in the northeastern SMC, with this data I unequivocally show the wide-spread presence of this feature in the eastern SMC. Some of the data suggest very small line-of-sight depths, such as ~ 0 to ~ 1 kpc. A visual inspection of those regions shows that the observed RC is not significantly affected by a line-of-sight depth, given the solution CMD replicates the RC dimensions well. It is also possible that, by simulating the crowding in the CMD, I account for the depth effect when the line-of-sight depth is smaller than the level of crowding in the CMD.

[Subramanian et al. \(2017\)](#); [El Youssoufi et al. \(2021\)](#) fit Gaussian profiles to the SMC's RC luminosity functions from the near-infrared VMC dataset; for the inner 1° and 2° , their best fitting Gaussian parameters suggest line-of-sight depths of $1\sigma = \sim 6$ kpc (in the FWHM definition adopted here, ~ 14 kpc). Also using RC stars from the VMC dataset, [Tatton et al. \(2021\)](#) estimated the depths across the SMC main body finding and average at $1\sigma = \sim 7.8$ kpc (~ 17 kpc). Although I present results for the inner 2° (≤ 10 kpc) that appear underestimated in comparison to those works, it is worth mentioning that they do make assumptions on the RC population effects and do not have SFH information on those regions, which significantly varies across the SMC. In this context, the methodology presented here agrees better with [Nidever et al. \(2013\)](#), who used RC luminosity functions from a SFH derivation to study the extent of the SMC's bimodality across island fields in the SMC's periphery at $\sim 4^\circ$ and beyond. For field 40S071 from ([Nidever et al., 2013](#)), which overlaps with bins 60 and 61, they quote a line-of-sight depth of $\text{FWHM} = \sim 22$ kpc, in agreement with our results ($\sim 21/\sim 22$ kpc). They measured the distance between the two RC peaks as ~ 12 kpc by re-constructing the bimodalities observed using two Gaussian distributions. [Subramanian et al. \(2017\)](#); [El Youssoufi et al. \(2021\)](#); [Omkumar et al. \(2021\)](#) also measure a $\sim 10\text{-}12$ kpc separation, and agree that signatures of bimodality appear from 2.5° onwards- this shift is also distinctly seen in [Figure 4.2](#) between $2.5 - 3^\circ$. Although I have already mentioned in [Section 2.3.3](#) that the bimodal features are linked to the tidal stripping that occurred during the formation of the Magellanic Bridge, I add that [Subramanian et al. \(2017\)](#) present a strong case for the tidally stripped component originating from the inner SMC. The authors argue that the $2 - 2.5^\circ$ benchmark is compatible with the tidal radius of the last pericentric passage of the SMC - the direct SMC/LMC collision $\sim 150 - 250$ Myr ago may have been strong enough to strip stars and gas from the inner 2.5 kpc of the SMC, leading to the formation of the Magellanic Bridge ([Besla et al. 2012](#); [Choi et al. 2022](#)). The impact of the event was not as pronounced in the central regions, explaining the lack of double RC features on the main body.

In conclusion, although the line-of-sight depth estimates for the inner 2° of the SMC seem underestimated, the match between the observed RC and the SFH solution RC appears good. The line-of-sight depth patterns observed 2.5° onwards in [Figure 4.2](#) agree remarkably well with the literature. The line-of-sight depths estimate for regions with clear RC bimodality (e.g., bin 60, 61) match extremely well to [Nidever et al. \(2013\)](#). As such, these results represent the geometry of the SMC well and will be used to improve the SFHs derived in the next [Section 4.6](#).

FIGURE 4.3: The global star formation and cumulative mass formation history of the SMC with the line-of-sight depth accounted for. Top: I find star formation enhancements at ~ 2 Gyr, ~ 1.3 Gyr, ~ 0.9 Gyr, ~ 0.5 Gyr, ~ 0.2 Gyr and one currently. I also find extended star formation, which peaked ~ 4 Gyr ago. See Section 4.6.1. Bottom: cumulative mass formation across the SMC. The 50% and 90% cumulative mass benchmarks are marked.

4.6 Star Formation Histories of the SMC

In the Appendix, I provide all of the SFHs (including their cumulative mass formation and chemical enrichment histories) corresponding to the 76 Voronoi bins. To dissect these results, understand how stars are distributed along the SMC, and shed light on the SMC's formation and evolution, in what follows I will show (i) the global SFH (the averaged SFH from all 76 Voronoi bins), (ii) the radially averaged SFH (the SFH and the stellar populations as a function of radius across the SMC), and (iii) a 2D map of the average ages of the Voronoi bins across the SMC, which is then analysed as a function of time from 13.7 Gyr ago until the present time.

4.6.1 The global star formation history

In the top panel of Figure 4.3 I present the results I obtained on the global SFH of the SMC. I combined all of the spatial SFHs and, to ensure the highest quality of results, I excluded the SFHs that belong to bins containing photometry less than 50% complete at i band ~ 2.5 mag. I present the results after the respective line-of-sight depths have been simulated for every region. The SMC has experienced young star formation enhancements at ~ 0.2 Gyr ago, ~ 0.5 Gyr ago, ~ 0.9 Gyr ago, and one presently. It experienced intermediate-age star formation peaks at ~ 1.3 Gyr ago and ~ 2 Gyr ago, including extended star formation from its beginnings until around ~ 4 Gyr ago. While it is likely that short (~ 0.1 Gyr) star formation bursts after 3.5 Gyr could be unresolved (as shown by Figure 3.3 in Section 3.3.1) I show that we are able to recover star

FIGURE 4.4: Comparison of this work (purple) versus [Massana et al. \(2022\)](#) (yellow). In grey I highlight the SFR peaks seen in [Massana et al. \(2022\)](#).

FIGURE 4.5: The global SFH of the SMC compared against that of the LMC's northern arm and its southern region from [Ruiz-Lara et al. \(2020\)](#) (also done with SMASH data). In grey I highlight the SFR peaks seen in [Ruiz-Lara et al. \(2020\)](#). I find star formation synchronicity now, ~ 0.2 Gyr, ~ 0.5 Gyr, ~ 1 Gyr and ~ 2 .

formation enhancements at these ages (albeit with a larger age dispersion) and therefore can make comprehensive conclusions about the SMC's evolution at those times.

In Figure 4.4 I present a comparison between the results I obtain and those from [Massana et al. \(2022\)](#), who have presented the global SFH results of the SMC using this SMASH dataset (the SFH was only presented, excluding the cumulative mass formation or chemical enrichment results). [Massana et al. \(2022\)](#) find a current star formation enhancement, and one at ~ 0.45 Gyr ago, ~ 1.1 Gyr ago, ~ 2 Gyr ago, and ~ 3 Gyr ago, followed by extended star formation $\sim 6.5 - \sim 9$ Gyr ago. The work I present here shows a current enhancement and further enhancements at ~ 0.2 Gyr ago, ~ 0.5 ago, ~ 0.9 Gyr ago, ~ 1.3 Gyr ago, ~ 2 Gyr ago, and extended intermediate star formation which peaked ~ 4 Gyr ago. The main differences in our results are (i) the resolution of the ~ 1.1 Gyr peak into ~ 0.9 Gyr and ~ 1.3 Gyr, and (ii) the increased star formation rate at 4 Gyr which blended in the previously reported 3 Gyr peak (which we also see in our data, albeit slightly shifted in age). The differences between our global SMC results are likely attributed to three different factors. I use an updated version of the BaSTI-IAC library to the versions employed in [Massana et al. \(2022\)](#) and [Ruiz-Lara et al. \(2020\)](#)² that might explain the higher

²In summary, the main differences between the models used by [Ruiz-Lara et al. \(2020\)](#); [Massana et al. \(2022\)](#) and this work are (i) new models account for new conductive opacity by [Cassisi et al. 2007](#), this produces a better match

star formation rate at the intermediate ages (3.5 Gyr ago - 6 Gyr ago) outside of the error bars of [Massana et al. \(2022\)](#). I also solve for the SFH with a finer age-binning metallicity grid than the one used in [Massana et al. \(2022\)](#), which potentially increased the resolution of the peaks. Finally, I have extended the [Massana et al. \(2022\)](#) results by including the line-of-sight depth into the SFH derivation. The differences between the results could be from a combination of those three factors.

As to other wide-field SFH works in literature, [Rubele et al. \(2018\)](#) find a burst at $\sim 0 - 0.2$ Gyr ago and extended star formation from ~ 2 Gyr ago - 8 Gyr ago (peaking at ~ 4 Gyr ago - 6.5 Gyr ago). While this is compatible with our findings, the lack of stronger, conspicuous bursts in the ~ 2 Gyr ago - 8 Gyr ago period suggests somewhat reduced resolution (See section 5.1 and Figure 4 of [Massana et al. \(2022\)](#) for a comparison between the SFH resolution from SMASH data against that achieved by [Rubele et al. \(2015, 2018\)](#) for the VMC survey). [Harris & Zaritsky \(2004\)](#) found star formation bursts at ~ 0.06 Gyr ago, ~ 0.4 Gyr ago, and ~ 2.5 Gyr ago, with a relatively quiescent period from ~ 3 Gyr ago - 8.4 Gyr ago, and a broad, comparably weak enhancement from ~ 3 Gyr ago to 5 Gyr ago. The young enhancements are compatible with Figure 4.3, and the authors' relatively weak ~ 1.1 Gyr enhancement could be a blend of the ~ 0.9 Gyr and ~ 1.3 Gyr peaks I present here. For the intermediate-age population, however, while I also find a ~ 3 Gyr to ~ 5 Gyr enhancement I find it to be comparable in strength to recent star formation, unlike the weaker SFR pattern shown in [Harris & Zaritsky \(2004\)](#).

After integrating the star formation rate over time, in the bottom panel of Figure 4.3 I present my results on the cumulative mass formation (CMF) of the SMC. My results show that the SMC has slowly assembled its stars, reaching the halfway 50% point (marked with a dashed line) around ~ 5.5 Gyr ago. A halfway point ~ 5.5 Gyr ago is somewhat compatible with [Rubele et al. \(2018\)](#), who quote ~ 6.3 Gyr, although it is considerably younger than [Harris & Zaritsky \(2004\)](#)'s estimate of ~ 8.4 Gyr. The differences between these estimates are likely due to factors discussed above such as different coverage areas and photometric depth. Finally, I stress that the CMF is only representative of the stars present in our CMDs. The CMF does not account for stellar migration or tidal disruption due to the influence of the LMC- for example, SMC member stars have been detected in the Magellanic Bridge which is not studied as part of this work ([Noël et al. 2013, 2015](#)) and even on the LMC itself ([Olsen et al. 2011](#)). However, qualitative conclusions using the CMF results can still be made.

To contextualise my results with the role of the LMC, similar to Figure 2.8 in Chapter 2 for the northeastern shell, in Figure 4.5 I present a direct comparison between our global SMC SFH result against the LMC's SMASH SFH results from [Ruiz-Lara et al. \(2020\)](#) for both the northern and southern arm. Over the last ~ 0.5 Gyr my results show clear synchronicity in the star formation rate between the SMC and the LMC, with mutual peaks at ~ 0.5 Gyr ago, ~ 0.2 Gyr ago, and one happening now. In the intermediate ages, there is a synchronised peak at ~ 2 Gyr ago. [Massana et al. \(2022\)](#) present a similar comparison, showing SFH synchronicity between the LMC and the SMC over the last ~ 3.5 Gyr. The reason I do not find synchronicity beginning ~ 3.5 Gyr ago is because of the updated stellar evolution library used for the new SMC result. As such, an updated SFH of the LMC, generated with the same stellar evolution library as this work would be required given we cannot unequivocally date the start of the SMC/LMC

to the Red clump; (ii), new models also account for atomic diffusion whereas the previous BaSTI-IAC models did not; (iii), the updated BaSTI-IAC models use the [Caffau et al. 2011](#) solar mixture. The lowest metallicity of the new library is now lower ($Z = 0.00001$) than before ($Z = 0.0001$)

synchronicity to as much precision as [Massana et al. 2022](#). In any case, my results uphold the SFH synchronicity seen across both galaxies.

4.6.2 Radial analysis of the star formation history

The global SFH presented in the previous section gives an overall picture of the evolution of the SMC and allows us to place our work within the context of what is known about the formation and evolution of this galaxy. In this Section, I discuss the radially integrated SFH, fully exploiting the spatial resolution that SMASH data enables. The following interpretations are made assuming no net radial migration of stars, although it is highly likely that the SMC has experienced it (see Section [4.8](#)).

FIGURE 4.6: Top: Map illustrating the radial subdivision of the SMC into 7 parts (in steps of 0.85°). Overlaid in grey is a stellar density map of the SMC for reference. The SMC has been projected with a position angle $PA = 178^{\circ}$ and inclination $i = 42^{\circ}$ (Tatton et al. 2021). The most crowded central bins are excluded. See text for details. Bottom: the results for the combined radial SFHs (top panel) and combined CMFs (bottom panel).

FIGURE 4.7: The results for the combined radial SFHs and CMFs. The top two panels show the SFH results for the inner $0^{\circ} - 2.56^{\circ}$ and for the inner $2.56^{\circ} - 5.47^{\circ}$ of the SMC, respectively. The two bottom panels show the CMF results for the inner $0^{\circ} - 2.56^{\circ}$ and for the inner $2.56^{\circ} - 5.47^{\circ}$ of the SMC, respectively. See the text for further details.

In Figure 4.6 (top) I subdivided the SMC radially into 7 parts (in steps of $\sim 0.85^{\circ}$). Overlaid in grey is a stellar density map of the SMC for reference. The SMC has been projected with a position angle $PA = 178^{\circ}$ and inclination $i = 42^{\circ}$ (Tatton et al. 2021). At the bottom part of Figure 4.6 I present the results for the combined radial SFHs (top panel) and combined CMFs (bottom panel). In Figure 4.7 I present the same result but for $0^{\circ} - 2.56^{\circ}$ of the SMC (first and

third panel, SFH and CMF respectively) and $2.56^\circ - 5.47^\circ$ of the SMC (second and last panel, SFH and CMF respectively).

The enhancements in the inner 1.71° trace well the pattern seen in the global SFH in Figure 4.3. Beginning ~ 400 Myr ago, the inner 1.71° is star forming at its highest rate (in comparison to the rest of the SMC's lifetime). This star formation is ongoing and decreases radially in scale out to about 5.47° of the SMC. We also see this enhancement in the LMC's northern arm (Figure 2.8). In Section 2.6.2 I discuss the combined effect of the LMC and MW on the SMC's recent SFH.

The build-up of the SMC throughout the old and intermediate ages is interesting. Beginning $\sim 11-11.5$ Gyr, the SFR starts to rise at all radii. For the inner 2.56° , the star formation steadily rises until it peaks ~ 4 Gyr ago and drops at around $\sim 4-3.5$ Gyr. From $3.42^\circ - 2.56^\circ$, the SFR is constant from 10-4 Gyr until a trough at $\sim 3 - 2.5$ Gyr. Lastly, from $5.47^\circ - 3.42^\circ$ the SFR peaks from 10 Gyr and gradually plateaus at ~ 5 Gyr ($4.27 - 5.47^\circ$) and $3.5-3$ Gyr ($4.27^\circ - 3.42^\circ$). Then, beginning ~ 3 Gyr ago, the SFR gradually begins to rise with decreasing radii, i.e. from the outer (5.47°) SMC at ~ 3 Gyr ago, to the inner (0.85°) SMC rising in SFR from 2 Gyr ago. These patterns suggest that the SMC's periphery was star forming from ~ 11 Gyrs before becoming quiescent from $\sim 5 - 3$ Gyr ago, until star formation re-ignited from around ~ 3 Gyr in the periphery, and henceforth the SFR gradually increased from the outer to the inner SMC before peaking at the close encounter ~ 2 Gyr ago.

In terms of cumulative mass formation, for the outer $5.47^\circ - 2.56^\circ$ (nearly 1.71° too) of the SMC, 90% of stars formed 2 Gyr ago and 50% of stars formed $\sim 7 - 9$ Gyr ago ($\sim 6 - 9$ Gyr ago if you count $1.71^\circ - 2.56^\circ$) too. This is in stark contrast to the result for the inner 1.71° of the SMC, where 90% of stars formed ~ 1 Gyr ago and 50% of stars formed $\sim 5 - 5.5$ Gyr ago.

In Figure 4.8 I present the radial stellar population gradients across the SMC up to 5.27° . Given the asymmetry of the SMC and the influence of the LMC in its northeastern/eastern outskirts, a radial profile may not be the best descriptor of its age. However, insightful observations can still be made. The average age of the stellar populations steadily increases- from $\sim 3.5/4$ Gyr in the very inner SMC, up to a plateau of ~ 6 Gyr $\sim 3^\circ$ from the centre. The young (1 Gyr) populations are limited to the inner 3° . The younger intermediate-aged populations ($1 < \text{age} < 4$ Gyr) follow a U-shaped trajectory, dominating the inner 1° before decreasing to a plateau at 3° and increasing again to a plateau at 4.4° . The older intermediate-aged populations ($4 < \text{age} < 8$ Gyr) follow a knee-shape: ascending to a plateau from $1.6^\circ - 2.5^\circ$ and descending to a plateau at 4.4° . The presence of old populations is low from $0^\circ - 1^\circ$ before rising steadily to 4° and levelling off.

FIGURE 4.8: Radial stellar population gradients across the SMC. Top: average age across the SMC age against degrees from the SMC centre. Bottom: average fraction of different stellar populations contribution to the total stellar populations. Here, I subdivide into four categories: young (< 1 Gyr, blue), young-intermediate ($1 < \text{age} < 4$ Gyr, yellow), old-intermediate ($4 < \text{age} < 8$ Gyr, green) and old ($8 < \text{age} < 13.7$ Gyr, red).

4.6.3 2D analysis of the star formation history

FIGURE 4.9: A 2D map of the average ages of the stellar populations belonging to each Voronoi bin. The Voronoi bins are colour-coded by their average age, with the younger ages coloured with lighter hues and the older ages with darker ones.

The radial SFHs presented in the previous section highlighted the star formation history trends across the SMC. In this section, I dissect the spatially resolved results further and inspect the star formation histories of every Voronoi bin studied, mapping the 2D spatial distribution of the different stellar populations across the SMC.

In Figure 4.9 I present a 2D map of the average ages of the stellar populations present in every Voronoi bin. This map complements Figure 4.8 given that we can now contextualise the stellar populations with their exact locations on the SMC. The main body of the SMC is on average $\sim 3 - 4$ Gyrs old. The asymmetry of the SMC's populations is evident- the northeastern/eastern outskirts (facing the LMC) are, on average, younger than their northwestern counterparts. In Figure 4.10 I investigate this further and present the map of the stellar mass fractions formed in each Voronoi bin across time. The mass fraction is generated by integrating the SFH- i.e., the SFR over the time interval specified (in Gyr) and the area (pc^2). The resulting mass is normalised to the total mass formed in each Voronoi bin as a fraction of 1. I present the results beginning 13.7 Gyr ago until now. The time intervals chosen complement the enhancements seen in Figure 4.3.

The top row of Figure 4.10 represents the first few Gyrs of the SMC's life and its old stellar population. Many of the SMC's peripheral stars formed then, and considerable star formation also occurred within the inner SMC. This row could represent the SMC's old spheroidal shape emerging as known from RR Lyrae maps (Jacyszyn-Dobrzyniecka et al. 2017). The inner SMC experienced significant star formation in panel 8.0 - 6.0 Gyr. From panel 6.0 - 4.5 Gyr, however, star formation appears to shut down in the eastern outskirts, which continues in panels 4.5 -

3.5 Gyr, 3.5 - 2.5 Gyr. In panel 3.5 - 2.5 Gyr the SMC takes on an ellipsoidal shape, with a notable elongation towards the southwest. Interestingly, in panel 2.5 - 1.5 Gyr, star formation is reignited in a gradient towards the northeast, in coincidence with the close encounter with the LMC which occurred $\sim 1.5 - 2$ Gyr ago. While current models of the encounter do not have sufficient resolution to effectively constrain the position and orientation of the MCs with relation to each other ~ 2 Gyr ago with low uncertainty, it is most likely that the star formation is in the direction of the LMC. It is plausible, even, that the re-ignited star formation in panel 2.5 - 1.5 Gyr is due to ram pressure stripping of gas, given it is known to both trigger and quench star formation in dwarf-dwarf galaxy interactions (Kado-Fong et al. 2023). After this encounter, most of the star formation is concentrated on the main body in the 1.5 - 1.0 Gyr panel. The bottom row of Figure 4.10 represents the SMC's young populations. In these panels, we see the SMC's present-day shape emerge, i.e., the formation of its Wing and northeastern tip. In Figure 4.11 I focus on the young stellar mass fractions in more depth.

In Figure 4.11 I present the fraction of stars formed over the last 1 Gyr. I divide the 1 Gyr period into steps of 100 Myr (except for panel 1.0 - 0.8 Gyr). Most of the young stars in the SMC's periphery form in panel 1.0-0.8 Gyr. In panel 0.8 - 0.7 Gyr there is a stream of star formation towards the south of the SMC, which contracts in the next panel. In panel 0.8 - 0.7 Gyr there is also a hint of star formation resembling an 'arm-like' structure in the northwest/north, which is 'pulled' anticlockwise downwards in the next panel. In panel 0.6 - 0.5 Gyr star formation is prominent in the south before the SMC's wing and its northeastern tip emerge in panel 0.5 - 0.4 Gyr and 0.4 - 0.3 Gyr. These features structurally stand out in panels 0.3 - 0.2 Gyr, 0.2 - 0.1 Gyr, which correspond to the last pericentric passage of the SMC around the LMC, and the formation of the Magellanic Bridge. In panel 0.2 - 0.1 Gyr we also observe star formation along the SMC's bar. Finally, panel 0.1 - 0.0 Gyr conspicuously show star formation along the Magellanic Bridge and towards the LMC.

The results presented here agree with the stellar mass formation map presented in Rubele et al. (2018), who also find active star formation along the SMC's bar and Wing from approximately 0 - 1 Gyr, and widespread star formation across the SMC in the intermediate ages. They also agree with the results of Noël et al. (2007, 2009), who spatially resolved five main star formation bursts: (i) young 0.2 - 0.5 Gyr enhancement in all eastern fields (towards the LMC) and a central southern field, (ii) intermediate age burst at 1.5 - 2.5 Gyr and a stronger one at 4 - 5 Gyr (all fields), and (iii), one old 10 Gyr enhancement in all but western fields (where it is split into 8 and 12 Gyr). Figure 4.10 agrees well with all of these findings- the 0.3 - 0.0 Gyr panel shows conspicuous star formation in the eastern SMC (finding i) and panels 2.5 - 1.5 Gyr, 4.5 - 3.5 Gyr and 6.0 - 4.5 Gyr show wide-spread star formation on the main body (the last two panels are stronger, finding ii). The top row of Figure 4.10 shows the bursts described in (iii).

FIGURE 4.10: A map of stellar mass fractions across the SMC. The resulting mass is normalised to the total mass formed in each Voronoi bin as a fraction of 1. The age bins were selected to investigate the enhancements seen in Figure 4.3. The oldest to youngest stellar populations start from the top left to bottom right corners. The most crowded central bins are excluded.

FIGURE 4.11: A map of young (<1 Gyr) stellar mass fractions across the SMC. The resulting mass is normalised to the total mass formed in each Voronoi bin *over the last 1 Gyr* as a fraction of 1. The age bins are divided into steps of 100 Myr (except for panel 1.0 - 0.8 Gyr). The oldest to youngest stellar populations start from the top left to bottom right corners. The most crowded central bins are excluded.

4.7 The Chemical Enrichment Histories of the SMC

Finally, in this Section, I present the results of the chemical enrichment histories of the SMC. In the Appendix, I provide all of the chemical enrichment histories corresponding to the 76 Voronoi bins. Here, I dissect these results and understand how the SMC evolved chemically. In this section, I show (i) the global chemical enrichment history averaged from all 76 Voronoi bins, (ii), the radially averaged chemical enrichment histories and the metallicity Z as a function of radius and, (iii), a 2D map of the average metallicity (in Z and median Fe/H) across the SMC analysed as a function of time.

4.7.1 The global chemical enrichment history

In Figure 4.12 I present the chemical enrichment history of the SMC in terms of average metallicity. Over the last ~ 0.5 Gyr the SMC experienced significant metallicity enrichment which peaked at $Z \sim 0.009$ ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -0.2$) preceded by two metallicity bumps from $\sim 0.5 - 1.6$ Gyr (corresponding to ~ 0.9 Gyr, ~ 1.1 Gyr SFR peaks) which both peaked at $Z \sim 0.005$ ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -0.5$). In the intermediate ages, the average metallicity trend gradually increased with two bumps at approximately $\sim 1.6 - 3$ Gyr and $\sim 3 - 5$ Gyr ($Z \sim 0.003$, 0.0025 and $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim$

FIGURE 4.12: The global metallicity of the SMC with the line-of-sight depth accounted for in terms of average metallicity Z (orange).

FIGURE 4.13: The global metallicity of the SMC in with the line-of-sight depth accounted for in units of $[Fe/H]$ (blue). I compare this result against that of [Rubele et al. \(2018\)](#) (black, dashed lines). Overplotted in red are star cluster metallicities from the [Bica et al. \(2020\)](#) catalogue.

-1.1, -1.2, respectively). Finally, the metallicity plateaued at look back times older than ~ 8 Gyr. It is unlikely that the average Z between ~ 12 -13.7 Gyr is correct. At those times, we have very few SMC stars available, and any potential MW foreground contamination on the red side of the CMD can mimic a very metal-rich population. This, in turn, causes spreads in the metallicity which creates deviations in the metallicity average. In Figure 4.13 I compare my global metallicity result in terms of average $[Fe/H]$ (blue) to [Rubele et al. \(2018\)](#). Overall my $[Fe/H]$ is more metal-rich than [Rubele et al. \(2018\)](#), with a conspicuous $[Fe/H]$ peak ~ 0.2 Gyr ago that is not seen in [Rubele et al. \(2018\)](#). As a sanity check, I overlay SMC star cluster ages and metallicities from the [Bica et al. \(2020\)](#) catalogue (red). As we can see, the $[Fe/H]$ result presented in this thesis agrees well with the star clusters, and the $[Fe/H]$ peak ~ 0.2 Gyr ago is in better agreement with the star cluster metallicities than [Rubele et al. \(2018\)](#).

4.7.2 Radial analysis of the chemical enrichment history

In Figure 4.14 I present the results for the combined radial chemical enrichment histories. The radial subdivision follows that presented in Figure 4.6 (i.e., into 7 parts in steps of $\sim 0.85^\circ$). In the top panel, I present the results from all 7 parts. In the middle panel, I present the results from the first three parts (covering $0 - 0.85^\circ$, $0.85 - 1.71^\circ$, $1.71 - 2.56^\circ$, i.e. representative of the

main body of the SMC) and in the bottom for the last four parts (covering $2.56 - 3.42^\circ$, $3.42 - 4.27^\circ$, $4.27 - 5.12^\circ$ and $5.12 - 5.47^\circ$ of the SMC). The data reaches up to 5.47° of the SMC. Any sharp metallicity jumps (e.g. at 12 Gyr) seen here are related to the low SFR and therefore low number of stars affecting the average metallicity. Up to ~ 3 Gyr ago, the entire SMC followed a linear chemical enrichment history with little or no inflow of pristine gas (or it was quickly diluted) given no metallicity dips were detected. From $\sim 3 - 1.5$ Gyr ago, the outer SMC grows more metal-rich than the inner SMC (which slightly dips from $\sim 2 - 1.5$ Gyr ago) although both results appear within their error bars. At 1.5 Gyr, the metallicity jumps for all regions (except for the very outer SMC) at increasing intensity towards the centre of the SMC. Interestingly, this metallicity jump of the inner SMC puts it on par with the metallicity of the outer SMC. Next, the outer $2.56-5.47^\circ$ grows in metallicity, peaking at ~ 0.9 Gyr, and the inner 2.56° follows it (peaking at ~ 0.75 Gyr). The outer $2.56 - 5.47^\circ$ of the SMC also experienced a small 'bump' ~ 0.6 Gyr ago. Finally, the entire SMC dips in metallicity at ~ 0.5 Gyr before experiencing its most significant metallicity peak at ~ 0.25 Gyr.

These metallicity evolution trends support the underlying trends presented in this Chapter that the SMC was relatively undisturbed until its close encounter with the (more metal rich) LMC ~ 2 Gyr ago. It is plausible the outer parts of the SMC first experienced the metallicity enrichment from the LMC's gas before the inner SMC followed and sharply peaked in metallicity after the encounter. The same behaviour is observed around the ~ 1 Gyr burst, and the small bump observed ~ 0.6 Gyr ago in the outer SMC could be linked to a potential SMC/LMC encounter ~ 400 Myr ago (Cullinane et al. 2022; Navarrete et al. 2023). Given that the MCs are on their first infall into the MW, it is also likely the MCs experienced a significant metallicity enrichment thanks to the MW's CGM. The most significant metallicity peak seen, at ~ 0.25 Gyr, coincides with the MC's last encounter and the formation of the Magellanic Bridge.

In Figure 4.15 I plot the radially averaged metallicity gradient across the SMC up to 5.47° . As previously mentioned, given the SMC's irregular morphology a radial metallicity profile may not paint the most accurate picture of its global metallicity. Despite this, I point out features of interest. The metallicity profile exhibits an interesting 'U'-shape: the inner 1.8° radially decreases in metallicity, the SMC experiences a metallicity 'bump' at 2° and 3.5° , and then it increases outwards. As shown by the map in Figure 4.6, the outermost $3.42 - 5.47^\circ$ of the SMC studied represents the northeastern and southeastern SMC, which have been affected by the LMC. The increase in the metallicity, and therefore the U-shape of the profile, is expected. In fact, it is surprising that the metallicity in the outer SMC mirrors the inner SMC so well. One interpretation is that in this region there tidally stripped stars from the inner SMC by the LMC, which are contributing to this metallicity. In the next Section, we will analyse the 2D average metallicity map and touch on this scenario more.

FIGURE 4.14: The results for the combined radial average metallicity Z (top panel). The middle and bottom panels show the CMF results for the inner $0^\circ - 2.56^\circ$ and for the inner $2.56^\circ - 5.47^\circ$ of the SMC, respectively. See the text for further details.

FIGURE 4.15: Average metallicity Z radially across the SMC against degrees from the SMC centre.

4.7.3 2D analysis of the chemical enrichment history

Finally, in this Section, I map the 2D spatial distribution of the metallicity across the SMC. First I will present the results in terms of Z and then, in order to compare the results with spectroscopic studies, show the 2D metallicity map as median $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$.

FIGURE 4.16: A 2D map of the average metallicity Z for each Voronoi bin. The Voronoi bins are colour coded such that the more metal-rich bins are lighter and the more metal-poor bins darker. The most crowded central bins are excluded.

In Figure 4.16 I depict the average metallicity Z as a function of Voronoi bin. This map complements Figure 4.15 given that we can now contextualise the metallicity trends observed with their locations on the SMC. A striking feature of the map is that the SMC's eastern outskirts are significantly more metal-rich than the western outskirts. In fact, the east appears divided into two. Another interesting feature is the most metal-rich bin in the northeastern outskirts (bin 61). I will return to discuss bin 61.

In Figure 4.10 I break down this map as a function of time, beginning 13.7 Gyr ago until now. Every Voronoi bin represents the average metallicity Z during the depicted time interval. The time intervals chosen complement the enhancements seen in Figure 4.3. The age bins selected complement Figure 4.10. The top 1st and 2nd rows show the SMC from 13.7 Gyr until 3.5 Gyr ago. The colour bar is adjusted to resolve the metallicities better ($Z = 0.00001 - 0.04$). The 13.7 - 12.0 Gyr panel represents the very start of the SMC's lifetime. As explained previously, the high metallicities observed in this panel (and 12.0-10.0 Gyr) are most likely spurious and due to both the low number of SMC stars available and MW foreground contamination on the redder side of the CMD misread as a metal-rich population. The 10.0 - 8.0 Gyr panel shows a homogenous distribution of average metallicity, which increases in scale in panels 8.0-6.0 Gyr, and 6.0 - 4.5 Gyr (mostly around the SMC). At this time, the SMC's outskirts and periphery appear more metal-rich than its inner parts. In the 4.5 - 3.5 Gyr panel, the inner SMC increases

FIGURE 4.17: A map of average metallicity Z for every Voronoi bin across the SMC as a function of time. The age bins selected complement Figure 4.10. Note the colour bar has been adjusted in each row to resolve metallicities better. Top 1st row, 2nd row: 13.7 - 3.5 Gyr ($Z = 0.00001-0.04$). 3rd row: 3.5-1.0 Gyr ($Z = 0.02-0.10$). Bottom row: 1.0-0.0 Gyr ($Z = 0.05-0.22$). The most crowded central bins are excluded.

in Z while its outskirts drop. In the third row (i.e. 3.5 - 1 Gyr) I increase the colour bar to resolve the increased metallicity better ($Z = 0.02 - 0.10$). In the 3.5 - 2.5 Gyr panel, the average metallicity increases again, especially around the SMC's main body in the outskirts. In the 2.5 - 1.5 Gyr panel the metallicity jump is significant- the outskirts are clearly more metal-rich than the main body, perhaps related to gas mixing during the SMC/LMC encounter. At 1.5 - 1.0 Gyr, the metallicity drops slightly, although there appears to be a gradient towards the northeast. For the last row, I increase the colour bar to $Z = 0.05 - 0.10$. At 1.0 - 0.7 Gyr, the northeast and south are more metal-rich than the main body. The 0.7 - 0.3 Gyr shows a very interesting feature- there appear to be two arm-like components standing out in the direction of the LMC. Could this component trace in-situ star formation, directed by the gas dynamics at the time? Curiously, the northeastern component includes the location of the shell. Finally, the 0.3 - 0.0 Gyr window traces the direction of the Magellanic Bridge in metallicity.

FIGURE 4.18: A 2D map of the median $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ for each Voronoi bin. The Voronoi bins are colour-coded such that the more metal-rich bins are lighter and the more metal-poor bins are darker. The most crowded central bins are excluded.

The spatially-resolved photometric metallicities presented here can be cross-checked with spectroscopic studies of the SMC. [Dobbie et al. \(2014\)](#) (hereafter PD14) studied the calcium triplet (CaT) line contiguously across the SMC (radially, up to 5°) for ~ 3000 stars, quoting a median $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -0.99 \pm 0.01$. PD14 complement [Carrera et al. \(2008\)](#), who find a mean $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -1.00$ after measuring 350 stars in a $1\text{-}4^\circ$ radius. To enable comparison, in Figure 4.18 I present the average metallicity map (as seen in Figure 4.16) but in units of median $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$. All of the bins (excluding the inner regions) average to a median $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -0.91 \pm 0.08$ which falls in the error bars of PD14 (mean $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -0.94 \pm_{0.07}^{0.06}$ also agrees with [Carrera et al. \(2008\)](#)). In Figure 4.19 I overlay the PD14 fields and in Table 4.1 present the results of the comparison. In Figure 4.19 I colour code the fields with (a) green, if my $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ is within the error bars of the literature value, (b) amber if the $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ is within the quartiles of the literature value and (c) red if the $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ is outside of the quartiles. To fill in the coverage gap for the northeastern Voronoi bins 60, 61, I also compare with [Almeida et al. \(2023\)](#) (hereafter AA23), who studied the RGB stars in this region using the APOGEE spectroscopic survey ([Majewski et al. 2017](#)). I add this to the bottom of Table 4.1. In general, my photometric metallicity determinations are more metal-rich than spectroscopic determinations. However, this is to be expected, given that the studies presented target RGB stars which are more metal-poor and do not represent the young stellar populations. It is understandable that the SMC's Wing and northeastern tip, which have formed recently, do not perfectly match the results. I also note that I have performed this comparison for the metallicity results before the line-of-sight depth correction, and it is clear that accounting for the line-of-sight depth has lowered the global metallicity to be closer in line with the spectroscopy results.

The metallicity maps presented in this Section show that Voronoi bin 61 has a metallicity significantly higher on average than its surroundings. As discussed in Section 4.5, bin 61 is an

interesting region- it is home to tidally stripped structures, likely created by the stripping of stars from the central SMC during the formation of the Magellanic Bridge. Due to the presence of (at least) two, distinct populations separated by ~ 10 - 12 kpc, bin 61's CMD shows a 'double' RC which I measure to produce a large ~ 21 kpc line-of-sight depth measurement. There are a handful of factors contributing to the higher metallicity observed. Firstly, the stars stripped from the SMC's body should be more metal-rich than those found in the periphery, hence the average should be skewed higher than expected for this region. Secondly, this bin shows conspicuous, metal-rich star formation ~ 12 - 13.7 Gyr ago. This is unphysical and likely due to MW foreground contamination, especially since this bin is significantly far from the SMC's main body and likely contains far fewer SMC stars than other regions. Nevertheless, the metallicity I obtained for this region (combined with contributions from bin 59 and 60) is still within the error of AA2023's value for Field 6. In fact, this bin is a great example as to why correcting for the line-of-sight depth effect is worthwhile- before the depth correction for bin 61, I obtain mean $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -0.73$, which is 0.17 dex more metal-rich than after the correction ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -0.90$). As for the area covered by Field 6, before I correct for the line-of-sight depth I measure the region to have a mean $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -0.80$, which is out of the errorbars of AA2023 (and 0.14 dex higher than after I correct for the effect).

FIGURE 4.19: Figure 4.18 with the fields from Dobbie et al. (2014) and field SMC6 from Almeida et al. (2023) overlaid. A comparison between my results and the fields presented is available in Table 4.1. I colour code the fields by match- green, if the result is within the error bars of the field; amber, if the result is within the quartiles of the field value; and red, if the result is outside the quartiles of the field value.

PD14 field	PD14 median [Fe/H] (Q_1, Q_3)	Median [Fe/H]
C1	-0.93 ± 0.02 (-0.81, -1.07)	-0.92
C2	-0.97 ± 0.02 (-0.86, -1.10)	-0.84
C3	-0.98 ± 0.01 (-0.77, -1.03)	-0.93
C4	-0.93 ± 0.02 (-0.82, -1.07)	-0.83
3D06	-1.17 ± 0.03 (-1.06, -1.32)	-1.05
3D07	-1.01 ± 0.03 (-0.87, -1.20)	-0.99
3D08	-1.03 ± 0.03 (-0.94, -1.21)	-1.00
3D09	-1.02 ± 0.03 (-0.90, -1.21)	-0.97
3D10	-1.00 ± 0.03 (-0.88, -1.14)	-0.94
3D11	-1.09 ± 0.03 (-0.93, -1.24)	-1.00
3D12	-1.05 ± 0.04 (-0.92, -1.16)	-0.86
3D14	-1.10 ± 0.03 (-0.97, -1.31)	-0.96
3D15	-1.04 ± 0.04 (-0.93, -1.21)	-0.94
3D16	-1.13 ± 0.04 (-0.95, -1.31)	-0.96
AA23 field	AA23 mean [Fe/H]	Mean [Fe/H]
SMC6	-1.04 ± 0.13	-0.94

TABLE 4.1: A table detailing the comparison between the metallicities obtained in this work and spectroscopic studies. In the first column I detail the field name from Dobbie et al. (2014) (PD14) or Almeida et al. (2023) (AA23). In the middle column, I provide either the median [Fe/H] value from PD14 (including the 25th, and 75th quartile) or the mean [Fe/H] value from AA23. In the final column, I provide either my median [Fe/H] or mean [Fe/H] value.

4.8 Discussion and future work

The derived star formation and chemical enrichment histories of the SMC paint a detailed portrait of its evolutionary trajectory, characterised by distinct periods of enhanced and subdued star formation activity. Prior to this pattern, the SMC appears to have been growing its stellar content from its early days until just after ~ 4 Gyr ago, when its global star formation rate dropped dramatically. Following the ~ 2 Gyr enhancement, the global SFH analysis reveals prominent peaks in star formation occurring approximately ~ 1.3 Gyr, ~ 0.9 Gyr, ~ 0.5 Gyr, and ~ 0.2 Gyr ago, alongside ongoing star formation, indicative of a complex and dynamic history over, at least, the last ~ 2 Gyr. The stellar mass formation maps showcase discernible patterns of localised bursts of recent star formation, particularly towards the northeastern regions and along the SMC centre. Additionally, the analysis of photometric metallicity maps reveals subtle gradients across the SMC towards the LMC, with an average mean metallicity of $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -0.94 \pm_{0.07}^{0.06}$. The observed enhancements in star formation and average metallicity directed towards the LMC hint at the influence of gravitational interactions and tidal forces, underscoring the interconnected nature of the MC system.

The radially integrated SFH results presented widely agree that the SMC displays a positive age gradient, where the dominant stellar population becomes older as a function of radius from the centre (see Figure 4.8), suggestive of an ‘outside-in’ progression of star formation. Indeed, an outside-in formation scenario appears to contradict modern hydrodynamical simulations of galaxy formation given that, under the LCDM cosmological framework, galaxies are expected to form their inner parts first (‘inside-out’) before growing out to their present day sizes. There exist a few plausible explanations for a positive age gradient in the SMC from both environmental and internal perspectives.

One plausible explanation for the positive age gradient could be due to the radial migration of stars. [El-Badry et al. \(2016\)](#) performed an extensive investigation into how stellar feedback drives radial migration and population gradients in low-mass ($M_{\star} = 2 \times 10^6 - 5 \times 10^{10} M_{\odot}$) isolated dwarf galaxies using the Feedback in Realistic Environments (FIRE) simulations. The authors found that low-mass dwarf galaxies experience significant radial migration due to outflowing/inflowing gas clouds, which drive strong fluctuations in the overall galactic potential and affect the orbits of stars of all ages. The oldest stellar populations presented the strongest systematic net migration, moving as much as ~ 4 kpc from their original locations (for a galaxy of mass $M_{\star}(z=0) \approx 3 \times 10^8 M_{\odot}$), given they have experienced the most outflow/inflow cycles. Importantly, for all of the galaxies studied, the true age gradient inverted from negative to positive by $z=0$ due to stellar migration. The extent of stellar migration in the SMC is currently not well constrained. However, if stellar feedback drives dark matter coring, then we could expect the SMC to flaunt a cored DM profile due to dark matter “heating” by baryonic effects. While [De Leo et al. \(2023\)](#) do not find evidence for a DM core currently in the SMC, they find that the SMC is still big enough for baryonic feedback processes to heat DM and, therefore, stellar migration due to baryonic feedback in the SMC cannot be ruled out.

However, the SMC is not an isolated galaxy, and the influence of the LMC/MW on the SMC must not be understated. It is plausible that, over the last ~ 2 Gyr years (or beginning even earlier), the SMC underwent a degree of environmental quenching- for example, Figures 4.6 and 4.7 show a progressive SFR drop from the outer to inner SMC, just before a global enhancement ~ 2 Gyr ago. As previously discussed, there is prevailing observational evidence for an SMC/LMC

close encounter $\sim 1.5 - 2$ Gyr ago, linked to the formation of the gaseous Magellanic Stream and Leading Arm structures (e.g. [Nidever et al. 2008](#); [Fox et al. 2018](#)) and even the LMC's northern arm ([Ruiz-Lara et al. 2020](#)). Hence, we cannot rule out that a degree of gas removal could have occurred in, at least, the SMC ~ 2 Gyr ago shortly before star formation re-ignited. Additionally, if the MCs are approaching the MW for the first time, then the MCs have been travelling in an increasingly denser medium for some time. [Gallart et al. \(2008\)](#); [Meschin et al. \(2014\)](#) present strong evidence for environmental quenching of the LMC by the MW showing that, while the oldest population is coeval in all fields studied, the age of the youngest component of the dominant stellar population gradually increases with radius (detecting no populations younger than 1.5-1.3 Gyr 7.1° from centre) in correlation with the decreasing H I gas column density. The authors suggest that the decreasing H I gas column density (and therefore less gas available for star formation) may be due to a compression of the LMC's gas disc from the ram pressure exerted (or ram pressure stripping of the gaseous LMC itself) as the LMC approached the MW's halo. Following this finding, it is therefore highly likely that the SMC also suffered a degree of environmental quenching as it approached the MW together with the LMC. However, this scenario is likely not sufficient to explain the spatial distributions of the stellar populations older than ~ 2 Gyrs. A detailed comparison of the SFH results presented here with a H I gas column density map should be done as a future work, following the assumption that stellar migration has not significantly affected the SMC over the last ~ 1 Gyr.

Finally, a third plausible explanation for the age gradient is that the SMC experienced a merger event and accreted a stellar halo. It has been long speculated that the SMC experienced a major merger event given the kinematic discrepancies between the SMC's old stellar populations and its HI gas (e.g. [Bekki & Chiba 2008](#)) and the significant (0.5 dex) metallicity dispersion for the SMC cluster population younger than about 7.5 Gyr. The [Tsujimoto & Bekki \(2009\)](#) model predicts that a chemical signature of a major merger (specifically with a mass ratio of 1:1 to 1:4) would be reflected as a dip in the $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim 7.5$ Gyrs ago. While the work presented here does not clearly indicate any evidence of a merger, some spectroscopic star cluster studies have identified potential $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ dips (~ 6 Gyrs ago, [Saroorn et al. 2023](#)). So far no "smoking-gun" evidence has been found.

Looking ahead, there are several avenues for further quantitative exploration and refinement of the findings presented here. Most importantly, quantitative comparisons with theoretical models and simulations could provide deeper insights into the underlying mechanisms driving star formation and chemical enrichment within the SMC, offering valuable constraints for future studies. Exploring the role of environmental factors, such as interactions with the LMC and Milky Way, through detailed numerical simulations and modelling efforts could yield key predictions and further elucidate the drivers of star formation and chemical evolution within the SMC. In addition, these results would highly benefit from interpretation against [Ruiz-Lara et al. \(2020\)](#) results re-computed with the same stellar evolution library used here. This quantitative assessment would shed new light on the synchronicity of the MCs and help elucidate the complexities of the SMC-LMC-MW system.

4.9 Conclusions

In this Chapter, I have presented a spatially-resolved star formation and the chemical enrichment history of the Small Magellanic Cloud's main body and periphery with SMASH DR2. Using

deep CMDs that reach below the oMSTO I study over 31 deg^2 of the galaxy, reaching as far as 5.47° , greatly improving the coverage and age-resolution presented in previous studies. I apply my updated SFH derivation methodology which accounts for the line-of-sight depth effects across the SMC and provides the most comprehensive star formation history determination to date. Below I summarise my main findings:

- I provide a 2D map of the line-of-sight depths in the observed CMDs as given by the RC stars. These results reveal an increasing line-of-sight depth towards the eastern outskirts of the SMC from $\sim 2.5^\circ$, reaching up to $\sim 23 \text{ kpc}$ in the northeastern and southeastern SMC, which agrees with literature (e.g. [Nidever et al. 2013](#)).
- Globally, the SMC has experienced young star formation enhancements now, $\sim 0.2 \text{ Gyr}$, $\sim 0.5 \text{ Gyr}$, and $\sim 0.9 \text{ Gyr}$ ago. It experienced intermediate age star formation peaks at $\sim 1.3 \text{ Gyr}$ and $\sim 2 \text{ Gyr}$, including extended star formation from its beginnings until around $\sim 4 \text{ Gyr}$ ago, when the SFR plummeted globally. Notably, from $\sim 2 \text{ Gyr}$ onwards there are localised bursts of star formation, many of which are directed towards the LMC.
- The radially integrated SFH reveals a positive age gradient across the SMC. Several explanations for this age gradient have been explored in this chapter - from radial migration, to environmental quenching and the accretion of a halo due to a past merger event.
- The global chemical enrichment history shows average metallicity peaks at $\sim 2 - 2.5 \text{ Gyr}$, $\sim 1.3 \text{ Gyr}$, $\sim 0.9 \text{ Gyr}$ and $\sim 0.25 \text{ Gyr}$. The metallicity significantly increases beginning $\sim 0.5 \text{ Gyr}$ ago likely due to the influence of the MW's CGM. Before these trends, the SMC showed gradual metallicity enrichment. These results agree with star cluster ages and other photometric metallicity studies of the SMC.
- The radially integrated chemical enrichment history shows hints of metallicity enrichment due to gas inflow following encounters with the LMC. The average metallicity maps also reflect this, showing hints of metallicity gradients towards the LMC. There is evidence the SMC experienced an inflow of metal-rich gas following the SMC/LMC encounter $\sim 1.5-2 \text{ Gyr}$ ago.
- For the entire SMC, I obtain a mean $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -0.94 \pm_{0.07}^{0.06}$ which falls in the error bars of major spectroscopic studies. Finally, I show that accounting for the line-of-sight depth effect produces metallicities closer to spectroscopic literature values, especially in the case of the northeastern SMC.

To conclude, I have demonstrated the robustness of my updated SFH derivation method on the entire SMC with great outcomes. These results provide unprecedented, state-of-the-art insight into the evolutionary journey of the SMC undergoing significant tidal disruption by the LMC and the MW. Looking ahead, quantitative comparisons of these results with simulations will set unprecedented constraints on the history of the Magellanic Clouds.

Chapter 5

Developing a pipeline for the detection of ancient, metal-poor stellar overdensities in the Magellanic periphery

Statement of Contribution: I have made all of the contributions to the analysis presented here, with extremely valuable guidance and feedback from Dr. N. E. D. Noël and the DELVE collaboration. My work includes adapting the `simple` algorithm to the DELVE-MC catalogue (`simple_delvemc`), working with the DELVE collaboration to identify issues with the photometry, analysis, and discussion of the findings.

5.1 Abstract

Spanning $\sim 2200 \text{ deg}^2$ around the MCs, the DELVE-MC survey employs the DELVERED pipeline for robust photometry. The analysis I present here utilises an algorithm, `simple`, to identify old, metal-poor stellar overdensities. I also introduce the `simple_delvemc` algorithm, which I developed by adapting `simple` to enhance the searches for contiguous dwarf galaxies, and facilitate parameter fine-tuning. I partition the DELVE-MC catalogue into HEALPix pixels enabling systematic, organised searches, and addressing spurious candidate detections. I conducted careful validation of high-probability detections to compensate for eventual photometric issues. The contributions presented here optimise catalogue processing and candidate identification, advancing the detection of substructures/ultra-faint objects associated with the MCs.

5.2 Introduction

FIGURE 5.1: Footprint of the DELVE survey taken from (Drlica-Wagner et al. 2021, including Sakowska). Colour coded are the areas studied by three different observational programs. DELVE-WIDE covers $\sim 15,000 \text{ deg}^2$ in the $g, r, i, z \geq 23.5$ mag bands. DELVE-MC images $\sim 2200 \text{ deg}^2$ around the Magellanic Clouds in the $g, r, i \geq 24.5$ mag bands. Finally, DELVE-DEEP focuses on deep imaging of four Magellanic analogues (IC 5152, NGC 300, NGC 55, Sextans B) in the $g, i \geq 25.5$ mag bands. The Dark Energy Survey (DES) footprint is indicated in black. The thicker black line denotes the Galactic plane ($b = \pm 10^\circ$) denoted with dashed lines. In total, DELVE will combine public archival data with 126 DECam nights.

The DECam Local Volume Survey¹ (DELVE; Drlica-Wagner et al. 2021, 2022, all including Sakowska) aims to unravel the mysteries of the faintest and most DM-dominated galaxies, the UFDGs. DELVE is a deep, multi-component 126 night survey that uses the DECam on the 4-meter Blanco Telescope at Cerro Tololo Interamerican Observatory in Chile. DELVE additionally combines existing DECam data from surveys such as SMASH, Dark Energy Survey (DES, Dark Energy Survey Collaboration et al. 2016), DECam Legacy Survey (DECaLS, Dey et al. 2019), and DeROSITAS (Toba et al., 2022) to study a range of dwarf galaxies: from the Magellanic Clouds and their Local Volume analogues ($L \sim 10^9 - 10^{10} L_\odot$) to the faintest dwarf spheroidal galaxies around the Milky Way ($L \sim 10^3 L_\odot$) and other resolved stellar substructures. DELVE is split into 3 different observing programmes:

- DELVE-WIDE covers $\sim 15,000 \text{ deg}^2$ in the $g, r, i, z \geq 23.5$ mag bands over the entire high Galactic latitude southern sky. One of the main science drivers of DELVE-WIDE is to deliver a deep census of ultra-faint dwarf galaxies/clusters around the MW. DELVE-WIDE is also suitable for the study of resolved stellar structures, such as stellar streams, the remnants of tidally disrupted dwarf galaxies and globular clusters.
- DELVE-DEEP focuses on deep imaging of four Magellanic analogues (IC 5152, NGC 300, NGC 55, Sextans B) in the $g, i \geq 25.5$ mag bands, encompassing about $\sim 135 \text{ deg}^2$. Observations of satellites around isolated MC analogues will allow studies of satellite/host demographics in environments outside the influence of a massive host, such as the MW or Andromeda.

¹<https://delve-survey.github.io>

- DELVE-MC images $\sim 2200 \text{ deg}^2$ around the MCs in the $g, r, i \geq 24.5$ mag bands. While roughly half of the DELVE-MC footprint has already been covered to the desired depth by DES and SMASH, DELVE is in the process of supplementing the remaining $\sim 1100 \text{ deg}^2$ of the periphery with ~ 2200 new exposures. The model of [Nadler et al. \(2020\)](#) predicts that $\sim 30\%$ of the ultrafaint galaxies contained within the DELVE footprint are associated with the MCs.

These survey components offer complementary perspectives on the abundance and characteristics of satellite dwarf galaxies across diverse environments. When combined with a cohesive theoretical framework, DELVE has the potential of facilitating investigations into how satellite properties are influenced by factors such as reionisation, host halo attributes, and environmental conditions, thereby enriching our understanding of the galaxy–halo relationship (e.g., [Read et al. 2008](#)).

Central to the present analysis is the `simple`² algorithm, which identifies old, metal-poor stellar populations through an isochrone-matched filter approach. In the past, the `simple` algorithm has shown much success with not only the DELVE-WIDE catalogue (e.g. [Mau et al.; Cerny et al., 2020; 2021a; 2021b; 2023a; 2023b; 2023c](#), all including Sakowska) but also with other DECam and Pan-STARRS surveys (e.g. [Bechtol et al. 2015; Mau et al. 2019](#)). `simple` relies on pre-installed job scheduling packages such as HTCondor³ to organise and schedule multiple localised catalogue searches, thus permitting the user to contiguously search the entire data footprint on demand. However, as the number of survey data catalogues increases, the demand for research computing facilities also grows. Given not all research computing facilities permit users to install external scheduling packages, the number of computing resources available to run algorithms such as `simple` becomes limited.

In this Chapter, I develop the `simple_delvemc`⁴ package, tailoring it towards the DELVE-MC catalogue. `simple_delvemc` removes HTCondor dependencies and employs Python modules such as `multiprocessing`, thereby maintaining the algorithm’s scheduling capabilities. The new version not only circumvents the need for external scheduling packages, but its tailored nature facilitates parameter optimisation and diagnostic analysis, crucial for discerning genuine candidate detections amidst the data deluge. The DELVE dataset is openly accessible through the NOIRLab Astro Data Lab⁵.

5.3 Data and method

5.3.1 DELVE-MC

As mentioned above, the complete DELVE-MC survey will image $\sim 2200 \text{ deg}^2$ around the MCs in the $g, r, i \geq 24.5$ mag bands. Each DECam image is subdivided into further $0.^\circ 25 \times 0.^\circ 25$ overlapping tiles (“brick”) following the DECaLS tiling scheme. During my PhD, I have worked with numerous iterations of the DELVE-MC catalogue with different band and area coverage.

²<https://github.com/DarkEnergySurvey/simple>

³<https://htcondor.readthedocs.io>

⁴https://github.com/JoannaSakowska/simple_delvemc

⁵<https://datalab.noirlab.edu/delve/>

The DELVE-MC catalogue was reduced differently to DELVE-WIDE and DELVE-DEEP. DELVE-WIDE and DELVE-DEEP have been processed with the DESDM pipeline (Dark Energy Survey Data Management pipeline, [Morganson et al. 2018](#)). The DESDM pipeline was created to analyse galaxy photometry taken by the Dark Energy Survey in high Galactic latitude regions. DESDM is not optimised for stellar photometry in crowded areas with sky subtraction and de-blending of point-like sources being the most affected, resulting in less complete photometry and poorer object classification. Due to the significantly large stellar density in the DELVE-MC catalogue, the proximity of the MCs to the galactic plane, and the need to better account for the large dithers⁶ between overlapping DELVE-MC exposures, the DELVE-MC catalogue was processed with an updated version of the PHOTRED pipeline ([Nidever & Dorta 2020](#)). PHOTRED was effectively used as a base to process the SMASH survey photometry (SMASHRED). The new pipeline, called DELVERED, performs PSF photometry for individual exposures and then forced PSF photometry for overlapping exposures. This leads to a more accurate de-blending of sources. The DELVE-MC processing is described in full detail in [Drlica-Wagner et al.](#); [Drlica-Wagner et al. \(2021; 2022](#), all including [Sakowska](#)).

5.3.2 The simple algorithm

The `simple` binning suite uses an isochrone matched filter in the colour-magnitude space of two bands to identify and enhance old, metal-poor stellar overdensities in the data. For DELVE data, we apply a PARSEC isochrone ([Bressan et al. 2012](#)) with metallicity $Z = 0.0001$ and age ~ 12 Gyr old. In each area searched, `simple` scans the matched filter using a distance modulus from $16.0 \text{ mag} < m - M < 23.5 \text{ mag}$ (increasing by 0.5 mag). At each interval, the program selects stars within 0.1 mag of the isochrone locus in the colour-magnitude space according to $\Delta(\text{band}_1 - \text{band}_2) > \sqrt{0.1^2 + \sigma_{\text{band}_1}^2 + \sigma_{\text{band}_2}^2}$, where $\sigma_{\text{band}_{1,2}}$ correspond to the photometric uncertainties for the PSF magnitude measurements in the filters used (in our case g, r). This creates a ‘filtered’ density field. Next, `simple` smooths the field using a $2'$ Gaussian kernel, and identifies stellar density peaks through iteratively increasing the density threshold until less than 10 disconnected peaks are seen. Finally, the code computes a candidate list by calculating a Poisson significance for each of the density peaks by comparing the observed number of filtered stars relative to an annular background. The candidate list also include a distance modulus estimate and a dynamic radius estimate.

As mentioned in the introduction, one of the available versions of `simple` is suited for parallel, local catalogue searches on clusters hosted by institutes using job scheduling packages such as HTCondor (this is the case for DELVE-WIDE, who host their search at the University of Chicago). This version is not appropriate for us, as we do not have such packages installed on the Surrey clusters. Another version `simple_ad1`⁷ is adapted for SQL searching and pulling data from the online `AstrodataLab`⁸ database ([Nikutta et al. 2020](#)), which hosts public and private survey data from surveys such as DELVE or SMASH. While this later is useful for checking updated DELVE-MC photometry, in the long term it is unfeasible to run a contiguous dwarf galaxy search on an on-line catalogue given the slow download speeds and reliance on the status of the database. As such it is apparent that, in order to search the DELVE-MC catalogue locally

⁶Dithering is done by slightly moving the telescope in order to offset the exposures. This approach yields many benefits as it minimises the effects of bad camera pixels, sensitivity variations across individual pixels, ghosts from bright sources, amongst other photometric and astrometric benefits.

⁷https://github.com/sidneymau/simple_ad1

⁸<https://https://datalab.noirlab.edu/>

and contiguously, with the ability to fine-tune parameters and photometric cuts with updated catalogue releases, a new version of `simple` needs to be made.

I produced the `simple_delvemc` suite, which I host and maintain on github for the DELVE collaboration to use. The biggest differences are the following. Firstly, `simple_delvemc` permits the user to search a catalogue locally without the need for scheduling packages such as HTCondor. I have added a Python script which uses the `multiprocessing` package to let the user schedule multiple commands to the command line based on an input file. The user can now run a local search of the catalogue, even from their personal computer. There is also an option to set the number of cores to run on for a faster search time. The faster search time makes it easier for the user to adjust and test parameters (this is especially useful when working with an in-progress catalogue). Finally, to help the user discriminate candidates, I added extra diagnostic plots which I discuss more in Section 5.3.3.1.

5.3.3 Searching the DELVE-MC catalogue

Following Cerny et al. (2021a), I partitioned the DELVE-MC catalogue into HEALPix (Górski et al. 2005) pixels at `nside = 32`, corresponding to $\sim 3.4 \text{ deg}^2$ pixel areas. This is advantageous as the scheme ensures the searched area is large enough, and that the neighbouring HEALPix can be identified and overlapped, such that the detections are not disturbed by area borders. The scheme also provides the user with a system to track the areas in an organised manner and log any problems with the data.

The first set of preliminary searches of the DELVE-MC catalogue in 2021 produced a very large number of candidate objects. Even after capping the candidate significance estimate at $\sigma = 5.5$ (following Mau et al. 2020; Cerny et al. 2021a), the number of candidates ranged from 10^4 to 10^5 . On closer inspection it was clear that many of these detections are spurious, which made it very difficult to trust high probability detections.

5.3.3.1 Matters with DELVE-MC photometry

Unfortunately the reduction of the DELVE-MC data resulted in photometry issues which resulted in many spurious candidate detections that made it significantly harder to trust high probability detections.

One of the problems found in the first few catalogue releases was patchy coverage in the catalogue due to a significant number of bricks that failed during the processing stage. If photometric junk was identified near missing coverage, the detection's significance would be amplified (because either the detection looked isolated or its diffuse structure would be removed). In Figure 5.2 I show an example candidate output plot which is affected by this. The top left and top middle panels are the respective stars and galaxies. The overdensity, centred on a brick gap, is likely due to the missing brick coverage to the left and top. Similar looking overdensities are also seen in the stars and galaxy panels.

To make it easier to analyse the candidates, and help diagnose the photometry problems, I added a few extra diagnostic plots to the `simple_delvemc` outputs (the original outputs only the plots shown in the top left, top middle and bottom right panels of Figure 5.2). In the top right of Figure

FIGURE 5.2: An example of false candidate between overlapping bricks. The candidate was likely identified due to the coverage gap in the region which made overlapping stars and photometric noise look more isolated.

5.2 I show a spatial distribution plot; in black are all of the stars within a ~ 0.25 deg radius; in blue are the stars identified to lie within $\delta = 0.1$ of the isochrone in the colour-magnitude space (labelled as ΔCM). In red are stars that are within $\Delta CM = 0.1$ and either (i) three times the estimated radius of the detection or (ii) three times a pre-set radius value which we expect for a cluster/dwarf galaxy ($r = 0.025$ deg). In this case we use the detected radius. We clearly see that the detection is in a brick gap. In the bottom left and bottom middle panels of Figure 5.2 I plot the CMDs for the stars and galaxies respectively. In green I show stars that are within 3 times the measured overdensity radius, but are *not* within $\Delta CM = 0.1$, and in red are stars that are also within $\Delta CM = 0.1$. The two plots highlight a horizontal ‘strip’ of very faint ($\Delta g = \sim 23 - 24.2$) signal which is characteristic of photometric noise. The bottom right plot is a Hess diagram which informs us on the stellar density in the CMD- a significant portion of stars (yellow boxes) in the detection are most likely junk. This detection had a poisson significance of 7.2σ , which is of the magnitude we expect for a faint star cluster (DELVE 2’s significance on discovery was 9.1σ)

Another important issue found was that `simple_delvemc` is extremely sensitive to areas with a significant amount of field stars, so searching near the Large and Small Magellanic Clouds’ outskirts produced a lot of spurious detections. While this is not a photometry issue, rather a testament to the depth of the dataset, it makes a contiguous search much more difficult. Going forwards the search area should be carefully refined and focused on much less populated areas.

Also, I identified problems with how the processing pipeline handles photometric effects due to bright stars. As previously discussed, DELVERED is designed to preserve the very faint, point-like sources in data. This lets us preserve the faintest signals, makes it the optimum choice for finding stellar overdensities and is very advantageous over the DELVE-WIDE coverage in the Magellanic regions. Unfortunately, the downside of this approach is that a lot of photometric effects and unwanted noise are also preserved and misidentified as candidate overdensities. One example is the presence of ‘ghosts’, i.e. reflected or scattered light from bright stars. I show an example in Figure 5.3 of a bright star (Canopus) in the Carina dwarf galaxy near the LMC. Even if the star is removed, the reflections around the star still show up in the photometry. For DELVE-WIDE

FIGURE 5.3: An example of a bright star (Canopus, in the Carina dwarf galaxy) in the DELVE-MC catalogue. Even if a bright star is removed from an image the reflections around it, called ‘ghosts’, contaminate the nearby footprint and trigger false candidate positives.

and DELVE-DEEP, images affected by ghosts are identified and the objects discarded using the DES ray-tracing tool (Kent, 2013). This was not used in the DELVE-MC processing in order to preserve as much information as possible.

In response, I added the $\text{ndet} > 1$ parameter to the star-galaxy separation criteria. The ndet parameter checks if the object was detected more than once across the individual exposures- in theory, most photometric noise should not reproduce itself in multiple exposures. One could also check if the detected object appears in both the $g-r$, $g-i$ - but this depends on how much i band coverage is available in the catalogue version. Unfortunately, both approaches are not enough to fully remove ghosts (especially if they occur close to the star), but they can help with other cases of photometric junk (e.g. cosmic rays). Another solution is to edit the search area to avoid searching around bright stars. The stars that create ghosts would need to be manually identified and these regions cut out of the search. This would work for the project, but the best long-term solution for the quality of the catalogue is to incorporate an automated method to review and remove ghosts as the DELVE-MC coverage expands.

5.4 Results and future work

5.4.1 Ultra-faint stellar systems in the Magellanic periphery as seen by DELVE-MC

To quality check the catalogue, and further investigate any photometry issues, for every catalogue version I checked if known dwarf galaxies, clusters, ultra-faint dwarf galaxies, and clusters can be recovered by `simple_delvemc`. I selected known ultra-faint dwarf galaxies/clusters in the DELVE-MC footprint and identified the HEALPIX in which they belonged to. Next, I ran `simple_delvemc` in the HEALPIX to check if the object can be blindly found.

The ultra-faint dwarf galaxies I selected were: Pic-II, Ret-III, Tuc-III, Tuc-IV, Tuc-V, Hor-II. The ultra-faint clusters were: DELVE-2, Tuc-V, Torrealba. I also looked at the Ret-II, Hor-II dwarf galaxies. All of the objects were recovered, with the exception of Hor-II due to a coverage gap. Interestingly, Tuc-III and Tuc-IV were not automatically detected. After further inspection of the images available on `simbad`⁹ this is likely due to the presence of nearby stars which offset the detection hotspot. I show these candidate plots in Figure 5.4. For Tuc-III, the hotspot looks ‘pulled’ to the right (towards the direction of the bright star), and also the isochrone on the CMD is offset from the distinct MS. In Figures 5.5 and 5.6 I show the results for other ultra-faint clusters and ultra-faint dwarf galaxies. in the most recent 2023 DELVE_MC_y4t2 catalogue.

The current catalogue has greatly improved in terms of fixing coverage and photometry issues. In Figure 5.7 I show the candidate plot for the ultra-faint cluster Torrealba in both DELVE_MC_y2t2 and DELVE_MC_y4t2 catalogues. The missing bricks are fixed and, thanks to the additional exposures, there are many fewer brick gaps.

⁹<https://simbad.u-strasbg.fr/simbad/sim-fcoo>

FIGURE 5.4: Candidate plots for Tuc-III (top panel), Tuc-IV (bottom panel) ultra-faint dwarf galaxies from a blind search of the DELVE-MC-y4t2 catalogue. See text for details.

FIGURE 5.5: Candidate plots for selected ultra-faint clusters from a blind search of the DELVE-MC-y4t2 catalogue. Top panel: DELVE-2. Middle panel: Pic-I. Bottom panel: Tuc-V. See text for details.

FIGURE 5.6: Candidate plots for selected ultra-faint dwarf galaxies from a blind search of the DELVE-MC-y4t2 catalogue. Top panel: Pic-II. Bottom panel: Reticulum-III. See text for details.

FIGURE 5.7: The ultra-faint cluster Torrealba as detected by simple-delvemc in the DELVE-MC-y2t2 catalogue (top panels) and DELVE-MC-y4t2 catalogue (bottom panels). The DELVE-MC-y2t2 catalogue has more tiling gaps and missing brick tiles than the vastly improved DELVE-MC-y4t2 catalogue.

5.5 Conclusions and future work

I developed the `simple_delvemc` algorithm, an adaptation of the `simple` algorithm tailored specifically for the DELVE-MC survey, which has facilitated the detection of ultra-faint stellar systems, demonstrating the utility of localised catalogue searches without the need for external scheduling packages. The systematic partitioning of the DELVE-MC catalogue into HEALPix pixels has enabled organised searches and addressed issues with spurious candidate detections. Despite challenges related to photometric issues, such as patchy coverage and the influence of bright stars, the diagnostic tools integrated into `simple_delvemc` have helped in validating high-probability detections and pinpointing photometric problems. This rigorous validation process has ensured that most detected candidates are genuine, enhancing the reliability of the search results. The initial searches using `simple_delvemc` not only validate the effectiveness of the algorithm but also highlight the potential of the DELVE-MC survey in uncovering new stellar substructures associated with the MCs.

Building on the successes of the current analysis, I identify several avenues for future work to further optimise and expand the search for ancient, metal-poor stellar overdensities in the Magellanic periphery. These include:

- Improving the DELVERED pipeline to minimise false detections due to photometric noise, especially near gaps in brick coverage and bright star reflections. Implementing an automated method to review and remove ghosts could significantly enhance the quality of the catalogue.
- Developing more sophisticated diagnostic tools within `simple_delvemc` to further aid in the discrimination of genuine candidates from spurious detections.

- Expanding the search area to include less populated regions around the MCs to uncover additional ultra-faint stellar systems. Careful selection of search areas, avoiding regions with high field star densities, will be important.
- Combining the observational data from DELVE-MC with theoretical models, such as those predicting the properties of ultra-faint galaxies (e.g., [Nadler et al. 2020](#)), could provide deeper insights into the formation and evolution of these stellar systems. This integration will enhance our understanding of the galaxy–halo relationship and the impact of environmental conditions on satellite properties.

Chapter 6

Conclusions

The main goals of the present thesis have been to further the current understanding of the stellar content, evolution, and interaction history of the Magellanic Clouds (MCs) by performing a detailed study of the stellar outskirts and main body of the Small Magellanic Cloud (SMC). A key component of this has been the Survey of the MAgellanic System History (SMASH), described in Chapter 2, 3, and 4. In Chapter 5, I presented the work I have carried out with the DELVE-MC survey towards expanding our picture of the Magellanic periphery. Here, I summarise the main conclusions of this thesis.

6.1 Star Formation History in the Small Magellanic Cloud’s Outskirts: characterisation of the northeastern shell structure

The outskirts of the SMC present a treasure trove of substructures, many of which harbour clues as to its past interaction history with the LMC. I characterised a shell-like structure in the northeastern SMC, which is prominent in spatial distribution maps of young stars. Using deep SMASH Colour-Magnitude Diagrams (CMDs), which reach below the oldest main sequence turnoff (oMSTO), I computed the northeastern shell’s star formation history (SFH). I developed a new SFH method which accounts for the complex, elongated morphology, and disperses stars from their original positions, permitting a comprehensive age and metallicity derivation. By targeting red clump (RC) stars, I derived line-of-sight depth estimates of 7.06 ± 4.00 kpc. The derived SFHs revealed the young nature of the northeastern shell, with enhancements at ~ 250 Myr, ~ 450 Myr, ~ 650 Myr, and ~ 1 Gyr ago, the strongest being the one at ~ 250 Myr. I also identified a peak at around ~ 2 Gyr ago and no significant enhancements in the SFH for older ages. Comparison between the northeastern shell’s SFH and the LMC’s northern arm SFH (also derived with SMASH data) showed clear synchronicity in the SFH. I concluded that the complex processes of ram pressure stripping, tidal stripping, and circumgalactic medium (CGM) involved in the SMC/LMC/MW system over the past ~ 2 Gyr have played an important role in the formation of the northeastern shell structure.

6.2 Assessing the Star Formation History recovery and quantifying the line-of-sight depth effect uncertainties

I designed computational tests with mock stellar populations which scrutinised the ability of THESTORM (the suite I used to obtain SFHs) in recovering SFHs from SMASH data. I investigated the age/metallicity recovery of young, intermediate-age and old populations in both cases, where the CMDs are affected/unaffected by line-of-sight depths. I found that the age/metallicity recovery of singular, young (≤ 1 Gyr) 100 Myr enhancements from CMDs unaffected by line-of-sight depths is excellent, with little age dispersion. This result confirmed our ability to make detailed, high-level conclusions on the SFHs of the MCs over the last ~ 1 Gyr. With regards to the intermediate-age and old stellar populations, the age-metallicity resolution becomes coarser. Despite this, I was still able to recover SF enhancements at these ages, reaffirming our capability to make comprehensive, quantitative conclusions about the SMC's evolution at those times. Once a line-of-sight depth is present in the CMD, I show clear evidence that accounting for such an effect in the SFH derivation improves the age and metallicity recovery, especially in the case of large (21 kpc) line-of-sight depths.

6.3 Star Formation and Chemical Enrichment Histories of the Small Magellanic Cloud

After successfully developing and testing the updated SFH derivation methodology, I finally computed the spatially-resolved SFH and chemical enrichment history of the SMC's main body and periphery. I carefully examined over 31 deg^2 of the galaxy reaching as far as ~ 5.86 kpc from the SMC centre, greatly improving the coverage and age resolution presented in previous studies. The inclusion of the line-of-sight depth effect, which reached up to ~ 23 kpc in the northeastern and southeastern SMC, vindicates this work as the most comprehensive SMC SFH determination to date. I found that the SMC experienced extended star formation (SF) from its beginnings until around ~ 4 Gyr ago when the SF plummeted globally. The radially integrated SFH reveals that the SMC possess a positive age gradient, with multiple plausible causes discussed in the chapter. Nevertheless, the SMC experienced enhancements ~ 2 Gyr, ~ 1.3 Gyr, ~ 0.9 Gyr, ~ 0.5 Gyr and ~ 0.2 Gyr ago, including ongoing SF. The stellar mass formation and average metallicity maps presented here link all of those enhancements to the LMC (and to some extent to the MW), emphasising the co-evolution of the MCs. For the entire SMC, I obtain a mean metallicity, $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \sim -0.94 \pm_{0.07}^{0.06}$, and show that accounting for the line-of-sight depth for all regions results in metallicity determinations which are more in-line with spectroscopic studies (e.g., [Carrera et al. 2008](#); [Dobbie et al. 2014](#)).

6.4 Developing a pipeline for the detection of ancient, metal-poor stellar overdensities in the Magellanic periphery

Finally, I present my ongoing work towards a contiguous search of the Magellanic periphery for ultra-faint stellar systems with the DELVE-MC survey. I adapted and fine-tuned the simple algorithm, which has shown robust success in identifying old and metal-poor stellar overdensities

in DECam data. The adapted code, called `simple_delvemc` is suitable for the DELVE-MC catalogue. With repeated searches, I identified systematic photometric issues in the early versions of the DELVE-MC catalogue, which were successfully rectified in further editions. I demonstrated the efficacy of `simple_delvemc` in recovering known ultra-faint dwarf galaxies and clusters in the latest version of the DELVE-MC catalogue. Looking forward, `simple_delvemc` holds significant promises in discovering new ultra-faint objects in the Magellanic periphery that will contribute to advancing our understanding of the complexity of the Magellanic system.

6.5 Future prospects

While the present thesis has made strides in understanding the SMC, impacting different regions of the system including, for the first time, a careful simulation of the line-of-sight depth in the SFHs, significant avenues for further study remain. I outline here potential future directions, both experimental and theoretical, aimed at enriching our understanding of the orbital and interaction history of the Magellanic system. Building upon the SMASH dataset, the ongoing DELVE-MC survey will fill up the coverage gaps in the Magellanic periphery in the *gri* bands. With this information, we will be able to study the Magellanic periphery and inter-cloud region with improved coverage and resolution. I am heavily involved in the discussion and planning of the DELVE-MC artificial star tests and SFHs.

In terms of other upcoming surveys, the ground-based Vera Rubin observatory (formerly the Large Synoptic Survey Telescope; the LSST, e.g., [Ivezić et al. 2019](#)) will greatly enhance the photometric quality, area and band coverage of the Magellanic periphery. The 8.4-m diameter telescope, in Cerro Pachón (Chile), boasts an impressive 10 deg^2 field of view. Over 10 years the survey will make ~ 825 visits to the MCs - down to the ~ 24 th magnitude in *ugrizy* - producing stacked images that will reach the ~ 27 th magnitude. While this depth will not be achieved for the central region of the MCs (due to crowding issues), the Vera Rubin Observatory will provide a wealth of data on the Magellanic periphery and other components of the Magellanic system. As such, the Rubin Observatory will complement the area and band coverage of SMASH/DELVE-MC surveys. The upcoming data will not only be able to expand the SFH footprint of the Magellanic periphery but also shed light on the inter-cloud stellar debris and past signs of tidal interactions in unprecedented depths.

As previously discussed, the SFH presented here omits the inner regions of the SMC due to crowding issues. So *how* can we measure the SFHs of the central regions of the MCs, in a contiguous manner? While the Hubble Space Telescope has successfully obtained photometry of the most crowded regions which reached below the oMSTO (e.g., [Cignoni et al. 2012](#); [Cignoni et al. 2013](#); [Weisz et al. 2013](#)), the HST's pencil beam field of view sacrifices coverage. The near-IR James Webb Space Telescope (JWST; e.g., [Gardner et al. 2006](#)) launched in 2021 does not have the wide-field view of the MCs, and the recently launched Euclid telescope (e.g., [Euclid Collaboration et al. 2022](#)) will not cover the LMC in its footprint. NASA's upcoming Nancy Grace Roman Space Telescope (Roman telescope; e.g., [Akeson et al. 2019](#)) holds significant promise. Roman's 0.28 deg^2 field of view (approx. ~ 1 full moon) and its infra-red abilities offer the best compromise between contiguously imaging the central bodies of the MCs and depth. The infrared band will significantly help diminish the photometric errors due to interstellar reddening and dust. As of writing, I am part of a group that has expressed an interest in proposing a Roman

space telescope survey of the Magellanic bodies, with the expected call in Summer 2025. The next few years are proving tremendously exciting for the Magellanic Clouds!

Appendix A

Spatial Star Formation and Chemical Evolution Histories of the Small Magellanic Cloud galaxy

Below I present the spatially-resolved star formation and chemical enrichment histories corresponding to 76 Voronoi bins on the SMC, as defined in Figure 4.1.

Region 2

Region 3

Region 10

Region 11

Region 12

Region 13

Region 20

Region 21

Region 22

Region 23

Region 26

Region 27

Region 28

Region 29

Region 30

Region 31

Region 32

Region 33

Region 36

Region 37

Region 44

Region 45

Region 46

Region 47

Region 48

Region 49

Region 50

Region 51

Region 58

Region 59

Region 60

Region 61

Region 64

Region 65

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